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Distance Education Perspectives and Practices of Educators in an Allied Medical Program: A Grounded Theory Approach within the Phenomenological Tradition

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Biographical Sketch

The author, Maria Freya T. Carungcong, CSP-PASP, is a graduate of B.S. Speech and Language Pathology (SLP) of the University of the Philippines, Manila. She specializes in managing communication disorders, speech and language disorders in children. She is currently the SLP unit manager and clinical supervisor of the Neurodevelopmental Center of De LaSalle University Medical Center. She has spearheaded free therapy, teletherapy and charity services in the municipalities of Dasmaringas and Imus, Cavite. She is an active member of the Philippine Association of Speech Pathologists (PASP). In 2020, she was a contributing author on the Telepractice Working Guidelines of PASP and was a speaker for benchmarking Telepractice of SLPs in the Philippines.

She became a faculty member of the College of Rehabilitation Sciences of De LaSalle Health Sciences Institute in 2016. Practicing in the academic field and having a curiosity in distance learning made her decide to take the course Masters in Distance Education at the University of the Philippines Open University.

Aside from being a clinician and an educator, she is also a dedicated mother and cyclist. With her free time she enjoys relaxing by the beach and cycling around NCR and CALABARZON with her family.

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ABSTRACT

Framing the study within the Phenomenological Tradition, it asked the questions why do educators engage in distance education. To discover the meaning and purpose of distance education to educators in the allied medical field the study looked into the perspectives of the educators and their practices in Distance Education.

The phenomenological tradition with the methodology of the grounded theory approach was applied in this study to gather data, analyze and understand the accounts of six teachers in an allied medical program at a private university. The phenomenological tradition in research can obtain authentic data by providing open ended questions and flexibility that may allow the participants to narrate salient events and experiences significant to distance education. By applying the strength of the traditional qualitative research approach to a methodical approach in data analysis, theory is built thru the analysis of relationships thru the components revealed within a phenomenon (Brower 1995, in Jeong, 2009).

The outcome of the study presented the phenomenological model of distance education in an allied medical field that provides the perspectives, practices in teaching and transitioning to distance education. The study generated the TIE Theory on distance education that explains the essence of distance education. The TIE theory states the following on distance education: a) **T**ransitioning to DE involves planning and provision of accessible learning resources to provide a formal mode of distance education that can promote the quality of life of the educators and the learners, (b) **I**nstructional designing and technology are intertwined in the teaching practices of DE to address transactional distance and secure the integrity and quality of education, and (c) **E**ducation that is equivalent to face-to-face mode of education that uses

varying modes of communication to address the needs of the learners, achieve learning and program outcomes and expand educational services.

The TIE Theory can be the framework of distance education in allied medical education. With this theory, institutions would be able to provide an explanation for practicing DE in allied medical education and be guided when conducting needs assessment and program evaluations to maintain the quality of education.

Keywords: Distance Education, Allied Medical, Grounded Theory

Chapter I

RATIONALE

Distance Education

The description of distance education (DE) had several revisions from when it was first introduced. The evolution of its description has been influenced by various factors such as technology and pedagogy. Holmberg (1974, in Keegan, 1980) described DE as having a separation between the teacher and learner; that involves planning of an educational organization that makes it distinct from other learning online platforms such as YouTube and Google. Moore's (1975, 1977 in Keegan, 1980) definition highlighted three elements: (1) the separation of teaching behaviors and learning behaviors, (2) the use of technical media and (3) the possibility of two-way communication. Keegan (1980) described DE by highlighting its different elements. According to Keegan (1980), DE is a mode of education that geographically separates the learner from the educator that allows dialogue or communication, uses technology, and is supervised and guided by an educational institution. Description of distance education mostly highlights the nature of DE and its various elements. Questions are still raised in the given descriptions. Saykili (2018) raised a question on the form of separation noted by Keegan (1980) between the learner and the educator given the technological innovations that may influence the description of separation in today's context. Distance education has been taking into different forms and has been reshaped to other forms of learning such as massive open online courses, mobile learning, and network learning. Bozkurt and Zawacki-Richter (2021) described distance education as dynamic and constantly evolving due

to a variety of factors such as sociocultural, demographic, political and technological influences.

The first issuance of Distance Education in the Philippines by CHED was in the year 2000 (Sabio & Sabio 2013). There are significant aspects in distance education that are different from the traditional education that contributes to the effectiveness of the distance education program. As Stern (2004) noted, not all programs are ideal for distance education. Distance education requires a lot of complex skills such as technological skills, content development, and instructional designing (Arinto,2016). The key point to address the different challenges of Distance education is planning (Sabio & Sabio, 2013). There are a few institutions known for delivering distance education in the Philippines ,such as University of the Philippines Open University(UPOU), Polytechnic University of the Philippines (PUP), Philippines Women's University (PWU) and Pamantasan ng Lungsod ng Maynila (PLM), however none of these institutions provide allied medical courses/ programs through distance learning.

Distance education is considered to be a more cost-effective way of providing and receiving education (Aries, J. J., Swinton, J. Anderson, K. 2018). During the pandemic it is considered as a safe alternative for delivering education without the worry of spreading the Covid-19 virus. However, there is always a debate when transforming education into a different modality such as distance education, and that is its equivalence to the traditional mode of education. There are still doubts if distance education can achieve the same result of competency and learning outcomes of the traditional mode of education. Results of the effectiveness of distance education in the different course programs vary depending on the instruction, courses offered, the students and their different learning styles (Stern,2004).

Distance education has both its advantages and disadvantages. Interaction among students and educators should be systematically and/or strategically designed in a course program to ensure that this element does not inhibit learning. Distance learning has the advantages of providing the capacity for students to get back to their lectures, interact with their classmates and content in their own time and store important information that will assist their learning (Stern,2004). Learning online provides the following benefits: (1) having the storage and ability of retrieval of the learners' interaction with concepts that can be used for later analysis, and (2) the learner gains more control and opportunities from immediate feedback the learner receives (Hargis,2001). With these advantages in distance education, it can be argued that this mode of education has the potential of making learners understand the course program and can be an effective mode of education if it goes through strategic planning and evaluation.

The concept of distance education has evolved from a novel mode of education to a conventional mode of education due to the pandemic. Nowadays, given its advantages and disadvantages, this mode of education is currently being applied by educational organizations and institutions in normal and emergency situations. The meaning and concept of distance education has continuously been changing due to modernizations, technological innovations and an individual's point of view. This research aims to obtain information on what distance education is, to the faculties of BS SLP program of the study site, to gain a more conceptual depth to the meaning of DE.

Comparison of Face To Face Education to Distance Education

There is a clear distinction between delivering distance education from the traditional face to face education. In distance education, the geographical separation of the learners from their co-learners and educators would require the use of technology to deliver content and facilitate interaction. Transactional distance was introduced by Moore (1973, Delgaty,2018) as the interplay of the content, the learners, and the instructor. It is the gap that results in misunderstandings, that can be addressed through improving dialogue or the communication between teachers and students, and the structure of pedagogy in Distance education. In Delgaty's (2018) critical review of transactional distance, he noted that the dynamics of these 3 variables in the transactional distance theory: dialogue, structure and autonomy are important to deliver a successful distance education.

Stern (2004) noted that online and face to face education were both an effective mode of education with some considerations in the American educational courses. Having considerations on the students' learning styles and instructional design were identified as critical factors for the effectiveness of an online course to be at par with the face-to-face program (Stern,2004). In other fields such as the business communication class, Tucker (2001) noted the lack of significant difference in the final course grades of students in the face to face education and distance education. In the field of Medical education, it was reported that in distance education recorded lectures and live streams replaced classroom-based discussions (Ferrel & Ryan,2020). Faculties noted that real time and immediate feedback during traditional class discussions are hard to replicate in distance education (Ferrel and Ryan,2020).

Adis (2009) noted that both modalities, face to face and distance education were successful in achieving the expected outcomes of the course and that online learners had more appreciation for lifelong learning and use of technology. Collaboration was noted to be easier with the face-to-face mode of education (Adis,2009). Teachers and online students of an undergraduate educational technological course needed time to adjust with the new learning environment and the use of technology in distance learning.

Literature noted that there is a distinction in terms of communication, interaction, technology, infrastructure, instruction, and perceptions of effectiveness between distance education and face to face or traditional education. With the innovations in technology and teaching strategies the definition and distinction of distance education from other modalities of education in different programs have been continuously evolving. It is therefore critical to gather data from different fields of education and stakeholders to gather information on the different aspects of distance education to gain a holistic understanding on this mode of education.

Challenges to of Educators in Delivering Distance Education

Educators during the pandemic had to deal with complicated situations to transform traditional education to online education. Adjustments were needed to restructure the content and curriculum, while educators are encouraged to explore novel modalities for delivering online and virtual education (Kachra & Brown. 2020). Given that distance education is a novel modality for the traditional educators, transforming a program into this modality would require an in depth understanding of distance education. O'Doherty, et al. (2018) identified that technical skills, educator skills can be both a barrier and a solution in providing distance education in medical

courses. Their study highlighted the importance of identifying the challenges in delivering medical education online to be able to keep up with the digital generation of today's education. The recent study by Al-Balas, et al. (2020) on distance learning conducted to medical students during their clinical years identified 3 types of barriers for an effective distance education. The researchers categorized these barriers according to technology/ infrastructure, institutional/ educators, and student barriers. These barriers included limited access to the internet, infrastructure, and lack of proper training.

Changes in pedagogy can be complicated and challenging for both the institution and the educators (Arinto, 2016). Aside from the technical skills, Arinto (2016) noted that teaching online would require skills in content development, learning activities, teaching strategies and assessment. Grimmer-Somers et. Al (2011) conducted a research on the best practices in E-Learning for allied health clinical education and training. The study revealed that distance learning has limitations in developing higher clinical skills and teaching interpersonal skills. Their study noted that there should be consideration of the different learning styles of students in designing an allied health program for distance education.

Sareen and Nangia (2020) conducted a study in India on attitudes and challenges faced by educators during the pandemic. The study revealed that lack of online teaching experience results in the difficulty of teaching for most educators. Lack or limited understanding and familiarity with the use of educational software for teaching may have contributed to the following challenges: lack of appropriate materials and resources, technical problems, lack of in-service training, difficulty in assembling all the students for the class, lack of cooperation from the parents, lack of

internet facilities of the students, and difficulty to follow up the learning of students (Sareen, S. And Nangia, A., 2020).

Providing clear and concise feedback was noted as essential by both faculty and students in distance education (Rajab M H, Gazal A M, Alkattan K, 2020). However, communication and technology were one of the challenges noted in the study of Rajab, et. Al (2020) when they conducted research on the challenges to online medical education during the COVID-19 Pandemic. Apparently, fear of technology was not a dominant issue. Student's online assessment, access to computer hardware or software, technical issues, time management, limited experience with online education and pandemic- related stress and anxiety were identified as challenges in online teaching and learning. Garrison (2000) noted that the challenge of distance education in the 21st century is to understand the limitations and opportunities of facilitating teaching and learning with the use of different technology and methods.

The Relationship Between Perspective and Practice of Distance Education

As distance education is continuously being provided as a safe alternative for traditional education, there are only a few faculties who have received formal training to understand and deliver DE. The depth of understanding on distance education of educators in allied medical programs in the Philippines has not yet been explored. Literatures on DE presented varying concepts of DE. It has evolved based on technological, pedagogical innovations and point of views of stakeholders. Related literature on DE would list a variety of parameters on its effectiveness for educational programs that may depend on different perspectives of the stakeholders. As noted by Bozkurt and Zawacki-Richter (2021) distance education is dynamic and constantly

evolving due to a variety of factors such as sociocultural, demographic, political and technological influences.

The ontological position of this study is that there is an existing variance on the meaning of distance education. The epistemological position of the study is that the meaning of DE can be derived from multiple realities and that it is influenced by the knowledge and experiences of an individual or the society.

Obtaining perspectives of all stakeholders is integral in improving and determining the quality and efficiency of a course program. According to Ulewicz (2017) stakeholders both internal and external were noted to have a substantial impact on the effectiveness of educational programs. Educators are one of the primary internal stakeholders of education since they are responsible for designing curriculums and delivering education to the students.

The Relevance of the Study

Allied medical courses have been delivered through face-to-face mode of education here in the Philippines. Due to the pandemic, transformation of traditional allied medical courses to distance learning was needed for the students to continue their education and to reduce the risk of acquiring Covid-19. Last March 2020 allied medical courses were transformed from the traditional face to face education to distance education and has continued to do so with the continuing school year. This is the 2nd school year that allied medical courses are being delivered online. Most of the educators of the BSSLP program have not undergone formal training or formal education on distance education. With this context, understanding distance education may vary depending on the participants' influences, personal research, experiences and knowledge.

The Bachelor of Science in Speech and Language Pathology (BSSLP) of the selected study site is an allied medical program that was initially offered in the year 2014. It was designed and delivered in a face-to-face mode of education. Courses in B.S. SLP program is divided into pre-professional courses for the first- and second-year level, professional courses for the 3rd year level and clinical courses for the 4th year level. With the surge of COVID -19 cases in different countries, the World Health Organization declared COVID-19 as a pandemic on March 11, 2020 (World Health Organization, 2021). Due to the pandemic, there was a sudden transition from face-to-face mode of education to distance education. The pandemic became a catalyst for the nationwide implementation of distance education in the Philippines. Educators in all educational levels – elementary, high school and tertiary – were given seminars, webinars, and workshops to prepare them to deliver distance education. With this transition, all SLP courses in this institution (pre-professional, professional and clinical courses) were transformed to distance education with the premise that it can deliver the same learning outcomes as of the traditional mode of instruction. Instructional designs were revised and reconstructed to be able to target the learning outcomes of the B.S. SLP Program. Traditional educators instantly became distance educators without formal training and education on delivering and designing distance education.

Being a part of the faculty of the BS SLP program of the study site, the researcher has observed different approaches and strategies in their transformation of traditional courses into distance education. Given that there is no existing formal study on distance education in the allied medical programs on the selected study site, there is ambiguity among the faculty on the appropriation of distance education in the BS SLP program of the study site. The study aims to reveal the meaning of distance

education from the point of view of educators of the BSSLP program of the study site who had experienced it and had no formal education of DE.

Information on how educators understand distance education may contribute to the conceptual depth of this mode of education. The study may also reveal the appropriation of this modality to the BS SLP program. Furthermore, information obtained in this study will help identify significant components in distance education that institutions should address when transforming a face-to-face program into DE in an allied medical course. Information obtained from this study may influence course designs and teaching strategies. With these assumptions, this study may further contribute to improving the quality and delivery of the B.S. SLP program.

With this research, information on what actually happened and what is going on in Distance education in an allied medical program in the Philippines can be revealed. The results of this study may further provide answers on the appropriate mode of education for the BS SLP program of study site and can serve as a guide for institutions in transforming and delivering allied medical programs to distance education. It may also identify areas of interest that would need further research.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

There are varying perceptions and perspectives on distance education since it was initially introduced. Perceptions and perspectives may seem similar, however there is a clear distinction between them. Perceptions refers to the way a concept is understood by the 5 senses that may be influenced by experiences, feelings and thoughts and can be affected by perspectives, on the other hand perspectives are an individual's point of view or the angle on how the concept is received; that can be influenced by attitudes (Hasa, 2016). This distinction would result to varied descriptions of distance education depending on the approach of the researcher to define this mode of education.

Perceptions on Distance Education

Literature has shown that the perceptions of distance education vary across the different levels of education, educational programs, and the stakeholders. Various studies identified different perceptions on distance learning from students and educators. The studies have shown that perceptions on distance education can be influenced by multiple factors.

It can be noted that the perceptions on distance education based on quantitative and mixed studies vary, depending on the stakeholder, level of education and program. The appropriation of distance education for a specific program may vary based on the perceptions of the stakeholders. An example of this is the students' perception of DE in an ECG course in Germany. Distance education that has a pure online course was perceived as an inadequate replacement for the traditional face to face mode of education for the ECG course in Germany (Keis et. Al,2017) . This

perception is based on 10 medical students that were interviewed. Keis et. Al (2017) identified intrinsic and extrinsic motivational factors as influencers on the student's preference on the mode of education. Extrinsic motivations were noted as having timeframes for working on topics and having external support, while intrinsic motivation includes providing individual feedback to students (Keis et. Al,2017). Having varying forms of interaction among the students and with the lecturers were noted to be important. In other fields of education such as Medical Imaging Technology, Medical Laboratory Technology , Operation Theatre and Anesthesia Technology and Nursing distance education, students noted that distance education as a satisfactory mode of education but with limitations on the development of practical knowledge (Debnath et. Al, 2021). Practical knowledge was described as questionably achieved by the students. Debnath et. Al (2021) further suggested the development of online simulation tools and blended learning to further develop practical skills. Students listed the use of e-content, various online webinars, online case reports, and assignment submission to provide distance education. Most of the institutes listed different software such as the Google platform as their primary application, supplemented by other applications such as Zoom and Edmodo (Debnath et. Al, 2021) .

Perception of distance learning of students from multiple allied medical health programs namely Doctor of Physical Therapy (PT), Master of Physician Assistant (PA), and Bachelor of Science or Post- Baccalaureate Professional Certificate in Medical Imaging and Therapeutic Sciences perceived distance education as an effective mode of education for delivering the curriculum. Faculty training, purposeful engagement and setting clear expectations were identified as key strategies for an effective distance education (Becker et. Al, 2018). The importance of technological

training of both students and faculty, existence of technological issues and the importance of having technical support to aid in addressing these challenges were highlighted in this study.

For an interdisciplinary course for students in the courses of Dentistry and Speech Pathology, distance learning was perceived as an effective modality of education or as a complementary material in formal learning programs (Ramos et. Al,2015). The effectiveness of distance learning was based on the presentation and quality of the content, audio-visual quality, adequacy to the target public, and information made available (Ramos et. Al,2015). Collaboration with other professionals in the field of pedagogy, information and technology and instructional design were suggested to further improve distance learning for the aforementioned course. Distance education in allied medical programs were noted to have a more of the synchronous instructional model and instructional design was identified as an important aspect in the effectivity of distance education (Williams,2006) .

A systematic review by Koet and Aziz (2021) on the perceptions of teachers and students towards distance learning during the Covid 19 Pandemic revealed that there are varied perceptions which can be influenced by social, technological, and pedagogical factors. It was noted that the lack of experience of students and teachers in distance learning has an influence on their perception. Distance learning was perceived as a supplemental teaching approach to formal education instead of a new mode of education by educators. Distance learning was also perceived as worth embracing for its capacity to provide education without the risk of spreading Covid 19 (Koet and Aziz ,2021). The level of engagement of teachers with their students was identified to be the most influential factor in the perception of distance learning. Teachers who have better interaction among their students, effectively utilize and

manage their time would have more invested students and would result in better motivation for educators to embrace distance learning. Koet and Aziz (2021) further recommends looking into the perspectives of students and teachers in the tertiary level on a specific course to gather relevant information in improving the program and policies.

Perspectives on Distance Education

The instructors' description of distance education in medical and public health programs were described to be as an acceptable and useful mode of education during the pandemic (Zhu and Zhang, 2021). The instructors identified transforming the clinical and lab sessions, and some areas of pedagogy as challenges in distance education. Instructors noted that some clinical and lab sessions cannot be replaced by online learning. The instructors emphasized the importance of hands-on sessions for students to be able to practice and establish relationships. Importance of course design was highlighted and blended mode of learning for clinical and lab sessions were suggested.

Nabolsi et. Al (2021) investigated the experiences in online distance education of faculties in a nursing program using a phenomenological approach. The study revealed that online distance education was provided mandatorily due to the Covid19 pandemic. Faculties described distance education, as having to learn to provide pure online teaching independently with their available resources, redesigning and implementing their student modules. Distance education was described as an interruption to personal time management wherein boundaries between work time and rest were vague, in contrast to the traditional education. Furthermore, Distance

education in the nursing program was described as insufficient in achieving learning outcomes and clinical competencies (Nabolsi et. Al , 2021).

Previous literature described Distance Education as a mode of education with unique challenges depending on the level of education and its program. Nabolsi et. Al (2021) noted that the faculty members in his study had to overcome several challenges in distance education that includes learning and training for distance learning, designing, and implementing online materials, lack of technical support and dealing with the limitations of their available resources for distance education. Limitations in technology and infrastructure were listed as the challenges of the faculties. Student engagement was identified as the most challenging, due to lack of readiness of the students for distance education. Nabolsi et. Al (2021) further noted that DE provided a new learning experience, however it affected the educators' personal time management and time frame boundaries. Limitations on achieving clinical competencies and learning outcomes were also identified.

In Turkey, teachers, administrators and academics of distance education listed the lack of infrastructures, difficulties in internet access, classroom management and human resources as aspects where the teachers had the most difficulty when delivering distance education (Sari & Nayir, 2020). Slow internet and poor connection would result in technical problems. The following were also listed as challenges of DE: readiness for distance education, communication, monitoring and maintaining student's attention and interest in class, lack of knowledge and training in distance education(Sari and Nayir,2020).

On the perspective of adult learners in criminal justice courses, adult learners were noted to appreciate both DE and traditionally based classrooms (Hannay & Newvine, 2006). However, the students noted that distance learning was more

appropriate for the older student population or commuter campuses instead of the undergraduate population aged 18-21 years old, which is considered as the campus-based population. Distance Education was noted to be appealing to students who multitask or for those who have several commitments (Hannay & Newvine, 2006). This perspective was also reflected in a study of educators and students who have no experience on distance learning before the pandemic period. that used mind genomics by Todri et. Al (2021) Distance learning was perceived as a learning platform that pushes students towards rational thinking; appropriate for the working population, has a more individual approach and should have interactions similar in the classroom setting. Distance learning was noted to be successfully used as a complementary approach only, compared to the traditional mode of education (Todri et. Al 2021).

Chapter III

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The Phenomenological Tradition of Distance Education Research

The discipline of phenomenology in research is the study and exploration of a phenomenon from the perspective of those who have experienced it to seek and describe its essence (Neubauer et. AL, 2019). Phenomenology is a philosophy, a methodology or an approach that has several types that is qualitative (Neubauer et. AL, 2019). The principles of phenomenology focus on the perception of the people or perception of events and things that is presented or occurring. Phenomenology are mostly based on recognition of the subjective and experiences of an individual and their description of their experiences (Sloan et. Al, 2014, Patton 2002). The study of phenomenology can obtain authentic data by providing open ended questions and flexibility that may allow the participants to narrate salient events and experiences significant to distance education. A detailed study and exploration of an individual's experience provides us with new insights of a specific phenomenon that allows researchers to gain knowledge and learn from it. Phenomenology has different types, but for this research we will just be differentiating 2 types of phenomenology; the transcendental and interpretative or hermeneutic phenomenology, all of which are rooted from the experiences of the subjects extracting its essence to explain the phenomenon. Transcendental phenomenology sees the researcher as a blank slate that explores the subject's experiences without any assumptions, to obtain a description and understanding of the phenomenon. Hermeneutic or interpretative phenomenological tradition is rooted not just on the description of the individual's experience but goes beyond the interpretation of the phenomenon that are influenced

and circumscribed by the subject's life world, that the researcher is aware of. The interpretive process of hermeneutic phenomenology includes the interplay of multiple analysis that is not bound to a single set of rule-bound analytical techniques that goes beyond the descriptive understanding that can provide insight in a complex phenomenon (Neubauer et al., 2019). The hermeneutic or interpretative phenomenological tradition involves deep engagement which broadens the understanding of phenomena such as distance education in an allied medical program.

In phenomenological philosophy the grounded theory analysis has the researcher consciously interpreting and orienting himself or herself with the data, that goes through a process of interpretive understanding to uncover the underlying theory (Jeong, 2009). The consciousness of the theory is considered as part of the process of data analysis in a grounded theory methodology that is rooted from the philosophy of interpretative phenomenology (Jeong, 2009). With this grounded theory analysis, constructivist perspective is conducted to determine common patterns, themes, or categories in relation to the understanding of distance education across the qualified participants. By applying the strength of the traditional qualitative research approach to a methodical approach in data analysis, theory is built through the analysis of relationships through the components revealed within a phenomenon (Brower 1995, in Jeong, 2009) With this premise, the constructivist grounded theory methodology was applied in this study. Grounded theory involves the process of organization and categorization of data to be able to generate a theory that explain the behavior and actions of individuals in a given context (Burns et al., 2022). The methodology of constructivist grounded theory is noted to be interpretivist in nature wherein the researcher is involved in the interpretation and discovery of

meaning; and that there is an interactive process in the grounded temporal, cultural, and structural contexts of the subjects' reality (Charmaz 2000, p.523 in Burns et. AL ,2022).

The Research Questions

The main question of this study is why do educators in an allied medical program engage in DE?

The general objective of the study is to answer this question by understanding the meaning of distance education to educators in an allied medical program at the tertiary level. The meaning can be derived by answering the following sub questions:

- a) What is the perspective on distance education of educators in an allied medical program?
- b) What are the educators' practices in teaching and transitioning to DE?

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Chapter IV

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The Grounded Theory Approach

Grounded theory methodology aims to discover or generate theories from the experiences of the participants (Cresswell, 2007). Constructivist Grounded theory emphasizes diversity and multiple realities that lies within the interpretative approach, wherein the researcher and participants are co-constructors of the theory (Charmaz 2005,2006 in Cresswell, 2007). In this study the researcher gathered different experiences of the target participants in delivering distance education in their assigned SLP courses, from the data gathered the researcher generate an explanation of the process, action , interaction and how individuals experience the phenomenon. Constructivist Grounded theory approach involves gathering rich data, coding, memoing and the use of theoretical sampling (Cresswell,2007). The grounded theory method allows the researcher to synthesize and analyze data beyond the given description by constructing new concepts that explain the given situation (Charmaz & Thornberg,2021). Charmaz (2000, in Mill et. Al 2006) noted that the discovered reality in constructivist grounded theory would arise from the interactive process, temporal, cultural and structural context. In this process the researcher positions as the observer and immerses in the narrative of the participants, including raw data from theoretical memos and embedding the narratives of the target participants in the research outcome (Charmaz,2000, in Mill et. Al 200).

Grounded theory research involves meticulous iterative and recursive processes (Tie et. Al.,2019). Grounded theory research consists of the following process: purposive sampling, collection of data, constant comparative analysis,

memoing, coding, theoretical sampling, generation of grounded theory, and theoretical sensitivity.

Purposive sampling is the process where the researcher selects qualified participants who are capable of answering the research questions through online interviews. From the data gathered, codes and categories were identified and analyzed.

Coding is the analytical process to look for concepts, discover similarities and recurrences in the acquired data (Tie Et. Al, 2019). Coding was conducted in 3 stages which are: Initial, intermediate and advanced coding. In the initial coding comparison of data was conducted to look for concepts, similarities, differences, patterns, and meanings attached to each concept. This involves comparative analysis of data and memoing. Memoing are informal analytic notes and records of the researcher's thoughts, feelings and intuitive contemplations on the data gathered (Tie, Et. Al, 2019). These are critical information that provides a trail of how the researcher was led to different ideas and reflections.

Intermediate coding took place after theoretical sampling has been conducted, as this builds more concepts and identifies core categories from the initial categories revealed in the initial coding. Theoretical sampling is the process where the researcher follows up on a lead revealed in the initial coding that may provide significant information to the research question and may contribute to the evolving theory. This was done by sending of questions thru the Viber messaging application that will further clarify or confirm information, concepts or categories revealed in the initial coding until the data reaches theoretical saturation.. Theoretical saturation is the point where there is no new information or themes emerging from the data (Guest et al.,

2006 in Low,2019). Intermediate coding involved constant comparative analysis, theoretical sampling, and saturation for the grounded theory to emerge. These processes, theoretical sampling and saturation strengthens the research analysis and provides material that will support the claims of the grounded theory, contributing to the quality of the study (Charmaz & Thornberg, 2021).

Advance coding would involve the storyline technique of Birks and Mills (2013, on Tie Et. AL., 2019), theoretical coding and integration. The story line technique involves the conceptualization of the core category and a comprehensive rendering of the grounded theory. The storyline technique connects identified categories in order to build a story (Birks and Mills, 2013, in Tie Et. AL., 2019). Storyline allows the researcher to provide a cohesive and comprehensive explanation for the grounded theory.

Theoretical sensitivity is the ability of extracting data that is relevant to the emerging theory; and it encompasses the ground theory research processes (Birks and Mills, 2013, in Tie Et. AL., 2019). This is a critical process allowed the researcher to uncover significant concepts or constructs that contributed to the grounded theory.

Figure1: Data Analysis Framework

(Image from Tie Et. Al, Research design framework: summary of the interplay between the essential grounded theory methods and processes, page 3, 2019).

The Research Site

The BSSLP program is a 4-year higher education program that is currently provided by 4 institutions in the Philippines. The BSSLP program consists of 160 units of general education and professional courses (CHED CMO 59, 2017). The BSSLP program aims to produce competent Speech and Language Pathologists that can provide Speech and Language Pathology services to different population and settings. The program was initially introduced in a face-to-face mode of education by the University of the Philippines Manila in the year 1978 (Cheng, et. Al. , 2002). offered the BS SLP program in the year 2014-2015, initially offering the course program as a 5-year course in accordance with the Commission of Higher Education (CHED) Memorandum Order No. 29 series of 2011 (Alcantara, 2015). By the year

2017, the course curriculum was modified by CHED into a 4-year program, as stated in CHED Memorandum Order no.59 series of 2017.

Distance education in the BSSLP program was non-existent until the pandemic was declared on March 11,2020. From this day and the next coming school year, specifically SY 2020-2021, the BSSLP program of the study site was transformed into distance education. Currently there are no existing records for providing distance education in the BSSLP program of any institution providing the BS SLP program here in the Philippines. There are also no current formal records providing distinction of the BSSLP program in the traditional or face to face mode of education from distance education.

Research instruments:

The primary research instrument in this study was the researcher. The researcher was responsible for the accumulation of data through observation, constructing and providing questions that will concretize the experiences of the target participants. The questions provided to the participants were guided by the research questions. Follow up questions were provided on the reactions and responses of the participants

The following research instruments were also be used for this study to facilitate interaction, acquire, encode and store data: (1) Hardware: Computer, Laptops, Video camera and recorder, (2) Software for online communications and encoding of data: Google applications: Google Mail and Google drive, Mind Map and Microsoft office, (3) Software for online interview and messaging: Viber Google applications: Google Meet, Google Mail and Google drive, and Microsoft office, (4) Software for data collection and storage: , Google applications:, Google Mail and Google drive, and

Microsoft office, (5) Software for storage: Encrypted Google drive and (6) Internet connection and (6) Software for data analysis: Mind map, Google docs and Microsoft office.

Ethical Issues In The Research Implementation:

Communication with the target participants was conducted following the proper line of communication and organization of the SLP Department. Permission was initially requested and granted by the department's program director before the research was able to communicate directly to the participants. Consent from all selected participants was acquired for them to engage in the interview and express their opinions and narrate their experiences. Agreement and consent forms containing detailed information of the objectives of the study, time consumption of participation was provided thru Google mail to the participants to ensure that they are aware of all the risk; that participation is voluntary and acquired data will be used for the sole objective of the study. Participants were given the option of anonymity and assigned with pseudonyms.

Any data on specific information of the learners such as grades or demographic information that were obtained from educators that was revealed by the researcher will be kept confidential. Information gathered will be for the sole purpose of the objectives of the research. The researcher informed all participants on her willingness to sign a nondisclosure agreement to secure the intellectual property of the institution. Permission and acknowledgement of ownership was accomplished and applied to information that was e used in this study.

All data shared abides to what is allowed by the institution and its policies on security and privacy of data. Data acquired from the participants can only be accessed

by the researcher and was kept in an online drive secured with the researcher's password and username. Transcribed data were reviewed and amended by the participants. Participants were given permission to delete data shared if there would be a breach in confidentiality and privacy agreement between the researchers.

The Research Participants

Selection of participants

Participants were the faculties and administrators of the program B.S. Speech and Language Pathology (BS SLP) of the study site. The study used the following Inclusion criteria: (1) Qualified faculty and administrators should be teaching in the BSSLP in the selected study site for at least 1 school year. and (2) they should be SLP faculties and administrators who delivered and supervised an SLP course in both modalities, traditional and distance education. Participants with the following criteria were excluded from the study: (1) Faculties who have taught a course on a single mode of education: either face to face only or distance education only will not be qualified to participate in this study, (2) faculties of other institutions, colleges, and other departments and (3) faculties who taught the same courses but with different curriculums will not be eligible to participate in this study.

Profile of the Participants

The researcher initially asked permission and assistance from the department's program director to conduct interviews and identify qualified faculties who have transformed BSSLP courses into distance education. 7 faculties were identified and invited to participate in this study. 6 out of 7 faculties agreed to take part in this study. All faculties have been practicing for more than a year in the SLP

department. 4 of the participants were faculties and at the same time were administrators of the SLP Department. All participants were graduates of the B.S. Speech and Language Pathology programs from institutions here in the Philippines. One of the participants is a degree holder of Master of Science in Speech Pathology from a University in the U.S. Another participant has a Master's degree in Clinical Audiology. 3 of the participants are currently taking their Master's degree in Health Professional Education, Clinical Epidemiology and Master of Rehabilitation Science - Speech Pathology in the University of the Philippines. None of them has received formal education on distance education. Table 1 provides a list of faculties with their assigned pseudonym, their roles in the SLP department and the online courses that they have transformed to Distance Education.

Table 1*Faculties interviewed and their transformed BSSLP courses*

Pseudonym	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6
Role in the SLP Dept	Faculty and Administrator	Faculty and Administrator	Faculty	Faculty	Faculty and Administrator	Faculty and Administrator
BSSLP Courses transformed to Distance Education	Voice disorders ,Research 1 and Research 2	Acquired Language and Cognitive Conditions, Dysphagia, Introduction to Audiology, Introduction to Diagnostics, Anatomy and Physiology for SLPs, Neuroanatomy for SLPs, Counseling, Intervention and Aural Habilitation	Aural Habilitation, Clinical Internship and Senior Sem 1	Articulation, Voice Disorders, Dysphagia And Clinical Internship	Fluency, Introduction to Audiology, Introduction to Diagnostics	Language Development and Language Conditions

The Data Collection and Analysis

Interview of Participants

Data were gathered through an individual semi-structured online interview using the software Google Meet and Viber messaging. Semi-structured interviews consist of a few predetermined questions that will allow the interviewer to probe and explore on issues or salient events that will be raised by the interviewee (Mc Grath et. Al,2019). Interactive and iterative in-depth interviews was conducted to gather the different views, beliefs, values and opinions of the target participants. The online interview consisted of the following to ensure the voluntary participation of the target participants: (1)Confirmation of agreement and consent to participate in the research, (2) Brief orientation of the research, and (3) introduction of participants and (4) assignment of pseudonyms. Follow up questions were sent using Viber messaging application. All interviews were recorded and transcribed in detail. The transcriptions of the initial interviews were sent to the participants through their email for amendment and validation. Each participant was requested to sign the validated transcription of their interview.

As I was transcribing the interview I would identify categories and get in touch with the participants thru the use of Viber messaging or online video conferencing to further probe on emerging categories in their initial interviews. In this manner I was able to seek clarification, probe more on a certain concept to be able to add depth to the concepts and categories that were raised and identified.

Initial coding

With each transcript I began sorting out concepts and categorizing information. Several concepts arise as I went through each transcription of each participant. . The following tables shows the list of concepts that I have collected from the 6 interviews that were considered relevant and has significance on distance education.

Table 2
Summary of Initial codes of P1-P6

<p>Voice disorder Motor speech condition, Research Recording Prerecorded lectures Work from home Minimizes the risk of contracting the infection Workload More tasks Reports Student assessment Extra work Mismatch with the expectations Adjust Working from home Time with family Free time Lecture Class activities Online video conference platform Adjust the task to make it more feasible in the online setting Online video conference platform, Course learning outcomes and program outcomes Differences during F2F Worksheet Video demonstrations Supplementary videos Accessible websites Innovative Online assessment Workload of student Bandwidth requirement Platform</p>	<p>Provide accommodations Communicate with email Learning management system Feedback Synchronous Short messaging applications PowerPoint presentations Video editing Adobe photoshop Complex materials for teaching Webinars for teaching online Ensuring quality of education Effectiveness of online education Similar to face to face. Passing and Attrition rate Faculty evaluation Similarities Performance Course curriculum remotely Facilitating teaching learning strategies Interaction Accommodation/changes Meetings Aural Hab Senior sem 1 Resistance Platform Exams Teaching style Modalities Lost in translation Preparative Environment Trainings Planning Transition there was resistance</p>	<p>Reklamo Outcome measure Training Orientation Transition Concerns Self-directed learning Articulation Voice Disorders Dysphagia Internship Formative activities Rubric Accommodate Similar experience Delineate Responsibilities at home Audiology Diagnostics Translated into online Support Ease of use of technology Materials online Capacities of our students Laboratory sessions Security Experience the same hands-on learning Translate some of the requirements Technological knowledge Online materials. Technological assistance Monitoring</p>	<p>Systems Assistance Platforms Learning experience Expectations Language development Fluency Language conditions Team effort Content Formative activities Consultation Summative assessment CHED, the government regulation body Program evaluation SWOT [<i>strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats</i>] analysis Paradigm shift Teaching process Delivering the same content, but thinking out of the box Student-directed Student-oriented Framework Technology Technical support</p>
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Memoing

Memoing according to Tie, Et. Al (2019) are informal analytic notes and records of the researcher's thoughts, feelings and intuitive contemplations on the data gathered (Tie, Et. Al,2019). This information is critical to reflect ideas and reflections that may lead to theoretical thinking. My position as both the researcher and a faculty of the study site gave me a vantage point on understanding the experiences of my colleagues as they were transforming their courses. As I was listening to the narratives of my colleagues whom I personally witness some of their struggles during the transition from face to face to distance education, I realized that I was in a greater advantage during these times since I already had formal education from the University of the Philippines Open University. My formal education in instructional designing, assessments and management of distance education helped me in transforming my own courses. The participants raised a lot of aspects that I agree are critical elements for distance education. Here are the thoughts that transpired while I was listening and transcribing to the interviews.

Time and Workload

Most of the participants were anxious of the overwhelming amount of workload to transform their courses into distance education. Time was limited for the participants to accomplish the necessary tasks and it seemed to take a toll on everyone when they were transforming their courses. Most of the participants emphasized the number of tasks they needed to do to be able to transform their courses. I considered looking into these tasks that they had experienced to understand how much they should accomplish to deliver distance education in the courses they are handling.

Technology

The use of both hardware and software seems to be a significant factor that eased their process in transforming their courses. Internet connection and the learning management system was highlighted by most of the participants as a factor that eased their transformation of courses to DE. As part of the faculty of the SLP department of the study site, I personally was able to experience the learning management system the participants were referring to. It helped me understand better the challenges and tasks they experienced in transforming their course using this system. I noted that majority of the faculty got oriented to different software such as Zoom, Google Meet for them to conduct their classes and facilitate teaching and learning activities. Given its critical importance in delivering distance education, most of the challenges noted by the participants are observed to be related to technology such as lacking or having limited knowledge on a specific software and establishing and maintaining connections online either asynchronously or synchronously.

Teaching and Learning Strategies

Almost all of the participants provided very detailed descriptions on how this has a significant difference in the distance education from face to face education. The importance of having an appropriate instructional design in both modes of education, distance learning or face to face was highlighted in most of the narratives.

Assessment

This aspect was consistently mentioned by all participants in their narratives. Almost all assessments in all of the courses underwent major transformation. Concerns and issues on security of assessments and test construction were noted by almost all participants.

Course and Learning Outcomes

I noted that almost all faculties use the learning outcomes and program outcomes as their guide in selecting content and providing different teaching and learning activities that they consider will target and elicit these set learning outcomes and program outcomes the course. This was consistent in both modes of education, face to face and distance education. I opted to ask all participants on the significance of the learning outcomes and program outcomes in designing their courses and was able to retrieve a constant response.

Communication

Without the participant's knowledge on the transactional distance as proposed by Moore as being existent in distance education, it seems that these educators have identified its presence in their experiences in communicating the content, interacting with their students and trying to understand the knowledge gap in their students. Most of the participants experienced a significant difference in communicating with their students for providing feedback and clarifications. Most of them felt the gap where they weren't sure if the students understood the content being delivered at the time of their lecture either in synchronous or asynchronous classes.

Leadership and Support

Leadership and training seems to play a significant role to motivate and allow changes in the current mode of education. This somehow served as a catalyst that enabled the faculty to transform their courses to distance education. There seems to be that looming presence of doubt among the staff in the introduction of distance education, however the pandemic gave the faculties no choice but to accept the changes in the mode of education. It was the leadership of their administrators that motivated them to accomplish the transformation of their course to the best of their abilities despite the overwhelming amount of workload that needed to be done during

those times. Given that the faculties noted an overwhelming amount of workload, having good technical and faculty support also played a significant role in pacifying their frustrations and anxiety; and helped in the transformation and provision of distance education in their courses. The presence of support was noted as an important element in keeping the staff motivated to accomplish the transformation of their courses.

Equivalence with F2F

I was surprised that most of the faculties noted equivalence of content, learning outcomes and program outcomes of their courses in both face to face and distance education. Almost all of them noted that accomplishing the learning and program outcomes was their guide in selecting teaching learning strategies and activities for their students.

Training

I noticed that most of the participants had to attend training provided by the institution and independently learn other skills that are related to management and use of different technologies needed for delivering their courses. Some of the participants noted that aside from the training provided by the institution they also relied on external resources and self-study to learn the different skills needed such as managing or manipulating the different software needed to transform their courses to distance education. I noted the presence of technology in all of their courses and the importance of having the technical knowledge in using and managing the variety of software and hardware needed to deliver their courses.

Intermediate and Advanced Coding: Categorizing Concepts

Intermediate coding occurs after initial coding and theoretical sampling has been applied in the initial interview. In this process core categories have emerged as the researcher tries to find connection and direction on the concepts that were raised in the initial coding. With repeated comparative analysis of the interviews among the participants common categories and concepts were connected. In this stage, I had to constantly compare and consolidate the responses of all the participants. Comparison of common categories and initial indicators that arises in their responses in the initial coding was conducted repeatedly.

Advance coding involves the storyline technique to integrate all the concepts and categories that arose in the initial and intermediate coding. I have discovered 3 core categories that will be discussed in the next paragraphs with supporting statements from the participants. These 3 core categories unraveled during the constant comparative analysis of the narratives retrieved from the participants of this study.

Here are the categories of the concepts that arise from the participants' responses:

A. Perspectives of Educators on Distance Education (DE)

1. Equivalence to face-to-face mode of education
2. Communication and interaction
3. Contributions of DE

B. Teaching practices in DE

C. Practices in Transitioning to DE

1. Planning for DE
2. Promoting Quality of life
3. Provision of Accessible Learning resources

The Core Categories, their Subcategories & the Respondent's Utterances

A. Perspectives of Educators on Distance Education

Table 3.

Equivalence to face-to-face mode of education

On Course and program outcomes	<p>We still want to achieve the course and program outcomes regardless of the mode of delivery (P1, line 104)</p> <p>Ensure that Program outcomes and year level outcomes are being achieved (P1, line 91-92)</p> <p>Did not lose the outcomes that were set (P2, line 83-84)</p> <p>Course outcomes nahihit naman (P3, line 29-30)</p> <p>Course outcomes and learning outcomes wala siyang masyadong difference (P3, line 32-33)</p> <p>Makikita mo naman kung nahit mo naman yung course outcomes(P3, line 114-115)</p> <p>Outcomes didn't really change that much during from face to face to online learning (P4, line 88-89)</p> <p>We're still able to achieve those learning outcomes even if they were provided online.(P4, line 91-92)</p> <p>We're able to adjust to it and still target our learning outcomes and program outcomes (P4 line 171-172)</p> <p>Ensure that the outcomes we have set for all of the courses that we are running are being met.(P5, line 105-107)</p> <p>We were able to achieve all those outcomes that we have set, even if the mode of delivery was very different, so it was a learning experience also for us to broaden our perspective (P5, line 170-172)</p> <p>Expectations and the outcomes that we have for the face-to-face , courses, we were able to replicate it in the online mode of teaching (P5, line 176-178)</p> <p>I always go back to the program outcomes and the year level outcomes. So if they're hitting those outcomes (P6, line 163-164)</p>
Effectiveness	<p>Effectiveness of online education is similar to face to face.(P1, line 114-115)</p> <p>Satisfied with their (the student's) performance (P1, line 120-121)</p> <p>I was pretty satisfied with the way the students' outcome– final outcome were made (P6, line 213-214)</p> <p>Passing and Attrition rate did not drastically change (P1, line 117-118)</p>
Quality	<p>Ensuring that the student receive the quality education (P1, line 106)</p> <p>Provide quality education for our students given that we're at home (P4, line 161)</p>

Table 4

Communication in DE

Communication	<p>Face to face I feel yung communication line parang mas mabilis nasasabi natatanong agad kung meron di naiintindihan (P3, line 561-562)</p> <p>I think the difference would mostly be being in front of the students and giving them 1 on 1 feedback (P4,line 108)</p> <p>Components that DE cannot provide -posture, expressions, small physical reactions can be pick up better if f2f (P2, line 337-343)</p> <p>You don't know what's happening to them at home kasi we don't require them to open their cameras (P2, line 390-391)</p> <p>I also feel sometimes things get lost in translation like in a classroom setting i would honestly know kung di naintindihan (P3, line 69-70)</p> <p>Hindi lahat nakakapagsabi kung naiintindihan nila yung material right there and then during the lecture itself (P3, line 72-73)</p> <p>Missing yung actual na interaction with the patient (P3,line 565-566)</p> <p>Limited interaction with actual patients (P2, line 63)</p> <p>We're not there to really monitor whether they're listening or not (P3, line 664-665)</p> <p>Cannot see them f2f and facilitate the activity f2f (P1, line 137-138)</p> <p>Sometimes some students were hesitant in asking questions during online classes since everyone is listening I think so I think they had worries about that (P4, line 109-111)</p>
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Table 5

Contributions of DE

Teaching and Learning	<p>Faculty evaluation of the students provide more positive comments on quality of feedback in online education (P1, line103-105)</p> <p>Benefits of having the lecture recorded because the students who didn't understand, they can go back to certain parts lang and then clarify (P2, line 316-317)</p> <p>Students making most of the material that is given to them (P2, line 318-319)</p> <p>Everyone was comfortable with the camera already (P2, line 314-315)</p> <p>A lot of the components are more honed since we had to do it online. The planning , how the students plan for the sessions is so much better now, compared when they were doing it face to face (P2, line 325-328)</p> <p>Better written communication (P2, line 336-337)</p>
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<p>Teaching and Learning</p>	<p>What's good about seeing both ends like the DE and the face to face, you also see how different kinds of learners respond to stimuli (P2, line 398-400)</p> <p>DE provided us with the opportunity to look into those things and to be more inclusive also because one's factor that de has provided us is that we were able to reach students who are not within the area of the institution like they're from different areas (P2, line 425-427)</p> <p>It provided us with a wider net for expansion and consideration of the needs of others (P2, line 430-431)</p> <p>It does work for some students like some students who might be too quiet or might be too shy when they are in the classroom might do work really well while they're on DE (P2, line 431-433)</p> <p>To a certain extent (DE) allows them also to connect more personally with the faculty members at a more personal level because we communicate regularly with them either through email or yun nga through direct message on chat (P2, line 433-436)</p> <p>(DE) it allows us to be more inclusive (P2, line 437)</p> <p>The advantage of doing online classes, is yun nga everything is recorded they get to play it back when they don't understand something (P3, line 154-156)</p> <p>Things are recorded so they can playback (P3, line 152)</p> <p>Appropriate for some subjects that do not require physical manipulation (P4, line 141-142)</p> <p>DE provides opportunities for the students to perform the SLP skills needed given that they are learning online (P4, line 166-167)</p> <p>It's a new way of being able to teach these concepts and teach these skills without the need for physical interaction, while ensuring that you know, your objectives are all being met (P5, line 186-188)</p> <p>Distance education for me is you know being conducting education activities in a nonphysical manner, in an online manner (P5, line 181-182)</p> <p>We are more outcomes-based like we geared towards more OBE [outcomes-based education] when we migrated to online versus when we were doing it face-to-face (P6, line. 189-191)</p> <p>More student-directed (P6, line 240-241)</p> <p>Distance learning actually forced me to be student-oriented, it forced me to be more creative in eliciting you know, the skills that are needed (P6, line 242-243)</p>
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The above analysis ended up in the following figure.

Figure 2. Perspectives of Educators on Distance Education

B. Teaching Practices in DE

Table 6

Teaching Practices

<p>Teaching practices</p>	<p>It was very clear to us that it was just going to be a shift in the method of delivery but there was never going to be a change in the content of the... and the outcomes needs to be met. (P2, line 251-253) Basic course did not have much issues (P2, line 93) Nakakapagturo pa rin kami kahit yung mga skill based tapos naasses pa rin namin yon (P3, line 30-31) Pareho lang ang demand (P3, line 62) I don't think there's a lot of difference kase the topics were maintained ganon tapos kahit papaano nahihit parin yung outcomes (P3, line 63-64) Naretain namin yung other outputs like evaluation report and case management (P3, line 84-85) Not much difference in terms of skills (P3, line 156-157) Lahat naman ng ginagawa on a face-to-face nagagawa pa rin naman siya when we are doing ano online intervention (P3, line 158-159) Lectures were or the topics given were the same (P4, line 93) The content will won't really change, it's just a matter of like preparing the outputs (P6, line 32-33) Delivering the same content, but thinking out of the box (P6, line 238-239) There were differences during F2F (comparing it to DE) (P1, line 40) Worksheet had to be accomplished electronically (P1, line 46) Some of the activities were not applicable to other students with different type of learning styles (P4, line 41-42) Difficult to adjust (P4, line 42) Concerns in motivation; Self Directed Learning (P3, line 203-204)</p>
<p>Teaching Principles</p>	<p>What you're doing is routed on you know your philosophies, your theories these are ideals you know that your only modifying your teaching and learning activities (P2, line 267-268) I just go back to rely on the program outcome and I go back to the videos that were made during the previous summer about the online evaluation (P6, line 231-232) It's a paradigm shift on your teaching process (P6, line 236-237) The framework was already how do you learn and how are you going to learn this material and with all the constraints that are happening and without changing the outcomes and how the program was designed. (P6, line 246-249) I was concerned about is the different learning um, capacities of our students (P5, line 50-51) Concerned if courses that needed to do laboratory sessions (P5, line 64) Laboratory sessions using simulations, using um, actual materials, sometimes, even actual patients and it was something that we were worried about because again it is very new in that particular manner (P5, line 46-49)</p>

	Ensure that learning isn't shortchange or sacrifice (P5, line 55-56)
Course and Learning outcomes	Course learning outcomes and program outcomes stayed the same (P1, line 38-39) Achieving set course year level and program outcomes (P1, line 133-134) Make alternative plans for them, how do we ensure that we still get to meet the outcomes that we have set for the course (P2, line 61-63)
Technology for teaching learning	Using online video conference platform like Google Meet or Zoom (P1, line 28) Online video conference platform (P1, line 37) (P5, line 68-69) Not confident about video editing (P1, line 66) Cannot use adobe photoshop to prepare more complex materials for teaching (P1, line 80-81) We had difficulties communicating with students who had poor internet connection (P4, line 40-41) not everyone has the same technological knowledge (P5, line 896) LMS for posting lecture materials (P1, line 64) Use Video conferencing (P1, line 76) Using ppt presentations (P1, line 80) Using Google forms to facilitate peer evaluation(P1, line 100) Easier to deliver course online since we already using LMS: Using Online exam (P1, line 102-103) Learn to navigate and be proficient in using Learning apps, LMS and Videoconferencing (P1, line 145-146) We are already utilizing zoom and had Moodle(LMS) (P2, line 149) We had Moodle to share lectures and get submission of the students that helped in the transition (P2, line 26-29) Use Moodle (P3, line 499) Bandwidth (P1, line 49), (P2, line63), (P3, line 546) Utilize (Google) meet and zoom (P2, line 103) Change sa platform (P3, line 07) Nagbago din yung LMS (P3, line 08) We already have a system (LMS) in place that we just had to utilize (P5, line 27-28) Lectures for blackboard (their LMS) (P3, line 46) You can make your exams there (in the LMS), you can post your lectures, provide forums, everything essential into ensuring that the discussion is still dynamic even if it's not face-to-face. (P5, line 147-149) We use zoom, since zoom had a direct message option there are some students who would send questions to me via direct message(P2, line 404-405) LMS [Learning Management System]. -Without the learning platform, i think it's going to be a very disorganized; the advantage of course of having a learning platform that is paid has all these extended services. (P5, line 141-144) The learning system that we are using basically if you understand it and you know how to maneuver it and use it to your advantage as a teacher, you wouldn't have problems(P5, line 145-147) Gumagamit din ako ng mga ibang modalities halimbawa h5p (P3, line 36-37)

Technology for teaching learning	<p>We had to research yung sa zoom kung paano gamitin yun then kailangan namin itrain sarili namin and yung intern din paano gamitin yung zoom, materials for internship (P3, line 21-23)</p> <p>We developed, a Google form wherein people will write in their questions in that form (P6, line 83-84)</p> <p>Communication: mostly email, madaming email, madaming discussion forum (P3, line 74-75)</p> <p>Asynchronous or synchronous yung line of communication- email and forums (P3, line 78-79)</p> <p>Used the learning management system (P1- P6)</p> <p>Using the whiteboard, annotate function zoom to exemplify further the concept (P1, line 78)</p> <p>Google forms for example to facilitate peer evaluation (P1, line 85)</p> <p>Internet is a concern for some students (P2, line 57-58, P4, line 14-15)</p> <p>There was no orientation regarding the LMS I remember ha parang it would have ease kung meron yon (P3, line 149-150)</p> <p>Concern about the student's internet connection (P4, line 14-15)</p> <p>Concern about students who did not have stable internet connection and not ready for online service delivery at home ,(P2, line 175-176)</p> <p>I (Educator) had problems with my internet connection (P4, line 15-16)</p> <p>Bandwidth considerations (P1, line 55-57, P2, line 63, P3, line 60)</p> <p>poor internet connection in specific areas (so that)contributed greatly to the difficulties (P4, line 75-76)</p> <p>We have different levels of our ease of use of technology (P5, line 35-36)</p> <p>Surprised that a lot of universities (in the Philippines) do not have LMS (P6, line 252-253)</p>
Communication	<p>Communicate with students Using institutional email (P1, line 54)</p> <p>Synchronous sessions (P1 line 36, P3 line 506, P4 line 16-17, P5 line 23, P6, line 48)</p> <p>Use short messaging applications (P1, line 59)</p> <p>Only Difference is that we don't interact directly or f2f with students (P1, line 115)</p> <p>Meron kaming phone in question ganyan so sasagutin ko lang (P2, line 470)</p> <p>We also have online forum where people can post questions and thoughts anonymously (P6, line 80-81)</p> <p>Comfortable facilitating activities used in f2f: Raising questions, waiting students to respond thru chat or opening cameras (P1, line 76)</p> <p>F2f feedback can be given right away but for online it's always gonna be via email, written communication that takes a lot of turnaround time that added a lot to the workload (P2, line 242-244)</p> <p>Make sure that even if we're all online we want to feel connected (P2, line 145)</p> <p>You have to confirm and validate what's happening to them and if it was a face-to-face class then it's gonna be easier because you see the groups already working together. (P2, line 394-396)</p> <p>During classes the group chats really helped having the group chat with the faculty (P2, line 282-283)</p> <p>We schedule meetings like for example after class and then we just talk about what happened in class and it helps you process the things that happened (P2, line 285-287)</p> <p>You try to engage your students as much as you can (P2, line 389)</p> <p>They (students) were never given a time to process (the transition to online education) (P3, line 148-149)</p>

Assessment	<p>Consider more factors in online assessment, workload of student, bandwidth requirement, platform (P1, line 56-57)</p> <p>Use LMS for quality academic assessment and for accreditation (P1, line 96-97)</p> <p>Making the Practical exam thru synchronous video call (P1, line 36)</p> <p>Adjust the method of evaluation of the students (P2, line 97)</p> <p>Answers are readily available on the internet, so the main adjustment there was that we did multiple cameras, so one camera for viewing the exams and another to view the student as they were actually completing the exams (P2, line 100-103)</p> <p>We had to ask them to record themselves and perform the techniques or the assessment procedures on their family members .instead to the teachers or the instructors of the course (P4, line 35-37)</p> <p>We had to just view the videos that they submitted (P4, line 37-38)</p> <p>Implementing more secure measures in the conduct of the exams (P5, line 77)</p> <p>Created a mandatory setup that would enable the facilitators of the exam to see the environment of the student while taking the exam, to see what the students able to access during the conduct of the exam (P5, line 78-81)</p> <p>We ask them to do dual camera setups when they use their laptops and another device just for us to be able to see them while they take the exam (P5, line 82-84)</p> <p>Recorded evaluation (P3, line 82)</p> <p>Additional preparation before the exam halimbawa yung kapag written exam na revalida pag panel presentation we had to check yung environment kung meron bang kodigo yung mga ganung bagay (P3, line 89-92)</p> <p>Summative assessment was very different because the lower order thinking questions were delivered uh, during weekly quizzes. (P6, line 91-93)</p> <p>When we migrated online we had a lot more case analysis and application questions during the output (P6, line 96-97)</p> <p>They (the students) were asked to apply the topics during that period (P6, line 100)</p> <p>We also took time to give them feedback individually, unlike before, we just gave return the paper and then, the case analysis sessions were done in groups, so the student wasn't given individual feedback on his or her understanding of the course. (P6, line 106-109)</p> <p>During the migration, the group activities were scaled down into individual output (P6, line 109-110)</p> <p>More formative output (P6, line 123-124)</p> <p>We were able to translate some of the requirements, some of the written exam requirement into other outputs, projects, papers all the other outputs that would still be reflective of their learning without sacrificing the measurement that we need to see for what they have learned and how we are going to move forward. (P5, line 85-89)</p> <p>Providing formative activities and then providing feedback for students and also providing a more specific rubric for each of the activity provided and then discussing it to the students helped in facilitating those activities (P4, line 67-69)</p> <p>The exams were transformed into an online modality (P4, line 27)</p> <p>There were specific techniques or assessment procedures that the students were expected to do so we had to change into online modality (P4, line 33-35)</p> <p>We provided very detailed guidelines written in verbal guidelines for these students (P4 line 45-46)</p> <p>Innovative ways to assess same skills online (P1, line 45)</p> <p>Yung mga exams yon written exams to online na (P3, line 516-27)</p> <p>We tried to at least provide the um similar experience for practical examinations or writing paper, writing evaluation reports, writing activity plans, or writing therapy plans so we tried to provide a similar experience with the face-to-face methods (P4, line 94-96)</p>
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Assessment	<p>For the practical examination so we had just like in face-to-face sessions we had a an online room where it was just the instructor and the student, and then the student will perform (P4, line 98-99)</p> <p>There is a rubric the students were able to perform skills needed for the online practical exam. (P4, line 102-103)</p> <p>We had the students observe different videos of patients and they had to create evaluation reports and then we would provide them a rubric and then write their evaluation reports, provide comments, and also grade them using that method (P4, line 103-106)</p> <p>I gave a lot of individual work and then I give, I gave several formative activities for them to complete (P6, line 64-65)</p> <p>I gave like two or three formative activities, and it's scaffolded (P6, line 68)</p> <p>The only difference is how we assess ; pag skills paano mo siya itatranslate into online (P3, line 64-65)</p>	
Challenges of Assessment	<p>challenging was finding creative or innovative ways to assess the same skills online we know that esp. clinical skills are needed to be demonstrated by students. It was kinda challenging to find ways on how to actually assess the skills even if we were just conducting it online. (P1., line 52-55)</p> <p>Giving them 1 on 1 feedback (P4, line 109)</p> <p>Yung actual interaction with the patient and sa mismo mag din planning magfa facilitate ng actual na eval and intervention yon mejo nawala yon (P3, line 86-87)</p> <p>The difference would be providing sometimes the feedback given to students are individualized in DE. Some students would email questions and then sometimes those questions will be or are not heard by the other students so we had to provide them extra effort to share what their classmate asked and then how we answered (P4, line 111-116)</p> <p>Concern is the integrity of how the students would be able to respond to the quizzes and the exams. (P2, line 99-100)</p> <p>There was a question of- you know, how do we ensure the security of our exams, how do we uh, ensure that there are no avenues for certain people to not be completely honest or diligent; honest with completing their requirements (P5, line 58-61)</p>	
Teaching and Learning Strategies and Activities for DE	Lectures	<p>Recorded na lectures (P3, line 26)</p> <p>Prerecorded lecture (P1 line 09,P3 line 524)</p> <p>Migrate those lectures into the online format either synchronously or asynchronously (P5, line 22-23)</p> <p>Meet the students on time and run the lecture live (P5, line 23-24)</p> <p>Lecture presentation were more or less the same (P1, line 26-27)</p> <p>Lecture no major changes for the activities (P1, line 29)</p> <p>Modifying yung mga lectures (P3, line 25-26)</p>
	Adjustments On other Teaching And Learning Activities	<p>Adjust class activities (P1 line 23-24, P2 line 171, P3 line 56, P4 line 24, P5 line 53,</p> <p>Adjust the task to make it more feasible in the online setting (P1, line 34-35)</p> <p>Majority is adjustment phase (P3, line 51)</p> <p>DE all of it were transformed to electronic (P1, line 39-40)</p> <p>Big adjustments that we can't do because of physical social distancing or the pandemic; Providing lectures, adjustments in assessing the students; adjustment in handling sessions or intern sessions that are conducted online so I think those were the adjustments (P4, line 162-166)</p>

<p>Teaching and Learning Strategies and Activities for DE</p>	<p>Adjustments On other Teaching And Learning Activities</p>	<p>Worksheet accomplished electronically(P1, line 40) Students had to adjust with sudden change (P1, line 59-60) Provide accommodations (P1, line 52, P3 line503) Provide feedback (P1-P6) DE is delivering course curriculum remotely (P1, line 133) Facilitating teaching and learning strategies (P1, line 133) Having them (the students) upload videos (P1, line 121) Structuring the program (P2, line 47) Introductory courses helped them (the students) it was a way to guide them(P2, line 52) Sacrificed Dysphagia - activities that require palpation (P2, line 78-80) Translating everything and delivering online. (P2, line 104-105) Teaching and learning were able to convert it online completely (P2, line 123) Asynchronous (P2, line 124, P3 line 15, P5 line 23) Showcase some outputs of students and view it like an expo (P2, line 147-148) View materials students did and learn from each other (P2, line149) We had to provide feedback as soon as possible (P2, line 220) We do breakout rooms. (P1, line 147, P2, line 453, P5 line 154) Kailangan kong um palitan or mag isip ng accommodation (P3, line 11) We just had to identify yung kailangan naming gawin for synchronous (P3, line 14) Kailangan namin identify pano namin mababago yung outputs na usually required for face to face (P3, line 16-17) Titingan mo muna kung akma kung alin dun ang pinaka okay na material bago mo siya incorporate sa lectures mo. (P3, line 37-38) Orientation with students (P2, line 223) setting expectations Easing them (with the transition) (P3, line 181-182) Made big adjustments to accommodate the changes from face to face to online (P4, line 08) We had to accommodate and then provide another session for them to be able to attend to their activities (P4, line 79-80) We had to describe in very detailed manner on how to how would the students gain their experience on how to touch patients or how to provide hands on experience given that we're in a virtual modality (P4, line 85-87) Identifying that we have would need to be translated into online (P5, line 12) All the students would be informed of how things will be running (P5, line 17) When we do synchronous sessions, we still encourage discussions, recitation, group work even if it's online (P5, line 152-153) Breakout rooms for example that would be the venue for certain students to come together and discuss and as teachers, we can just jump from one forum to another (P5, line 154-157) For asynchronous sessions, what i have been doing is providing a forum for discussion, so even if the interaction isn't live or directly online or on time, at least using the forums the opinions and questions still be expressed and</p>
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<p>Teaching and Learning Strategies and Activities for DE</p>	<p>Adjustments On other Teaching And Learning Activities</p>	<p>response from the teachers would still be provided and the advantage there is since it's written, or it's typed the students can actually go back to the discussion at any point in time (P5, line 157-162) Having to look at, requirements, the flow of the discussion, all of the aspects that we have put up and constantly comparing them to the outcomes that we have set for the course. (P5, line 167-169) We were more focused now on ensuring that each and individual student is learning because we are teaching it in a different way (P6, line 42-43) Preparing the materials (P2, line 142, P3, line 123, P6, line 49) I have to ensure that these students really understood the main ideas of the subject (P6, line 59-60) I had a lot more consultation periods during the class itself (P6, line 73) The way I setup the online is that I gave a lecture for two hours and then independent work for one hour and then, group discussion again after one hour (P6, line 75-77) Group didactic wherein like they teach one another and then, when someone does not understand something, that's the time they consult with me (P6, line 87-89) Reklamo na not enough time given for the outputs kase yung mga outputs before na kailangan niyo gawin or demonstrate in class now it has to be recorded so there is really additional work also for them (the students) (P3, line 125-128) There were students who expressed concerns sa motivation. (P3, line 203)</p>
	<p>Internship</p>	<p>For internship parang 1 week kayong puro classroom muna synchronous Pinakamahirap for me was internship kase yun nga prang it was andami niyang planning in the sense (P3, line 57-58) We had to do a technical meeting (P2, line 174) Maghanap ng platform na magagawa ng intern kahit papano pa rin yung nagagawa nila sa face to face (P3, line 20-21) It became a translation of seeing patients in person into seeing patients using zoom or google meet or any other platforms for video conferencing (P5, line 67-69) Introduce teletherapy, get them(the students) comfortable with the idea (P2, line 41) Wait for the guidelines coming from PASP (Philippine Association of Speech Pathologists) (P2, line 43) We had to adjust and had to instruct our patients to access the online meeting (P4, line 21-22) Provide webinars or seminars for some of the activities (P4, line 23)</p>

The above analysis ended up in the following figure.

Figure 3. Teaching Practices in DE

C. Practices in Transitioning to Distance Education

Table 7

Planning for DE

<p>Planning and preparation</p>	<p>Difficulties then was I felt I didn't had enough time to prepare yung mga materials (P3, line 123-124) Some of the students had difficulties learning through the online method (P4, line 43) The discussion needs to be facilitated in the way that we have to ask each and everyone of the students rather than being in a classroom in a classroom you can see their facial expressions, you can see their gestures or sometimes their confused faces so we can ask them directly what are they thinking about and then how they feel about discussing inside the classroom.(P4, line 116-121) Several meetings, several trainings that we had to undergo in a short span of time (P4, line123) The difference between face to face and online is that when you after you finish your lecture, after you prepare your PowerPoint presentation you'll just discuss it with your students but for online, but for the online practice you had to record yourself right after you finish your PowerPoint so it would sometimes make you work until late at night in order to finish that and also upload that presentation. (P4, line 127-132) We're at home so it was difficult to delineate when are you working for your work and also time for your family and also responsibilities at home (P4, line 133-135) Some therapy techniques also provide an instruction where we use physical moves so i think some of the courses like that are better with face to face sessions (P4, line 144-145) A few instances wherein we have to teach students to physically manipulate our patients or how to manage them hands on I think would need additional parameters on training siguro for our students for us to ensure that they will be ready (P4, line154-156) additional time that are required to do it sometimes it overlaps with responsibilities at home so i think that's the problem. (P4, line 139-140) Not everyone has the same technological knowledge (P5, line 91) A lot of uh, the people are not well aware of the of how online classes happen (P6, line 17-18) The issue that I encountered is actually more of me being an administrator and, and trying to convince the entire team that you know, we are equipped for the transition and again, and convincing the students and their family that it would actually work (P6, line 21-24) Enough time to plan ahead and given enough time to be given feedback and then revised some of the plans (P2, line 190-192)</p>
<p>Planning process</p>	<p>I had plan A,B,C,D ahead of time so i knew if something's not gonna work I had a backup plan (P2, line 197-198) Planning, the preparation of the materials whether I had to convert something para maging synchronous; asynchronous man siya na activity (P3, line 102-103) Gauge how much what is necessary, ano yung necessary na outputs tapos gaano katagal ibibigay namin for a certain output. (P3, line 134-136) Teaching style- mas maraming preparation and planning for online (P3, line 522) We had several meetings (P4, line 48)</p>

Planning process	<p>I always go back to the program outcomes and the year level outcomes (P6, line 163) We make sure that everyone could be included and also how we prepare for things that could and may happen. (P2, line 423-424) Our department planned as a department, so that's why there were very little hiccup when we were delivering the program (P6, line 211-212) We have, specialist in the team whom I consulted and were able to provide feedback on what should be done (P6, line 205-206)</p>	
Time allotment	<p>Distance education is not ok if you put it if there's not enough time, if there's not enough time to do everything you're supposed to do, so a big component i did not realize that for distance education time is such a huge component. (P2, line 236-239) I didn't had enough time to ano prepare yung ano mga materials (P3, 123-124) additional time that we had to that we had to had in order to adjust to online modalities (P4-136-137) a population of our student body that would need more time for them to adjust to the new way of learning (P5, lines 52-53) a lot of time was also used familiarizing with what the other options there are online (P5, line 95-96) preparing the materials eats up a lot of time (P6, line 49-50) We weren't really prepared with the immediate migration (P6, line 116-117) Main concern was the capacity of the students to cope with the sudden change (P2, line 49-50) Concerns at home also affected the way we had to adjust to this life (P4, line 74-75) Manage the extra time that we had to provide in making the materials (P4, line 126-127) Extra work (P1, line 17)</p>	
Description of Workload when transforming courses to DE	<p>Surprising amount of work (P1, line 07) More tasks(P1, line 07) Sobrang daming kailangan (P3, line 06) It took a toll on the faculty members because of, you know, how their workload increased like three-four-five times(P6, line 33-35) Added a lot to the workload....how..how ...so..yeah it was just the workload it was just a lot of work versus face to face (P2, line 246-247)</p>	
List of BS SLP Courses that were transformed from F2F to DE with the same Curriculum	2 nd year BSSLP courses	<p>Voice disorders (P1, line 03, P4 line 04) Research 1 (P1, line 04) Introduction to Audiology (P5, line 823), (P2, line 11) Anatomy and Physiology for SLPs (P2, line 8) Neuroanatomy for SLPs (P2, line 8) Counseling (P2, line 8) Articulation (P4, line 03) Fluency (P5, line 3), (P6, line 3) Language development (P6, line 3) Language conditions (P6, line 08)</p>

List of BS SLP Courses that were transformed from F2F to DE with the same Curriculum	3 rd year BSSLP courses	<p>Research 2 (P1, line 04)</p> <p>Motor speech condition (P1, line 03)</p> <p>Acquired Language and Cognitive Conditions (ALCC) (P2, line 10)</p> <p>Dysphagia (P4, line 04)</p> <p>Introduction to Diagnostics (P2, line 12)</p> <p>Intervention & Clinical Reasoning ((P2, line 131)</p> <p>Aural Habilitation (P3, line 03)</p> <p>CRP1 (Clinical Reasoning) (P2, line 12)</p>
	4 th year BSSLP courses	<p>Clinical Internship (P3, line 12), P4, line 05)</p> <p>Senior sem 1 (P3, line 03)</p>

Table 8

Administrative Tasks

Documentation	<p>Submit Weekly reports, detailed reports, activities, and student assessment (P1, line 19)</p> <p>It was more of like a team effort, of being able to provide an example and provide the document and sharing what, you know, what you could do (P6, line 27-29)</p>
Evaluation and Feedback	<p>Have feedback based on the results of the eval (P3, line 592)</p> <p>We did a program evaluation (P6, line 174-175)</p> <p>Feedback from students (P1, line 113, P2, line 240, P5, line 102)</p> <p>(From P6 whose an admin and educator)I had to just really think of like do SWOT [strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats] analysis (laughs) on what could go wrong (P6, line 203-204)</p>

Table 9*Leadership in DE*

Roles and responsibilities of the Program Director	<p>Program director was really instrumental towards having the right mindset towards distance education (P2, line 249-250)</p> <p>Our program director also encouraged us to think about what are the problems that might happen and since we were going at it with that perspective that “okay what could go wrong?” It helped us to plan....make different plans (P2, line 271-274)</p> <p>I have to lead a department and make them believe that this is achievable (P6, line 200-201)</p> <p>(Admin’s concern) My apprehension is not, does not really root from us not knowing what to do, but it’s more of the team believing that we can actually do it (P6, line 15-17)</p>
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Table 10*Support for DE*

Technological support	<p>CITC (Center of Information and Communications Technology) of Institution providing regular webinars for teaching online (P1, line 85-86)</p> <p>Technological assistance that was given was very sufficient (P5, line 115-116)</p> <p>Monitoring how we are all using the systems (P5, line 117-118)</p> <p>(Referring to the CITC) They’re a phone call-away, email-away for concerns that I might have for all the platforms that we are using (P5, line 118-120)</p> <p>Technical support from the ICT (CITC or ITC -Information and Communications Technology) (P6, line 254)</p>
Educational Support	<p>Free seminars, webinars (P2, line 256, P4, line 23, P5, line 134)</p> <p>Had a lot of support from the department (P6, line 192)</p> <p>We have the specialist needed to execute that, so within the department (P6, line 193-194)</p> <p>There’s a support system (P6, line 194-195)</p>
Support system	<p>Support system that I felt was really lacking when we did online was that we didn’t have....we weren’t physically together, and we didn’t have that chit chat during lunch time (P2, line 279-281)</p> <p>I did not feel that there was enough support on my end (P3, line 44)</p> <p>I would definitely appreciate the assistance of all my co-faculty members because they were the ones that facilitated how we could learn faster, how we could learn together , and it ended up well, the anxiety(P5, line 100-102)</p> <p>Support of the faculties is very important (P5, line 34)</p>

Table 11*Education And Trainings Received by The Faculty During the Transition*

Learning Management System	<p>We underwent training (P4, line 49)</p> <p>Trainings for Blackboard (P3, line 96,)</p> <p>I took also some courses on online service delivery like how to modify like some of the activities or like the....having some of the background just to utilize Moodle how to maximize Moodle, how to maximize your LMS helps a lot(P2, line 260-263)</p> <p>More training in the use of all these modalities, all these platforms (P5, line 131)</p>
Best practices	<p>We also discuss the different best practices for each of the courses done during the semester or the year and it helped us adjust (P4, line 64-66)</p> <p>The department has been able to share each other's best practice and implement it in the different courses (P5, line 36-37)</p>
Test construction	<p>We had training on test construction (P4, line 61, P6, line 232)</p>
Shared experiences with DE	<p>We had faculty members who were trained to provide; shared experiences with online modalities (P4, line 49-50)</p> <p>Had experience for online learning but not a full one but the training that we got actually helped me become more confident in providing activities or lecture or educational activities for our students (P4, line 56-59)</p>
Creating online materials	<p>There were a lot of hours spent on- learning how to do things, learning how create online materials. (p5, line 94-95)</p>
Self- Study	<p>Mostly experiential yung parang nagresearch ka rin kaw rin mismo magfamiliarize sa sarili mo dun sa platform so yon (P3, line 48-50)</p> <p>Some the faculty members also researched also did some readings on different studies regarding online education, so they also shared what they learned to other faculty (P4, line 51-52)</p> <p>A lot of time was also used familiarizing with what the other options there are online that we can use (P5, line 95-96)</p> <p>I had to also ask for assistance from people that I know are knowledgeable with um, these things that we are going to be using, I'm going to be using for the first time. (P5, line 109-110)</p> <p>I had to seek help from external people that are more familiar with it (P5, line 111-112)</p> <p>I had to do my own research (P5, line 112)</p> <p>I had to look it into references or resources online that would help me understand better how could use these different modes online (P5, line 112-114)</p> <p>I scour through the internet about these practices and the application (P6, line 152-153)</p>

On training	<p>Training- kung merong training for those who are starting with distance ed that will be helpful yun (P3, line 178-179)</p> <p>It could have been very helpful if there is an exposure to more online means of teaching (P5, line 121-122)</p> <p>If those workshops were more frequent from the institution or if those workshops were something that could be accessible at your own time, i think a lot of the faculty members would definitely be able to learn more in such a shorter amount of time and be helpful with the transition (P5, line 137-140)</p> <p>More training would be the best practice for conducting online or distance learning for our students (P4, line 168)</p> <p>I will attend more training, formal training, formal education (P4, line 170-171)</p> <p>I don't think everything that was thought before was really made me very prepared (P3, line 98-99)</p>
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Table 12

Transitioning to DE

Transitioning to DE	<p>Mismatch with the expectations (P1, line 21)</p> <p>I'm still confident that we were able to achieve the program outcomes of our students even if it was conducted online. (P1, line 127-128)</p> <p>May resistance (P3, line 05)</p> <p>May dread (P3, line 05)</p> <p>There was a lot of anxiety at the start (P5, line 93)</p> <p>Anxiety over sa mga posibleng madaming gawin (P3, line 9-10)</p> <p>Frustrating at first because it was very difficult to adjust from one method to another completely (P4, line 122-123)</p> <p>Frustrating one is the additional time that we had to that we had to had in order to adjust to online modalities (P4, line 787)</p> <p>I was doing more than the work that I would've done had it been face to face so tung transition na yan was really stressful (P3, line 585)</p> <p>adjust (P1, line 27, P2, line 97, P3, line 56, P4, line 122, P5, line 18)</p> <p>It was hard even yung first sem na full blast ng online kase ano all of those are subjects that were previously thought face to face (P3, line 100-101)</p> <p>First transition there was resistance (P3, line 125)</p> <p>I was also questioning whether the activities i have prepared or my assessments were they really hitting the course outcomes (P3, line 108-109)</p>
After implementing DE	<p>Generally happy with how we did it (P2, line 304)</p> <p>Prefer DE because we can still achieve outcomes without being infected with covid19 (P1, line 130-131)</p> <p>Good experience (P2, line 361, P4, line 818)</p> <p>Time consuming (P4, line 125)</p> <p>I felt overworked (P3, line 104)</p> <p>Still want face to face there's a human component that needs to translate physically (P2, line 305-306)</p>

After implementing DE	<p>able to adjust (P1, line 22)</p> <p>It will take time before you get used to that kind of modality (P3, line 139)</p> <p>It is not as different as a lot of people might think. (P5, line 184-185)</p> <p>I was pretty satisfied with the way the students' outcome final outcome were made and how I saw their evolution (P6, line 213-214)</p> <p>P6 reported that CHED, the government regulation body thought that we had the best practice amongst all four university (P6, line 149-150)</p> <p>We have to do it all over again for one whole year and then there were some adjustments again but i think we were more ready because of the things that we learn when we ran it the first time. (P2, line 301)</p> <p>There still similar but few adjustments for DE (P1, line 140)</p> <p>I do not see a lot of difference whether it is done f2f or online (P2, line 324-325)</p> <p>there's not much difference (P2, line 359)</p> <p>Not fair to say DE better than face to face (P2, line 360)</p> <p>Wala siyang masyadong difference (P3, line 29)</p>
Promoting Quality of life	<p>More comfortable or relaxed in the setting in the work from home (P1, line 11)</p> <p>minimizes the risk of contracting the infection (P1, line 12)</p> <p>Able to adjust with the work from home setting (P1, line 22)</p> <p>I Like the comfort of working from home (P1, line 23)</p> <p>Spending more time with family (P1, line 24)</p> <p>More time for me to relax and enjoy free time (P1, line 24-25)</p> <p>making the most of your time also with your family because you get to spend more time with them (P2, line 296-297)</p>

Table 13

Providing Learning Resources

Learning Resources	<p>Prepare video demonstrations in advance (P1, line 48-49)</p> <p>Provide Supplementary videos (P1, line 49-50)</p> <p>Accessible websites (P1, line 50-51)</p> <p>Recorded sessions (P1, line 08, P2 line 316, P3, line 516, P4, line 10-11, P6 line 52)</p> <p>Putting materials on the screen and then utilizing it in terms of how they would use it in classrooms (P2, line 94-96)</p> <p>Maximizing the materials (P5, line 42, P1 line 63, P2 line 347)</p> <p>We were able to maximize the materials online that our department has and use it as we tackle everything through the online teaching mode. (P5, line 42-44)</p> <p>we would make recordings for them to access at a given time (P5, line 24-25)</p>
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Learning Resources	<p>We were able to do is to maximize, again the online resources available for them to be able to experience the same hands-on learning that we are providing in the lab sessions (P5, line 65-66)</p> <p>Nakapagmigrate din ako that time ng mga materials (P3, line 529)</p> <p>Had materials on hand (P2, line 93-94)</p> <p>Ask the students to access materials that were recorded (P4, line 10-11)</p> <p>Lectures had been recorded (P1, line 08, P6, line 52)</p>
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The above analysis ended up in the following figure.

Figure 4. Practices in Transitioning to Distance Education

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This study investigated how distance education is understood and defined by the educators of an allied medical program. Significant elements that encompasses Distance Education were provided by this study that answers the research question: why do educators in an allied medical program engage in DE?. The study was able to provide information on the perspectives and practices in teaching and transitioning to distance education that would give us the explanation of educators to provide distance education in an allied medical program.

The Perspectives On Distance Education Of Educators In An Allied Medical Program

After a meticulous process of data comparison and analysis the following perspectives on distance education of educators of allied medical programs were identified: (i) DE can be equivalent to face-to-face mode of education as it can target the same course and program outcomes and provide quality education. (ii) The physical separation of the student from the educators affects the speed and mode of communication in Distance Education, (iii) Distance education has contributed to promoting inclusivity, outcome-based education, student-educator relationships, improving student's written communication, and the quality of feedback of educators.

Equivalence of DE To Face-To-Face Mode of Education

Distance education is described to be equivalent to face-to-face mode of education as it can target and achieve the same course and program outcomes and provide quality education. All participants of this study noted they were able to

achieve the same learning and program outcomes set for face-to-face mode of education. It was also identified that during the transition it has become the goal for each course to find innovative ways to achieve the learning and program outcomes..

“We still want to achieve the course and program outcomes regardless of the mode of delivery” (P1, line 104-105)

“Outcomes didn’t really change that much during from face to face to online learning “(P4, line 88-99)

Educators had to ensure that the same quality and outcomes are met during the transformation of their courses to DE. The outcomes were constant and accomplished for all courses when the program was transformed to DE. The educators were able to replicate these outcomes in the online mode of education.

“Ensure that the outcomes we have set for all of the courses that we are running are being met.”(P5, line 106-107)

“Ensuring that the student receive the quality education” (P1, line 89)

“We’re still able to achieve those learning outcomes even if they were provided online.” (P4, line 91-92)

“We were able to achieve all those outcomes that we have set, even if the mode of delivery was very different, so it was a learning experience also for us to broaden our perspective” (P5, line 170-172)

“ Expectations and the outcomes that we have for the face-to-face , courses, we were able to replicate it in the online mode of teaching (P5, line 176-178)”

The effectiveness of DE was based on the student's performance and accomplishment of learning and program outcomes. With this, DE was described as effective as the face-to-face mode of education based on the satisfactory performance of the students and accomplishment of learning and program outcomes. It was reported by P1 that the passing and attrition rate of the program did not drastically change.

"Effectiveness of online education is similar to face to face."(P1, line114-115)

"Satisfied with their (the student's) performance" (P1, line 120-121)

"I was pretty satisfied with the way the students' outcome final outcome were made" (P6, line 213-214)

Education in Varying Modes and Speed of Communication

Given that the learners and educators are geographically separated in distance education, the physical separation affected the speed and mode of communication in distance education. Physically being in front of students during class is one of the differences of face to face from distance education.

" I think the difference would mostly be being in front of the students"
(P4,line 108)

Being geographically separated in distance education resulted in a difference in the speed and mode of communication between the educator and the students. The physical separation affected the interaction and facilitation of learning activities. One of the educators noted that it was faster for students to communicate their queries and ask for clarification in the face-to-face mode of education. Another educator noted that

there is a need to validate what is happening with the student in their personal learning environment in contrast if it was face to face wherein educators can monitor and manage their students immediately.

“Face to face I feel yung communication line parang mas mabilis nasasabi natatanong agad kung meron di naiintindihan” (P3, line 76-77)

“Hindi lahat nakakapagsabi kung naiintindihan nila yung material right there and then during the lecture itself (P3, line 72-73)

“You have to confirm and validate what’s happening to them and if it was a face-to-face class then it’s gonna be easier because you see the groups already working together. (P2, line 394-396)

Communication was conducted using emails, messaging applications, video conferencing applications and online forums. It is conducted either synchronously, asynchronously or mixed.

“Communicate with students using institutional email “(P1, line 54)

“Synchronous sessions” (P1 line 36, P3 line 506, P4 line 16-17, P5 line 23, P6, line 48)

”Use short messaging applications” (P1, line 59)

“When we do synchronous sessions, we still encourage discussions, recitation, group work even if it’s online” (P5, line 152-153)

“Asynchronous” (P2, line 124, P3 line 15, P5 line 23)

“Asynchronous or synchronous yung line of communication- email and forums “(P3, line 78-79)

Expansion and Consideration for The Needs of Others

The study has shown that Distance education contributed to promoting inclusivity, outcome-based education, student-educator relationships, improving student's written communication and the quality of feedback of educators.

Distance education involves teaching concepts, targeting expected learning outcomes without physical interaction. P6 noted that DE made them geared towards an outcome-based education. The learning process became more student oriented, and student directed. DE made the educators more creative in eliciting the skills that are needed from their students.

“We are more outcomes-based like we geared towards more OBE [outcomes-based education] when we migrated to online versus when we were doing it face-to-face” (P6, line 189-191)

Distance education was identified to be an effective mode of education especially for courses that wouldn't involve physical handling or manipulation. Feedback in DE was more individualized. The quality of feedback given by educators in DE in this study was evaluated by the students and was noted to have significant improvements.

“Faculty evaluation of the students provide more positive comments on quality of feedback in online education” (P1, line 122-123)

Aside from this, DE helped in providing understanding on how learners respond to different stimuli. Educators observed that there are students who are considered shy in the classroom and would be more responsive in DE. DE allowed the students to connect with the educators at a personal level because of the constant direct communication thru email, chat, or direct message.

“ To a certain extent (DE) allows them also to connect more personally with the faculty members at a more personal level because we communicate regularly with them either through email or yun nga through direct message on chat” (P2, line 433-436)

DE paved the way for the institution to expand and cater to students beyond its region and to have more consideration on the needs of others. It made the institution more inclusive and enabled the program to expand their services.

“It provided us with a wider net for expansion and consideration of the needs of others” (P2, line 430-431)

“So, I think those are things DE provided us with the opportunity to look into those things and to be more inclusive also because one’s factor that DE has provided us is that we were able to reach students who are not within the area of the institution like they’re from different areas” (P2, line 424-427)

Educators identified significant improvement in their student’s planning and written communication. Since students would use email or online messaging for communication it was observed that there were significant improvements with the student’s written communication.

“A lot of components honed when done online-ex. The planning , how the students plan for the sessions is so much better now” (P2, line 325-326)

“Student’s communicating better, better written communication” (P2, line 334)

Practices In Teaching

The teaching practices in DE consists of instructional designing that is intertwined with the use of technology. The study was able to provide significant information on the educator's teaching practices, teaching principles, course and learning outcomes, technology for teaching and learning, communication, learning resources, assessment and the teaching and learning strategies and activities for DE.

Similarities in teaching practices in the face-to-face mode of education were identified in this study. Aside from having the same outcomes, the content and topics of each course were the same. The lectures and topics had the same content that was delivered synchronously or asynchronously. In Distance education, educators were able to teach and assess the skills necessary for each course, however it was noted that though DE would deliver the same lectures and content that involves thinking out of the box in terms of selecting teaching strategies, assessment, and activities.

Transactional Distance in Distance Education

Transactional distance was explained by Moore (1997) as the psychological and communication gap between the learner and the instructor that may cause misunderstanding. The presence of transactional distance was confirmed by almost all the educators in this study. The educators described this as having that sense of disconnection between themselves and their students caused by the limitations in providing immediate and receiving feedback and/ or the lack of knowledge on what may be occurring in their student's personal learning spaces. Their learning principles, learning outcomes, program outcomes, and technology influenced the course design in distance education and addressed issues of transactional distance.

Communication: Things Get Lost in Translation

Being geographically separated would affect the level of interaction and communication among students and educators. DE has limitations in providing non-linguistic information such as body posture, facial expressions, gestures, and reactions during communication that would provide better understanding between the students and the educators.

*“I think there are still a lot of components that distance education could not provide for example...uhmmm yun nga.... while those...ano ba...aspects of communication is improve, other like the software skills like watching out for your posture, watching out for your...like small physical reactions for example facial expressions those are somethings that I think we need to....that you can pick up better if you were doing things face to face because the context that the environment provides
“(P2, line 337-343)*

There are classes that would not require students to open their cameras and in this context the educators have no information on the current learning environment of their students while they are in class. There are classes wherein educators would have limitations in monitoring their students' attention and understanding during lectures. There are also observations that there are students who are hesitant with asking clarifications during the class and educators had difficulty picking up non-linguistic reactions that may indicate that the students needed further clarification. One educator stated that she felt things get lost in translation during distance education unlike in face to face where she can see their confused faces and ask them about what they are thinking and have the discussion within the classroom setting.

“You don’t know what’s happening to them at home kasi we don’t require them to open their cameras” (P2, line 390-391)

“ I also feel sometimes things get lost in translation like in a classroom setting i would honestly know kung di naintindihan” (P3, line 69-70)

Communication and interaction in distance education was done through various methods with the use of different software. Educators had to ensure that even if learning was conducted online they would still be able to achieve the learning outcomes, connect and engage with their students.

“Make sure that even if we’re all online we want to feel connected” (P2, line 145)

“You try to engage your students as much as you can” (P2, line 389)

Educators would communicate with their students synchronously and asynchronously. Institutional emails, online forums where students can post their questions and thoughts anonymously, phone in questions and short messaging applications were used for asynchronous communication.

“Communicate with students Using institutional email” (P1, line 63)

“Synchronous sessions” (P1 line 08, P3 line 14, P4 line 15-16, P5 line 23, P6, line 48)

“Use short messaging applications “ (P1, line 69)

“Only difference is that we don’t interact directly or f2f with students” (P1, line 135-136)

“Meron kaming phone in question ganyan so sasagutin ko lang” (P2, line 412)

“We also have online forum where people can post questions and thoughts anonymously” (P6, line 80-81)

In asynchronous communication, feedback is not given right away unlike in face-to-face mode of education. Written communication thru email, messaging or forums may take a lot of turnaround time and may be an additional workload for some educators.

“If you were faced to face you’re all together In one whole room and the feedback can be given right there, right then and there but for online it’s always gonna be via email, via written communication and that takes a lot of turnaround time so that added a lot to the workload “ (P2, line 241-244)

Providing feedback can also be challenging for group activities. Educators would need to confirm and validate what’s going on with the students in contrast to face to face wherein you can immediately observe the groups working together. Group chats, which includes the faculty, were noted to be helpful for group activities.

“You have to confirm and validate what’s happening to them and if it was a face-to-face class then it’s gonna be easier because you see the groups already working together.” (P2, line 394-395)

“During classes the group chats really helped having the group chat with the faculty” (P2, line 282-283)

For synchronous interaction, online video conferencing was held. Synchronous meetings are properly scheduled. Same teaching activities conducted in the face-to-face mode of education can still be applied to facilitate activities in synchronous classes. This was done by raising questions during the synchronous class, waiting for students to respond through the chat room or by reciting with open cameras.

“Comfortable facilitating activities used in f2f: Raising questions, waiting students to respond thru chat or opening cameras” (P1, line 88-91)

Rooting on Teaching Principles and Achieving Course and Learning Outcomes

In distance education, the teaching principles and learning outcomes are the same with face-to-face mode of education, wherein you would only be modifying your teaching and learning activities. The program outcomes and year level outcomes of the courses are the guiding compass when transforming the courses. One educator noted that it was more of a paradigm shift in the teaching process.

“Course learning outcomes and program outcomes stayed the same” (P1, line 38-39)

“Make alternative plans to meet the outcomes.” (P2, line 61-62)

“ It’s a paradigm shift on your teaching process (P6, line 236-237)

Educators were providing alternative plans to achieve the same outcomes in distance education. One of the educators described their teaching framework as identifying how students will learn given the limitations of distance education without changing the outcomes and the design of the program. All the learning and teaching activities were still rooted from the philosophies and ideals that were set in the face-to-face mode of education.

“What you’re doing is routed on you know your philosophies, your theories these are ideals you know that you’re only modifying your teaching and learning activities” (P2, line 267-268)

“It was very clear to us that it was just going to be a shift in the method of delivery but there was never going to be a change in the content of the... and the outcomes needs to be met. (P2, line 252-253)

“I don’t think there’s a lot of difference kase the topics were maintained ganon tapos kahit papaano nahihit parin yung outcomes (P3, line 63-64)

“The framework was already how do you learn and how are you going to learn this material and with all the constraints that are happening and without changing the outcomes and how the program was designed.” (P6, line 246-249)

” I just go back to rely on the program outcome (P6, line 231-232)

With the various changes in teaching strategies and assessment there are learning activities that are not fit for students with different learning styles. Some students who would prefer a more interactive learning approach would have difficulty adjusting to distance education.

“Some of the activities were not applicable to other students with different type of learning styles” (P4, line 41-42)

“What’s good about seeing both ends like the DE and the face to face, you also see how different kinds of learners respond to stimuli (P2, line 459-460)

“It does work for some students like some students who might be too quiet or might be too shy when they are in the classroom might do work really well while they’re on DE “(P2, line 431-433)

Technology is Capitalized

Technology is identified as one of the most powerful and important components in providing Distance Education (DE). Technology is highlighted as a critical tool to be able to deliver education through distance education. The educators listed various hardware and software that they used in providing DE.

Easier To Deliver Courses Online

Technology was used for delivering content, facilitating communication, discussion, interaction, and providing assessments of the courses they were delivering. Bandwidth needed for these applications was also considered in selecting software for distance education. Training all users, the students and educators was provided for them to be proficient in navigating and using these applications for teaching and learning.

All participants were using computers equipped with a learning management system (LMS). Blackboard and Moodle were the specified LMS mentioned in the study. The LMS assisted the educators in organizing the class and ensuring that the discussion is still dynamic. The LMS was very helpful in delivering distance education. The LMS that was used for distance education has the capacity to do all the necessary actions needed for teaching and learning, such as delivering learning materials , posting lectures, receiving outputs from the students, conducting forums, and providing assessments.

“You can make your exams there (in the LMS), you can post your lectures, provide forums, everything essential into ensuring that the discussion is still dynamic even if it’s not face-to-face.” (P5, line145-149)

“LMS for posting lecture materials” (P1, line 75)

“We had Moodle.... to share lectures and get submission of the students that helped in the transition” (P2, line 26--29)

Aside from the LMS, various software were used for communication and delivering their lectures. Emails and discussion forums were used by the educators to communicate with their students. Videoconferencing applications such as Zoom, and Google Meet were used to deliver their lectures synchronously. Zoom was a

preference for some educators noting that aside from videoconferencing, it can deliver and receive direct messages during synchronous classes and has the annotate function that can be used for exemplifying a concept which mirrors the use of whiteboards used in classrooms.

“Using online video conference platform like Google Meet or Zoom” (P1, line 28)

“Utilize (Google) Meet and Zoom” (P2, line 103)

“We use zoom, since zoom had a direct message option there are some students who would send questions to me via direct message” (P2, line 404-405)

Other software used for teaching and providing assessments were Google forms and PowerPoint. PowerPoint presentations were utilized for presenting their lectures. Google forms were used for exams, obtaining queries from the class and peer evaluations.

“Using Google forms to facilitate peer evaluation”(P1, line 100-101)

“We developed, a Google form wherein people will write in their questions in that form (P6, line 83-84)

“Using PowerPoint presentations” (P1, line 65)

Managing technology involved in delivering distance education can also be challenging. Technology was highlighted as a tool that helped the educators to deliver distance education. However, it was also one of their concerns. The ease of use of the technology should be considered in DE, since technical skills may vary among the faculties. Some educators noted that they lack confidence in their video editing skills and use of applications such as Adobe Photoshop to develop more complex teaching materials.

“We have different levels of our ease of use of technology” (P5, line 35-36)

“Cannot use adobe photoshop to prepare more complex materials for teaching (P1, line 80-81)

Aside from the use of various software, internet connections can also be a challenge. Weak internet connections can affect their communication with their students. Concerns were raised on the internet connection for both stakeholders, students, and educators. With the sudden transition to online learning activities, stability of the internet was needed for the educators to deliver their courses and for the students to participate in their classes. Having an unstable internet may result in different problems. Bandwidth should also be considered for the software that the learners and educators will be using. Educators had to use a variety of software such as Zoom, the learning system and Google applications in their classes. These software applications have varying bandwidth requirements to be efficiently used by both educators and students. With this, they would need a stable internet connection during their classes to adequately run this software, deliver information and facilitate interaction. Bandwidth and internet connection is a complementary aspect that should be considered when delivering DE.

“Concern about the student's internet connection” (P4, line 14-15)

“Concern about students who did not have stable internet connection and not ready for online service delivery at home” ,(P2, line 57-59)

“ I had problems with my internet connection” (P4, line 15-16)

“ Bandwidth considerations” (P1, line 57, P2, line 63, P3, line 60)

“Poor internet connection in specific areas (so that)contributed greatly to the difficulties (P4, line 75-76)

The shift to DE was immediate because of the pandemic. Some educators noted that the students were not given enough time to process the changes in the mode of education. And there are various novel activities and learning materials such as the LMS that was introduced. Having proper orientation such as with the use of the LMS, can ease the transition of the students. After the implementation of DE there were realizations on the importance of LMS, faculty support and training for delivering this mode of education. An educator noted that she was surprised at the lack of LMS in most schools in the Philippines, as it was identified as one of the helpful tools they utilized to deliver DE.

*“Surprised that a lot of universities (in the Philippines) do not have LMS
(P6, line 252-253)*

Delivering The Course Curriculum Remotely

Delivering content for each course would involve educators delivering lectures to their students. There were no changes with the content of their lectures, however migration and modifications for it to be delivered online is needed. There were pre-recorded lectures and live lectures that were used for asynchronous and synchronous classes.

There are a lot of adjustments with the class activities in distance education to make it more feasible in an online setting. Majority of the activities such as providing lectures, worksheets, assessments, and internship were transformed to an online modality. Course curriculums were restructured and delivered remotely, and students had to adjust to the change of modality.

“Migrate those lectures into the online format either synchronously or asynchronously” (P5, line 22-23)

“Big adjustments that we can't do because of physical social distancing or the pandemic; Providing lectures, adjustments in assessing the students; adjustment in handling sessions or intern sessions that are conducted online so I think those were the adjustments (P4, line 809-811)

“DE is delivering course curriculum remotely” (P1, line 133)

All the courses that were handled by the educators were transformed online completely when they transitioned to distance education. The transformation involved planning and applying changes to their teaching and learning activities, structuring the program, and having more consultation time with their students. The educators had to analyze and determine how face to face outputs will be transformed for it to be fit for distance learning. Identification of activities fit for synchronous and asynchronous classes was also done. Activities that would require physical manipulation such as palpation were somehow sacrificed because of the lack of physical interaction. Learning materials were sorted and selected according to what the educators can manage and what is appropriate for their lectures. Throughout the changes, educators had to see to it that students are learning, accommodations were provided for those who need it and learning outcomes were achieved.

“Titingan mo muna kung akma kung alin dun ang pinaka okay na material bago mo siya incorporate sa lectures mo.” (P3, line 37-38)

“Structuring the program” (P2, line 47)

“Identifying that we have would need to be translated into online” (P5, line 12)

“Having to look at, requirements, the flow of the discussion, all of the aspects that we have put up and constantly comparing them to the outcomes that we have set for the course. (P5, line 167-169)

“We were more focused now on ensuring that each and individual student is learning because we are teaching it in a different way” (P6, line 42-43)

Students were informed on how things will be running. Orientation included setting expectations. Some of the courses had introductory courses to guide them with the changes. Structured meetings were held for their classes and instructions given to students were described to be very detailed. Learning activities may vary from asynchronous to synchronous activities. For synchronous activities, educators would have discussions, recitation, group activities, which was the same as what they had in the face-to-face mode of education. Breakout rooms were also used online as a venue for students to have their group discussion while educators can enter from one room to another. For asynchronous sessions, educators would provide an online forum for discussion where students and teachers can post their opinions, questions, and responses. A noted advantage with discussion forums is that students can go back to the discussion at any point of time.

“Introductory courses helped them (the students) it was a way to guide them” (P2, line 52)

“When we do synchronous sessions, we still encourage discussions, recitation, group work even if it’s online” (P5, line 152-153)

“Breakout rooms for example that would be the venue for certain students to come together and discuss and as teachers, we can just jump from one forum to another” (P5, line 154-157)

“For asynchronous sessions, what i have been doing is providing a forum for discussion, so even if the interaction isn’t live or directly online or on time, at least using the forums the opinions and questions still be expressed and response from the teachers would still be provided and the advantage there is since it’s written, or it’s typed the students can actually go back to the discussion at any point in time” (P5, line 157-162)

Some classes would consist of both asynchronous and synchronous interaction. Example given for a class as described by an educator was that she would lecture synchronously for two hours and then have an independent work or an asynchronous task for one hour and then group discussion again after another hour. Outputs were in various forms such as videos or group presentations. One educator reported that she showcased the students’ outputs through an exhibit where other students can view the outputs of their classmates and learn from each other.

“Migrate those lectures into the online format either synchronously or asynchronously” (P5, line 22-23)

“Showcase some outputs of students and view it like an expo, view materials students did and learn from each other (P2, line 147-148)

“The way I setup the online is that I gave a lecture for two hours and then independent work for one hour and then, group discussion again after one hour (P6, line 75-77)

The internship program in this study involved a lot of planning. It would have synchronous classes and technical meetings. Educators had to look for an online platform where the interns can have the same learning experiences they would have in a face-to-face mode of internship. Introduction of novel service modality was also done for the students. Webinars and seminars were given. Coordination with the

professional body was also needed for further guidance on novel services that will be provided online. In this study, the educators had to wait for guidelines on delivering online services from the Philippine Association of Speech Pathologists (PASP).

“For internship parang 1-week kayong puro classroom muna synchronous...Pinakamahirap for me was internship kase yun nga prang it was andami niyang planning in the sense” (P3, line 544-545)

“We had to do a technical meeting” (P2, line 174)

“Maghanap ng platform na magagawa ng intern kahit papano pa rin yung nagagawa nila sa face to face” (P3, line 20-21)

“It became a translation of seeing patients in person into seeing patients using zoom or google meet or any other platforms for video conferencing” (P5, line 67-69)

“Introduce teletherapy, get them(the students) comfortable with the idea” (P2, line 41)

“Wait for the guidelines coming from PASP (Philippine Association of Speech Pathologists)” (P2, line 42-43)

“We had to adjust and had to instruct our patients to access the online meeting” (P4, line 21-22)

“Provide webinars or seminars for some of the activities” (P4, line 23)

With their teaching learning activities, there were concerns raised on managing the time needed for constructing the learning materials and making changes with the learning activities. Laboratory sessions that are traditionally delivered through a face-to-face mode of education was identified as one of their concerns. There were concerns expressed on how classes such as the laboratory sessions wherein face to face interactions and manipulation of learning materials would be requiring novel

learning activities in distance education. Given the changes, the quality of learning was also of concern, stating that they had to ensure that the student's learning shouldn't be shortchanged or sacrificed, and that the integrity of assessments are intact and secured.

"Main concern was the capacity of the students to cope with the sudden change (P2, line 49-50)

" I was concerned about is the different learning um, capacities of our students.....A population of our student body that would need more time for them to adjust to the new way of learning" (P5, lines 50-51)

"Laboratory sessions using simulations, using um, actual materials, sometimes, even actual patients and it was something that we were worried about because again it is very new in that particular manner" (P5, line 46-49)

"Ensure that learning isn't shortchange or sacrifice" (P5, line 55-56)

With change there will be adjustments. Adjustment to change may vary among each individual. Educators were concerned about those who would need more time to adjust to the new way of learning. Concerns on the learning capacities of their students, student's motivation, capacity to do self-directed learning and communication with their professors were raised. There were students who expressed concerns on their motivation to study and learn. Educators had to consider appropriate time allotment for each requirement, since there were students who had issues regarding time for accomplishing tasks assigned to them. An example cited were outputs that would require a demonstration would now require more tasks such

as recording themselves unlike if they had to simply perform it in the classroom during a face-to-face mode of education.

“Concerns in motivation....Self Directed Learning” (P3, line 203-204)

“A population of our student body that would need more time for them to adjust to the new way of learning” (P5, lines 52-53)

“Main concern was the capacity of the students to cope with the sudden change (P2, line 49-50)

“Reklamo na not enough time given for the outputs kase yung mga outputs before na kailangan niyo gawin or demonstrate in class now it has to be recorded so there is really additional work also for them (the students) (P3, line 125-128)

There were students who expressed concerns sa motivation. (P3, line 203)

Transforming Assessments and Adding Security Measures

Assessment is an educator's tool for understanding the learner's learning styles, and to gauge how much knowledge was acquired. Assessments are strategically planned and constructed in distance education. There are a lot of adjustments on providing and constructing assessments in DE. Bandwidth, workload, learning platform, learning environment of students are factors to consider in providing assessments in DE.

“Consider more factors in online assessment, workload of student, bandwidth requirement, platform” (P1, line 56-57)

Written exams were transformed to online exams. Given that assessments were transformed into a different modality, all outputs should still be reflective of the expected learning outcomes without sacrificing the measurement of learning set for each course. Assessment in DE is described as finding innovative ways of assessing the same skills; with a similar learning experience expected in the face-to-face mode of education.

“Innovative ways to assess same skills online (P1, line 52-53)

“We tried to at least provide the um similar experience for practical examinations or writing paper, writing evaluation reports, writing activity plans, or writing therapy plans so we tried to provide a similar experience with the face-to-face methods” (P4, line 94-96)

The use of LMS for assessments was noted to be important for ensuring quality and compliance on the requirements for accreditation. Additional security measures were put in place such as setting up multiple cameras in the student's learning environment to have visibility on the exam, the examination site and inspect if the student has access to any reference that may indicate cheating.

“Implementing more secure measures in the conduct of the exams” (P5, line 77)

“Answers are readily available on the internet, so the main adjustment there was that we did multiple cameras, so one camera for viewing the exams and another to view the student as they were actually completing the exams” (P2, line 101-103)

“Created a mandatory setup that would enable the facilitators of the exam to see the environment of the student while taking the exam, to see what the students able to access during the conduct of the exam” (P5, line 78-81)

“ We ask them to do dual camera setups when they use their laptops and another device just for us to be able to see them while they take the exam” (P5, line 82-84)

“ Additional preparation before the exam halimbawa yung kapag written exam na revalida pag panel presentation we had to check yung environment kung meron bang kodigo yung mga ganung bagay “(P3, line 89-92)

For distance education it was identified that there were more formative assessments and individual tasks compared to group activities. Rubrics were provided for each requirement. The rubrics were described to be more specific and detailed. Written and verbal guidelines were also provided to the students. Consultation and individual feedback were conducted more frequently.

“There is a rubric the students were able to perform skills needed for the online practical exam.” (P4, line 102-103)

“I gave a lot of individual work and then I give, I gave several formative activities for them to complete” (P6, line 64-65)

“We also took time to give them feedback individually, unlike before, we just gave return the paper and then, the case analysis sessions were done in groups, so the student wasn’t given individual feedback on his or her understanding of the course.” (P6, line106-109)

“During the migration, the group activities were scaled down into individual output (P6, line 109-110)

“More formative activities” (P6, line 123-124)

“We were able to translate some of the requirements, some of the written exam requirement into other outputs, projects, papers all the other outputs that would still be reflective of their learning without sacrificing the measurement that we need to see for what they have learned and how we are going to move forward.” (P5, line 85-89)

“Providing formative activities and then providing feedback for students and also providing a more specific rubric for each of the activity provided and then discussing it to the students helped in facilitating those activities” (P4, line 67-69)

Summative assessments were different in distance education. It would consist more of the application of knowledge acquired and case analysis. Outputs would vary from written documents, video recordings, online exams, synchronous practical and oral exams. Recorded outputs would involve performing a task with a peer or family member in contrast if it was conducted face to face wherein the students can perform a specified task with their classmates and the educator. Videos were also presented for some written outputs such as viewing a video of a patient and constructing an evaluation report based on what they have observed in the video. Posting comments and grades in the student’s written output was reported to be one of the ways of providing feedback to the students . Synchronous practical and oral exams were conducted through video conferencing wherein the student will perform a specific task assigned by their instructor.

“When we migrated online we had a lot more case analysis and application questions during the output” (P6, line 96-97)

“Making the Practical exam thru synchronous video call (P1, line 36)

“Adjust the method of evaluation of the students” (P2, line 97)

“We had to ask them to record themselves and perform the techniques or the assessment procedures on their family members .instead to the teachers or the instructors of the course” (P4, line 35-37)

“We had the students observe different videos of patients and they had to create evaluation reports and then we would provide them a rubric and then write their evaluation reports, provide comments, and also grade them using that method (P4, line 103-106)

Providing assessments is crucial to determine the learning styles and knowledge acquired by the students. Providing assessments in DE can also be challenging. Educators in this study had to select and construct online assessments for their courses. Feedback given to students was more individualized in DE. Providing individualized feedback to several students can be laborious and educators must find ways to share feedback that would be beneficial to the class but was given individually. An example for this would be feedback given thru email was noted to benefit the student who sent the email; rather if it was done in a class in a face-to-face setting, a student who may have the same concern would benefit from hearing the feedback given if it was delivered within the classroom.

We also took time to give them feedback individually, unlike before, we just gave return the paper and then, the case analysis sessions were done in groups, so the student wasn't given individual feedback on his or her understanding of the course. (P6, line 106-109)

During the migration, the group activities were scaled down into individual output (P6, line 109-110)

The difference would be providing sometimes the feedback given to students are individualized in DE. Some students would email questions and then sometimes those questions will be or are not heard by the other students, so we had to provide them extra effort to share what their classmate asked and then how we answered (P4, line 111-116)

Distance education had limitations in teaching skills that would require physical manipulation and patient handling. Additional parameters and training was needed for educators to teach skills that would involve physical manipulation and practical skills.

“Yung actual interaction with the patient and sa mismo mag din planning magfa facilitate ng actual na eval and intervention yon mejo nawala yon” (P3, line 85-87)

“A few instances wherein we have to teach students to physically manipulate our patients or how to manage them hands on I think would need additional parameters on training siguro for our students for us to ensure that they will be ready” (P4, line 154-155)

Practices in Transitioning to DE

The study has shown that transitioning to distance education involves planning, promoting quality of life, and provision of accessible learning resources. The planning process would include leadership, administrative tasks, support, education, and

training. Adequate time allotment is important to successfully transition to distance education that would improve the quality of life of all stakeholders.

Planning as a Department

Distance education involves preparation and planning prior to its implementation. Planning and preparing for distance education also requires adequate time allotment. With the immediate transition from face to face to distance education due to the pandemic, the educators of this study noted that they didn't have ample time to prepare the materials, redesign their program, train, and plan for the transition. The educators had several meetings and underwent training in a short span of time to plan and prepare for the transition to distance education.

“Several meetings, several trainings that we had to undergo in a short span of time” (P4, line 123)

“Enough time to plan ahead and given enough time to be given feedback and then revised some of the plans (P2, line 191-192)

“Difficulties then was I felt I didn't had enough time to prepare yung mga materials” (P3, line 123-124)

“The difference between face to face and online is that when you after you finish your lecture, after you prepare your PowerPoint presentation you'll just discuss it with your students but for online, but for the online practice you had to record yourself right after you finish your PowerPoint so it would sometimes make you work until late at night in order to finish that and also upload that presentation.”(P4, line 127-132)

The planning for distance education is a strategic process that would involve several tasks and time allotment. One of the participants stated that she had several plans and backup plans to prepare her for the transition to DE.

“I had plan A,B,C,D ahead of time so i knew if something’s not gonna work I had a backup plan” (P2, line 197-198)

“Planning, the preparation of the materials whether I had to convert something para maging synchronous; asynchronous man siya na activity” (P3, line 102-103)

With the sudden surge of the covid19, the transformation to DE by the participants of their courses was sudden and immediate. Almost all of them were surprised with the amount of workload that they had to accomplish in transforming their courses. The workload of the educators during this time were described to increase 3-4x.

“Surprising amount of work” (P1, line 07)

“More tasks”(P1, line 15)

“Sobrang daming kailangan” (P3, line 06)

“It took a toll on the faculty members because of, you know, how their workload increased like three-four-five times” (P6, line 33-35)

“Added a lot to the workload....how..how ...so..yeah it was just the workload it was just a lot of work versus face to face” (P2, line 246-247)

Time was highlighted to be of importance when transitioning to DE. Adequate time should be allotted for planning and preparing for the transition, for conducting meetings, for providing and receiving training needed for transitioning to DE, for designing the courses, whether it would be asynchronous, synchronous or hybrid; and preparing the teaching materials.

“Distance education is not ok if you put it if there’s not enough time, if there’s not enough time to do everything you’re supposed to do, so a big component i did not realize that for distance education time is such a huge component. (P2, line 236-239)

“I didn't had enough time to ano prepare yung ano mga materials” (P3, 123-124)

“Additional time that we had to that we had to had in order to adjust to online modalities” (P4-136-137)

“ A population of our student body that would need more time for them to adjust to the new way of learning” (P5, lines 52-53)

“A lot of time was also used familiarizing with what the other options there are online” (P5, line 95-96)

“Preparing the materials eats up a lot of time” (P6, line 49-50)

Planning for distance education would include all the stakeholders, gauging necessary outputs and determining teaching styles. It was stated by one of the participants who was also an administrator that she had to ensure that everyone was included.

“Gauge how much what is necessary, ano yung necessary na outputs tapos gaano katagal ibibigay namin for a certain output.” (P3, line 134-136)

“We make sure that everyone could be included and also how we prepare for things that could and may happen.” (P2, line 423)

“Our department planned as a department, so that’s why there were very little hiccup when we were delivering the program” (P6, line 211-212)

Obtaining feedback is an important aspect of providing DE to maintain the quality of education. Getting feedback from specialists and having enough time to reflect and revise the plans were part of the process the educators experienced in their transition.

“We have, specialist in the team whom I consulted and were able to provide feedback on what should be done” (P6, line 205-206)

With this, the participants were able to transform 10 courses in the 2nd year level, 9 courses in the 3rd year level and 2 major courses in the 4th year level of the BSSLP program into Distance Education.

Administrative Tasks

Transitioning to distance education would require administrative duties and responsibilities. Administrative tasks involve documentation and obtaining an evaluation and feedback on the course programs that were transformed to distance education. Documentation would be submitting weekly detailed reports of activities and student assessments. The document was described to contain information on the capacities and knowledge obtained by the educator and learning activities to deliver distance education.

“Submit Weekly reports, detailed reports, activities, and student assessment” (P1, line 19-20)

“It was more of like a team effort, of being able to provide an example and provide the document and sharing what, you know, what you could do (P6, line 27-29)

Aside from the documentation, a program evaluation was also done. Feedback from students was obtained. Educators received feedback based on the results of

the program evaluation. SWOT (strength, weakness, opportunities, and threats) analysis was also conducted to determine possible problems during their transition and implementation of distance education.

“Have feedback based on the results of the eval “(P3, line 114)

“We did a program evaluation” (P6, line 174-175)

“Feedback from students” (P1, line 113, P2, line 135, P5, line 102)

“I had to just really think of like do SWOT [strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats] analysis (laughs) on what could go wrong (P6, line 203-204)

Leadership

For educational programs a leader guides the staff towards the mission and vision of the organization. One of the administrators noted that one of the challenges in providing DE is convincing the educational team to accept the transition even if the institution is equipped in providing this mode of education. The program director guided the educators in planning for their courses and encouraging them to be ready for possible mishaps.

“I have to lead a department and make them believe that this is achievable” (P6, line 200-201)

Acceptance of distance education and coping on the changes was noted as the concerns of the educators. Due to the sudden migration to DE it was reported by P6 that she had to motivate her team to believe that they are able to transform their courses.

“My apprehension is not, does not really root from us not knowing what to do, but it’s more of the team believing that we can actually do it” (P6, line 15-17)

In this study the identified leader was the program director of the faculty department. The program director was instrumental in having the right mindset towards distance education. Their program director guided the team in planning for distance education.

“Program director was really instrumental towards having the right mindset towards distance education “(P2, line 249)

“Our program director also encouraged us to think about what are the problems that might happen and since we were going at it with that perspective that “okay what could go wrong?” It helped us to plan....make different plans” (P2, line 271-274)

Support for Distance Education

In providing distance education, technological support and educational support were identified to be helpful in delivering distance education. For technological support there was an existing unit within the organization that manages and provides technical support to the educators. The technical unit would be responsible for monitoring the usage of different systems and providing technological assistance through email and calls. They would address and resolve issues related to the learning platform system. It also provided regular webinars for teaching online.

“CITC (Center of Information and Communications Technology) of Institution providing regular webinars for teaching online” (P1, line 85-86)

“Technological assistance that was given was very sufficient” (P5, line 115-116)

“Monitoring how we are all using the systems. (Referring to the CITC) They’re a phone call-away, email-away for concerns that I might have for all the platforms that we are using (P5, line 118-120)

“Technical support from the ICT (CITC or ITC -Information and Communications Technology)” (P6, line 254)

“Support of the faculties is very important “(P5, line 34)

Educational support provided by the institution for the educators were free webinars and seminars. Aside from the free webinars, having a support system and being able to consult experts and their colleagues on technical and educational issues was noted to be helpful.

“Free seminars, webinars” (P2, line 256, P4, line 23,P5, line 134)

“Had a lot of support from the department; We have the specialist needed to execute that, so within the department “ (P6, line 192)

“There’s a support system” (P6, line 194-195)

Limited support system was identified as one of the challenges in distance education. Working from home was noted as difficult for some educators who had to delineate their responsibilities and obligations for their family, and for their work. It was reported that there are times that responsibilities at home and work would overlap.

“I did not feel that there was enough support on my end” (P3, line 44)

“Concerns at home also affected the way we had to adjust to this life” (P4, line 74-76)

Educators needed that support in dealing with work related issues. Being geographically separated from their workmates when working from home reduces physical and social interaction during their break time where they can somehow decompress and find support from their colleagues.

“Support system that I felt was really lacking when we did online was that we didn’t have....we weren’t physically together, and we didn’t have that chit chat during lunch time” (P2, line 279-281)

“I would definitely appreciate the assistance of all my co-faculty members because they were the ones that facilitated how we could learn faster, how we could learn together , and it ended up well, the anxiety”(P5, line 100-102)

Education And Trainings Received by The Faculty During the Transition

Training is needed to equip the educators on how to use technology to provide distance education, as not all educators have the technological skills and knowledge for delivering DE. The educators in this study had to go through several training sessions in a short span of time due to the immediate transition which made it difficult for the educators to prepare the necessary materials for DE. The free webinars and training provided by their institution were noted to be helpful by the educators. The following topics were identified by the educators as helpful for them to transform and deliver their courses to distance education:(1) Learning Management System, (2) Best practices, (3) Test Construction, (4) Experiences with Distance Education, and (5) Creating online materials. Since the learning management system(LMS) was a very helpful tool in organizing and delivering their courses, the educators had to learn to utilize and manage their learning systems. Educators received an online training on

how to utilize the LMS. Some educators took online courses to learn more on how to maximize the LMS.

“LMS [Learning Management System]. -Without the learning platform, i think it’s going to be a very disorganized; the advantage of course of having a learning platform that is paid has all these extended services.....The learning system that we are using basically if you understand it and you know how to maneuver it and use it to your advantage as a teacher, you wouldn’t have problems “ (P5, line 141-147)

Providing distance education is a novel experience for educators who had no previous experience in teaching and learning through this modality; and have no formal education on distance education. The organization equipped their educators with information on best practices , test construction, creating online materials and shared experiences in distance education which were deemed helpful. There was a lot of time spent on creating online materials and learning how to use different applications. Faculties who had training on distance education and had personally experienced this modality shared information that was noted to help their colleagues to gain more confidence in providing teaching and learning activities for their students.

“We had faculty members who were trained to provide; shared experiences with online modalities” (P4, line 49-50)

“We had training on test construction” (P4, line 61, P6, line 1175)

“ We also discuss the different best practices for each of the courses done during the semester or the year and it helped us adjust” (P4, line 64-66)

”We underwent training” (P4, line 49)”

“Trainings for Blackboard” (P3, line 96)

“There were a lot of hours spent on learning how to do things, learning how to create online materials.” (P5, line 94-95)

The educators also took the initiative to do self- studying and research to understand distance education. Some educators had to look up references and online resources on online education. They would seek personal consultation from other people who are not part of the institution who they think are more knowledgeable in distance education. Educators would personally work on familiarizing themselves with the learning platform and look for other options they can use for teaching.

“Mostly experiential yung parang nagresearch ka rin kaw rin mismo magfamiliarize sa sarili mo dun sa platform so yon” (P3, line 48-50)

“Some the faculty members also researched also did some readings on different studies regarding online education, so they also shared what they learned to other faculty” (P4, line 51-52)

“A lot of time was also used familiarizing with what the other options there are online that we can use” (P5, line 95-96)

“I had to also ask for assistance from people that I know are knowledgeable with um, these things that we are going to be using, I’m going to be using for the first time.” (P5, line 109-110)

*“I had to seek help from external people that are more familiar with it
“(P5, line 111-112)*

“I had to do my own research” (P5, line 112)

“I had to look it into references or resources online that would help me understand better how could use these different modes online” (P5, line 112-114)

*“I scour through the internet about these practices and the application”
(P6, line 152-153)*

Training for distance education was identified as one of their best practices during their transition. It motivated the educators to implement DE and receive more formal education and training that will help them transform their courses .

“I don't think everything that was thought before was really made me very prepared (P3, line 98-99)

“More training would be the best practice for conducting online or distance learning for our students” (P4, line 168)

“I will attend more training, formal training, formal education” (P4, line 168)

Here are some suggestions from the educators on training and assistance needed for DE: (1)Provide training for beginners in DE, (2) assistance from co-faculty in delivering DE, (3)more exposure to online teaching and lastly (4) more frequent workshops that they can access on their own time.

Promoting Quality of Life

Educators had mixed reactions during the initial transition to distance education. The pandemic made the transformation of all their courses that were traditionally delivered in face-to-face mode of education sudden and immediate. Dread, anxiety, and resistance were felt by the educators. Anxiety and dread were felt on the workload that they had to accomplish. They also felt frustrated and stressed out on the additional workload and the adjustments that they had to do in a short span of time. Frustration was felt when they had difficulty adjusting to DE completely. An educator described it as having a mismatch of expectations.

“Mismatch with the expectations” (P1, line 21)

“I was doing more than the work that I would've done had it been face to face so tung transition na yan was really stressful” (P3, line 104-106)

Doubts on their capacity to transform their courses into DE were also expressed. As stated by one of the educators, she felt that she wasn't prepared enough to deliver DE. Some of them were questioning whether their assessments were hitting the course outcomes.

“I was also questioning whether the activities i have prepared or my assessments were they really hitting the course outcomes” (P3, line 108-109)

There were a few who were confident in achieving the program outcomes and were satisfied with the results of distance education.

“I'm still confident that we were able to achieve the program outcomes of our students even if it was conducted online.” (P1, line 127-128)

“I was pretty satisfied with the way the students' outcome final outcome were made and how I saw their evolution” (P6, line 213-214)

DE was described to be time consuming and it resulted in feelings of being overworked. The sudden transition involved transforming their courses and an overwhelming amount of workload such as recording their lectures and constructing assessments fit for DE. Some educators still prefer face to face because of the physical interaction that it provides. Time is needed to adjust to distance education.

“Still want face to face there's a human component that needs to translate physically” (P2, line 305-306)

“It will take time before you get used to that kind of modality” (P3, line 139)

Their first run of DE was a learning experience that made them ready to deliver DE the following semester.

“We have to do it all again for one whole year and then there were some adjustments again but I think we were more ready because of the things that we learn when we ran it the first time. (P2, line 208-210)

Generally, all educators were happy and satisfied with the outcomes of distance education after its implementation. An educator noted that he was able to adjust to the work from home setting and it was able to reduce the risk of acquiring the COVID-19 virus. Distance education made it possible for the institution to provide quality education during the pandemic while protecting them from contracting the virus.

“Minimizes the risk of contracting the infection “(P1, line 12)

“Prefer DE because we can still achieve outcomes without being infected with covid19” (P1, line 130-131)

“I was able to adjust with the work from home setting” (P1, line 22)

“Happy I’m happy with how we ran it because I think whenever we like for me especially since I handled the pre internship courses like diags and intervention. Whenever I see them working together with the patients I really do not see a lot of difference” (P2, line 322-325)

“I think distance education actually help um us to still provide quality education for our students given that we're at home” (P4, 161-162)

With Distance Education the educators were able to achieve their learning outcomes, provide quality education in the comfort of their homes, while being protected from communicable diseases. Some educators noted that upon adjusting

with the work-from-home setting, they found it to be more comfortable and relaxing. It gave them more time to spend with their family and enjoy their free time.

“More comfortable or relaxed in the setting in the work from home” (P1, line 10-11)

“Making the most of your time also with your family because you get to spend more time with them” (P2, line 296-297)

The educators realized that DE has its similarities with face-to-face education. An educator stated that DE is not as different as what other people think, another participant stated that it is similar but there will be certain adjustments.

“ There still similar but few adjustments for DE (P1, line 140)

“It is not as different as a lot of people might think.” (P5, line 184-185)

“I do not see a lot of difference whether it is done f2f or online” (P2, line 324-325)

“Wala siyang masyadong difference” (P3, line 32-22)

Another educator stated that it wasn't fair to say that face to face was better than DE. It was reported by one of the participants of the study that their DE practice was recognized by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) as one of the best practices for the BS SLP program.

“Not fair to say DE better than face to face” (P2, line 360)

“..the government regulation body (CHED) thought that we had the best practice amongst all four university” (P6, line 149-150)

Providing Accessible and Online Learning Resources

Learning resources are critical tools in providing education. In distance education, most of the learning resources are accessible online. Educators had to maximize the online resources that were already available in their institution to provide the same learning experience they provide in their face-to-face classes. Some of the materials used in face-to-face mode of education were transformed or migrated online.

“Putting materials on the screen and then utilizing it in terms of how they would use it in classrooms” (P2, line 94-95)

“Maximizing the materials” (P5, line 42, P1 line 63, P2 line 347)

“We were able to do is to maximize, again the online resources available for them to be able to experience the same hands-on learning that we are providing in the lab sessions” (P5, line 42-44)

“Nakapagmigrate din ako that time ng mga materials” (P3, line 41)

The following materials were provided to their students for distance education: video demonstrations, supplementary videos, and accessible websites. Students were also given access to recorded lectures, recorded demonstrations, and recorded classes. The transformation to DE provided recorded lectures to the students which was considered to be advantageous for their learning as it gave the learners the capacity to review and play back lectures.

“Ask the students to access materials that were recorded” (P4, line 10-11)

“Lectures had been recorded” (P1, line 08, P6, line 1022)

“We would make recordings for them to access at a given time” (P5, line 24-25)

“Prepare video demonstrations in advance” (P1, line 48-49)

“Provide Supplementary videos” (P1, line 49-50)

“Accessible websites “(P1, line 50-51)

“Recorded sessions” (P1, line 08, P2 line 316, P3, line 26, P4, line 10-11, P6 lin 52e)

Students were observed to be more comfortable working in front of the camera. They were able to maximize the learning materials given to them by the educators. They were able to go back to the lectures and ask for clarification.

“The advantage of doing online classes, is yun nga everything is recorded they get to play it back when they don't understand something” (P3, line 154-156)

“Students making most of the material that is given to them” (P2, line 318-319)

“ Everyone was comfortable with the camera already” (P2, line 314-315)

Distance education was identified to have its own advantages and challenges in this study. It was able to prevent the spread of the COVID-19 virus by separating the learners and educators physically and yet allowing the students to continue to learn. Educators were able to develop the planning skills of their students and understand the learning styles of their students through distance education. However, given its physical separation from the learners and instructors there are certain limitations to this mode of education. Educators noted that even with their current technology, a pure online distance education may not be able to address learning skills that would require physical manipulation or actual handling. Congruent to the study by Zhu and Zhang (2021) wherein the researchers noted the importance of hands-on experience for building relationships and developing practical skills. Debnath et. Al (2021) also noted practical knowledge as questionably achieved in online learning.

With this, I would suggest exploring other modes of learning to achieve practical knowledge. A flexible learning as suggested by the Commission on Higher Education, (2020) can be considered. Flexible learning is defined by the Commission on Higher Education, (2020) as a pedagogical approach that allows changes in time, place and audience and does not solely rely on technology. This would cover other modes of learning such as face to face, out of classroom learning or a combination of both. This would provide the needed physical interaction to further develop the practical skills needed in medical and allied medical courses.

There were challenges in providing assessments and communication in distance education. Additional security measures on summative assessments were applied to ensure the integrity of assessments. With communication, there is a noted difference in the speed of exchange in the communication between the students and the educators. Unlike in face to face wherein immediate feedback is received, communicating with the use of email, chat rooms and video conferencing would still have a delay in the responses among the communicators. Rajab, et. Al (2020) noted communication and use of assessment as one of the challenges of medical education in distance education. With these identified challenges, shifting the focus on innovative practices as suggested by Garrison (2000), and recognizing the changes and evolution of instructional designing for distance education should be applied for distance education to address these issues and catch up with the technological developments.

Delivering distance education; or transitioning from face to face to distance education requires leadership and strategic planning. Pahal (1999) noted that leaders are considered as motivators and decision makers. Leadership was noted by the educators as a critical component that motivated and guided their transition to

distance education. This study outcomes presented that leadership involves motivating the team to accept changes and move forward. The importance of having a leader was recognized by the educators as someone who directed them towards the transformation to distance education.

Planning and training were important aspects when transitioning to distance education. However, time was a critical factor for planning and implementation of distance education. In this study, time was limited due to the immediate transition from face to face to distance education because of the pandemic . Adequate time should be allotted on training and orientation on the technology needed for DE. Transitioning to DE involves allocating and organizing learning resources, designing or restructuring programs, and constructing assessments. Institutions needed to allot time for training and orientation for all stakeholders on the needs and requirements of distance education. Orientation and training with the different technologies is important for both students and educators. Both stakeholders should be familiar in managing and manipulating their online learning applications to decrease anxiety and effectively deliver their courses and facilitate interaction. The study showed evidence on how the educators benefited from the training and workshops provided by the institution in learning to manage the learning management system they used for delivering the DE courses. Though educators were given educational support, some of them took the initiative of learning the different software and applications they felt they needed for teaching. Their institution was equipped with technical support which all educators noted as important in assisting their transformation to distance education. The technical support given by their institution was highlighted as one factor that eased their transition from face to face to distance education by addressing technical concerns of both the students and educators. Nabolsi's et. Al (2021) study highlighted

the lack of support, limited training, time for planning and preparing online learning resources for distance education as their challenges in distance education. This study has shown similarities in the constraints of planning and training due to the sudden shift to distance education because of the pandemic. The study has further shown the importance of training, having ample technical support in assisting educators in managing technology and resolving technical issues. Adequate time allotment is also important for strategic planning, implementation, training and evaluation of programs transformed to distance education .

Distance education is described to have the same components of face-to-face education. There were identified similarities in the aspect of management, teaching and learning, and technology. In terms of management, both Distance education and face to face mode of education requires leadership and planning. This will guide and monitor the transformation and maintain the quality of education provided to the students. Assessment and evaluation of the program in both modes of education is a critical component to further improve and maintain the quality of education provided. Another similarity noted were the course and program outcomes. Achieving the program and course outcomes are the compass for the educators in designing their courses. Each course in this program aims to achieve the expected learning and program outcomes by restructuring their teaching and learning strategies with the use of technology to transform their courses into distance education. Though there are similarities such as the content of lectures, use of PowerPoint presentations, facilitating interactions with oral discussion; differences were present in the teaching practices. Differences were identified in the teaching practices of the educators in delivering the content, constructing, providing, and securing assessments, facilitating communication, and interaction. The program and learning outcomes for each course,

either it be face to face or distance education remained constant. Tatum (2019) noted that efficiency in education can be described in many aspects in education such as learning outcomes and competencies. The following elements were listed by Ball (2017) for a systematic evaluation of educational programs: having defined goals and intended outcomes; adequately measuring impact of programs thru standardized assessments or domain-reference test, having formative and summative type of assessment, a specialized instrument that can be developed and establishing rapport within the community where data can be properly gathered. Ball (2017) highlighted the importance of collecting evidence-based data from different sources of assessment, observations that would be significant for determining the effectiveness of the program to be evaluated. All educators noted that they were able to achieve the set program and course outcomes for their courses in distance education. This study has presented empirical data noting that in this selected allied medical program achieving the program outcomes was a critical component to determine the effectiveness of distance education.

The study presented that distance education was able to target and achieve the same learning and program outcomes and improve the planning and communication skills of their students. It provided a realization that allied medical programs can be delivered in other modes of education. Distance Education made the program more inclusive by extending the reach where education and services can be provided. This is a contradiction to the findings of Todri et. Al(2021) wherein the study stated that distance education can only be successfully used as a complementary approach compared to the traditional mode of education. As this study has shown that it could be another option on the mode of delivery of formal education by institutions. In addition, distance education has somehow contributed to improving

the quality of life of the educators by protecting them from contracting a communicable disease, providing them with more time with their families by reducing time allotted for traveling to work.

In terms of teaching practices, the study presented how instructional design and technology is intertwined. Technology was identified as a critical element that is incorporated into all the components of distance education, namely management, teaching, and learning. Instructional design has been an integral part of education to effectively impart knowledge to students. Smith and Ragan (1999 in Botturi, L. 2003,p.5) defined instructional design as

“ The systematic and reflective process of translating principles of learning and instruction into plans for instructional materials, activities, information resources and evaluation.”

(Smith and Ragan 1999 in Botturi, L. 2003,p.5)

In this study, instructional design of a course was highlighted as an important aspect in both face to face and distance education in addressing transactional distance. This study is congruent to Delgaty’s (2018) findings on the importance of instructional design to address transactional distance. The educators used different software such as their LMS, Email, online forums, and video conferencing applications to communicate with their students, provide feedback and clarifications. Furthermore, in transforming their courses, educators had to keep in mind their learning principles, learning and program outcomes, learning styles of their students in selecting their teaching and learning activities. Technology was identified as a critical aspect in determining the mode of communication and interaction for their courses; namely synchronous, asynchronous or hybrid which is a mixture of both asynchronous and synchronous interaction. Restructuring courses would involve selecting and designing

the mode of communication and interaction between learners, content, and educators. Technology was used in securing the integrity of assessments.

Learning how to manage and use the different technologies needed to deliver the content of their courses, facilitate interaction, construct, and secure assessments, and provide feedback should be part of the training educators in distance education. The educators had to learn how to maximize different software and applications, such as the learning management systems to deliver their courses, to prevent leakage and cheating during summative assessments such as their practical exams and performance tasks. With the assistance of technology, the educators were able to interact and communicate with their students and keep them motivated in accomplishing their courses. Technology and their student's learning styles influenced how educators provided learning resources, restructured their learning activities and assessments. Technology included learning management systems, internet connections, educational software, email, accessible websites, Microsoft office applications and video conferencing applications. The capacity of online learning management systems, with their existing chat rooms, discussion forums, and the use of applications such as Google mail, Zoom and Google Meet were used to deliver the content of the course program, receive, and submit course requirements, facilitate interaction and communication synchronously and asynchronously.

Distance Education has been evolving with the influence of technologies. Taylor (2001) discussed 5 models of distance education which were based on the technology used. From the first model the Correspondence Model which was based on print technology; Second, the Multi-media Model which involves print, audio and video technologies; Third, the Tele-learning Model, that involves the telecommunications technologies that allowed for synchronous communication;

Fourth, the Flexible Learning Model where the use of internet was initially introduced for delivery; and Fifth, Intelligent Flexible Learning Model is based on the extended use of the web and the internet. The 5th generation was described by Taylor as having the capacity to use interactive multimedia online, having computer mediated responses using automated responses and having a campus portal for resources and institutional processes. Today's technology has the capacity to provide and extend services needed for distance education. The use of a web-based learning environment and a learning management system (LMS) such as Moodle and Blackboard has been highlighted in this research as an important aspect of delivering distance education. It allowed the institution to provide a variety of services to their students and educators. This includes access to online resources, delivery, and storage of content of the course program, automated and non-automated exams, embedding of multimedia for teaching and conducting assessments, and facilitating asynchronous and synchronous communication and interaction. Teaching and learning online in today's generation involves automation but most importantly a responsive interface that provides an organized and improved learning experience.

Garrison (2000) characterized distance education as having an adaptability design before and during the teaching and learning process through an interactive technology. He further noted that understanding the limitations and opportunities of facilitating teaching and learning with the use of different technology and addressing transactional issues as one of the biggest challenges of distance education. This study supports the characteristics of distance education as described by Garrison (2000). Aside from the LMS, this generation also includes the usage of online interactive software for video conferencing and educational applications. The introduction of video conferencing applications such as Zoom and Google meet that has the capacity

to access different multimedia presentations and facilitate communication through their chat rooms provided diversity in the interaction of distance education. With this, it was important for educators to have access to the web-based learning environment and learn the different usage of these software such as their LMS, educational and interactive applications to deliver their courses efficiently and to communicate effectively with their students.

The Phenomenological Model of Distance Education

The outcome of the study is a phenomenological model of distance education that explains why educators in the allied field engage in DE by understanding their meaning. Meaning is constituted by the perspectives and practices of distance education. The phenomenological model presents the various perspectives of the educators and how these perspectives influenced the educators practices and engagement in DE. With the findings of my study the TIE theory on distance education has emerged. The name of the theory is an acronym of the essence of distance education that was constructed thru the meticulous constant comparison and analysis of the data gathered.

The TIE theory states the following on distance education (a) Transitioning to DE involves planning and provision of accessible learning resources to provide a formal mode of distance education that can promote the quality of life of the educators and the learners, (b) Instructional designing and technology are intertwined in the teaching practices of DE to address transactional distance and secure the integrity and quality of education and (c) Education that is equivalent to face-to-face mode of education that uses varying modes of communication to address the needs of the learners, achieve learning and program outcomes and expand educational services.

Figure 5. The Phenomenological Model of Distance Education

Chapter VI

RESEARCH SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

The research aims to discover why educators in the allied medical field engage in distance education. To answer this question the researcher looked into their perspectives and practices to obtain the essence of distance education in the allied medical field. A qualitative study with a grounded theory approach within a phenomenological tradition was applied to gather data and gain knowledge. The phenomenological tradition with the methodology of the grounded theory approach was applied in this study to gather data, analyze and understand the accounts of six teachers in an allied medical program at a private university. The phenomenological tradition in research was applied for this study as it can obtain authentic data by providing open ended questions and flexibility that allows the participants to narrate salient events and experiences significant to distance education. By applying the strength of the traditional qualitative research approach to a methodical approach in data analysis, theory is built through the analysis of relationships through the components revealed within a phenomenon (Brower 1995, in Jeong, 2009).

The study was conducted at a private university providing allied medical courses. Educators who transformed and delivered their courses through distance education participated in this study. All participants had no formal education in DE. Online individual interviews were conducted to gather data on their experiences of distance education.

The study presented several critical pieces of information on distance education that will benefit the allied medical field of education. It has presented a phenomenological model that provides information on the perspectives, practices in teaching and transitioning to DE. The study was able to identify the contributions of distance education as well as its limitations from face-to-face education in an allied medical program.

The study has provided data on the teaching practices and the impact of technology in delivering distance education. The study presented how technology has evolved and enabled the educators to address transactional distance and provide quality education. The study showed the importance of planning, technology, leadership, instructional designing, training, and support for delivering and transitioning to distance education.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study generated the TIE theory of distance education that explains the meaning of distance education, their teaching practices, and the rationale for practicing distance education in the allied medical field of education. The TIE theory states the following: a) Transitioning to DE involves planning and provision of accessible learning resources to provide a formal mode of distance education that can promote the quality of life of the educators and the learners, (b) Instructional designing and technology are intertwined in the teaching practices of DE to address transactional distance and secure the integrity and quality of education and (c) Education that is equivalent to face-to-face mode of education that uses varying modes of communication to address the needs of the learners, achieve learning and program outcomes and expand educational services.

The outcome of the study has contributed by providing a phenomenological model of distance education that presents the perspectives on DE and the practices in teaching and transitioning to distance education in the field of allied medical education. Distance education is seen as equivalent to the face-to-face mode of education, using various modes of communication that can expand the educational services and address the needs of the learners. It is an equivalent mode of education to the face-to-face mode of education as it can target the same course and program outcomes and provide quality education. The physical separation of the student from the educators resulted in using varying modes and speed of communication that can deliver content, facilitate interaction, and communication that enabled the institution to expand educational and allied medical services.

The teaching practices were guided by these perspectives which led the educators to capitalize on technology for transforming assessments and addressing transactional distance. Teaching and learning activities and assessments would provide the same learning experience and measure the same outcomes as the traditional mode of education. To secure the integrity and quality of assessments additional security measures were applied. Teaching practices in distance education involved technology, technical knowledge and instructional designing.

Distance Education in this field of education incorporated technology in their instructional design to be able facilitate communication and interaction among the learners and educators. Technology aided the educators in addressing transactional distance when delivering their courses. This includes the selection and management of different software and hardware needed for transforming and providing learning resources, activities, and assessments into an online modality to achieve the learning outcomes of the program. This study has shown the evolution of educational

applications by having a responsive interface and a learning management system that facilitated the provision of distance education. Technology was a critical component for determining the level of interaction between the content, educators, and the learners. The structure of the program is highly influenced by the capacity of the technology involved in the delivery and facilitation of the course content and activities.

The practices in transitioning to distance education involved planning, provision of accessible learning resources and promoting quality of life of stakeholders. Distance education involves preparation and planning prior to its implementation. It would require leadership and adequate time allotment for planning, training, construction of learning materials, and evaluation. Educators would need technical and educational support to successfully transform their courses to distance education and provide accessible learning resources for their students. The quality of life should also be improved through distance education. This study has shown how distance education made it possible for educators to provide quality education while improving the quality of life by providing more time for their families, more time to enjoy their free time while protecting them from contracting communicable diseases.

The allied medical program benefited from distance education as it promoted inclusivity, outcome-based education, student-educator relationships, improved student's written communication, quality of feedback and the quality of life of educators. Distance education was able to provide formal education to their students that is equivalent to the face to face mode of education and expanded educational services with the use of various modes of communication. The study was able to provide significant rationale for the provision of distance education in the allied medical field.

Recommendations

Theoretical Recommendations

The generated theory and phenomenological model of distance education have provided an explanation on the meaning and purpose of distance education. It is therefore recommended that researchers may further explore and expand the model in different fields of education. There are significant differences with the curriculum, discipline and practice of other medical programs. The exploration and further development of the TIE theory may further improve the framework of distance education in the medical and allied medical field of education and will greatly contribute to improving the quality of distance education. Gathering more data on the extent of how technology can expand the medical and educational services is also recommended to further determine the opportunities distance education can provide.

Methodological Recommendations

It is also recommended to conduct further socio-cultural constructivist qualitative studies such as ethnographic or auto ethnographic studies focusing on how technology influences distance education. Technological advances may vary in different cultures and communities. Exploring this aspect in different educational communities will be able to provide us with more insights on how technology is intertwined in instructional design and will gather more data on the extent of technology in enhancing distance education. It is also recommended to conduct research studies, quantitative, qualitative or mix methods that will look further into the barriers and facilitators in providing and securing assessments in distance education. Development of an assessment or program evaluation tool that is based on the TIE

theory that can be used for program evaluation of distance education is also suggested to aid in monitoring and maintaining the quality of education.

Practical Recommendations

The study has proven that distance education can provide teaching and learning activities that can achieve the learning outcomes set for an allied medical program, it is respectfully recommended to include distance education in the curriculum of allied medical education. Having other modalities for learning provide more opportunities for students to receive formal education. Development of policies for the provision of distance education as a formal mode of education in the allied medical field is also recommended to establish proper guidelines and reinforce the standards of an allied medical program in distance education.

It is also recommended to provide more formal training to educators and proper orientation to students to be more equipped with the skills needed for distance education. Training for students and educators specifically on the management and usage of various technologies needed for DE, as well as accessing and using online educational resources is highly recommended to address limitations and encourage self-directed learning. Conducting needs assessment in institutions transitioning from face to face to distance education is highly recommended to further identify the needs of all stakeholders in delivering distance education. And lastly, conducting program evaluations is recommended to monitor and maintain the standard and quality of distance education as the face-to-face mode of education.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Letter Of Invitation

Dear Sir/ Ma'am _____,

Greetings.

I am Ma. Freya Carungcong, a full time faculty of CRS- SLP Department and currently a Masters of Distance Education (MDE) student of the University of the Philippines Open University (UPOU).

I would like to request your participation in my study entitled:

"Distance Education as Experienced by Educators in an Allied Medical Program: A Grounded Theory Approach within the Phenomenological Tradition"

This is my final requirement to complete the MDE program of UPOU. Methodology, ethical considerations, and content of this study were reviewed by UPOU and my research adviser, Prof. Jean A. Saludadez, PhD, Vice Chancellor for Finance and Administration of UPOU.

The main objective of the study is to obtain information on the understanding and meaning of distance education to educators in an allied medical program.

As a faculty and administrator who has been teaching in the study site-CRS- SLP Department for more than 1 school year and have delivered and supervised an SLP course in both modalities, traditional and distance education of the same curriculum; you are deemed qualified to participate in my study.

Participation in this study would require a 1:1 unstructured online interview via Google meet or Zoom. The interview may take 20-30 minutes of your time. Interviews will be recorded and will be recursive. Recurring interviews will be done to further seek clarification of initial information from the first interview and this will be done in your most convenient time using the same software.

All demographic data will be kept private and confidential. Access to data collected will be exclusive to the researcher. Pseudonyms will be assigned to each participant to secure their identity. Processing of data submitted will only be conducted with your consent and if needed, approval and consent of the institution. You will be requested to validate transcripts of interviews conducted between you and the researcher. Amendments will be allowed to strengthen the accuracy of the data gathered.

Participation in this study involves responsibility with the information you will be providing. This entails the premise that data shared are factual, complete, accurate, true and correct to the best of your knowledge.

Participation in this study is voluntary and will be very much appreciated.

Consent form will be sent upon your acceptance of this invitation.

Upon request, I can furnish you a copy of the final results of my study as soon as I have accomplished and defended my research.

Thank you and I'm looking forward to your response.

Respectfully,

Ma. Freya L. Talisaysay- Carungcong, CSP-PASP

APPENDIX B

Consent Form

Title of the Study:

Researcher: Ma. Freya T. Carungcong, CSP-PASP

Contact information:

Email address:, mtcarungcong@up.edu.ph

Contact numbers:

Purpose of the study:

The main objective of the study is to obtain information on the understanding and meaning of distance education to educators in an allied medical program

Voluntary Participation:

Participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign this consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time and without giving a reason. Withdrawing from this study will not affect the relationship you have, if any, with the researcher. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be returned to you or destroyed.

Requirements:

Participation in this study would require a 1:1 unstructured online interview via Google meet or Zoom. The interview may take 20-30 minutes of your time. Interviews will be recorded and will be recursive. Recurring interviews will be done to further seek clarification of initial information from the first interview and this will be done in your most convenient time using the same software. You will be requested to validate transcripts of interviews conducted between you and the researcher. Amendments will be allowed to strengthen the accuracy of the data gathered. Participation in this study involves responsibility with the information you will be providing. This entails the premise that data shared are factual, complete, accurate, true and correct to the best of your knowledge.

Risk: Participants will have no physical risks in their participation in this study. Intellectual properties will be respected and protected. However, this study would require a few minutes of their time, internet connection and devices with Zoom or Google Meet for their participation in the online interview, Adobe for signing pdf documents and Microsoft Word for editing documents.

Benefits: Your participation may provide depth to the concept of distance education and may provide critical information that may further improve the delivery of distance education in the selected study site

Confidentiality:

All demographic data will be kept private and confidential. Access to data collected will be exclusive to the researcher. Pseudonyms will be assigned to each participant

to secure their identity. Processing of data submitted will only be conducted with your consent and if needed, approval and consent of the institution.

Please check all applicable items:

1. I confirm that I have been working in the selected institution for more than a year as an educator/ administrator

YES

NO

2. Position:

Administrator of

Full time faculty

Part time faculty

3. I confirm that I have handled and delivered BSSLP course/s of the same curriculum at the study site in both modalities of education: face to face and online.

YES

NO

CONSENT:

I have read and I understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I hereby allow the researcher to record our online interviews, use and share all data given the agreed conditions stated above

I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form.

I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

.

Participant's Initials and Signature _____ Date _____

Researcher's Signature _____
_____ Date _____

APPENDIX C

Initial Codes of P1-P6

Initial codes of P1

- Facilitate Voice disorder, Motor speech condition, Research 1 & 2.
- Surprising amount of work
- recording or preparing prerecorded lectures
- More comfortable or relaxed in the setting in the work from home
- minimizes the risk of contracting the infection
- Surprising Workload
- More tasks
- Submit Weekly reports, detailed reports, activities and student assessment
- Preparing and prerecorded lectures in advance
- Extra work
- Mismatch with the expectations
- Able to adjust with the work from home setting
- I Like the comfort of working from home
- Spending more time with family
- More time for me to relax and enjoy free time
- Lecture presentation were more or less the same
- Adjust class activities
- Using online video conference platform like Google Meet or Zoom
- Lecture no major changes for the activities
- Slight adjustment for student assessments
- Adjust the task to make it more feasible in the online setting

- Online video conference platform,
- Course learning outcomes and program outcomes stayed the same.
- There were differences during F2F
- Use of worksheet during F2F
- DE all of it were transformed to electronic
- Worksheet accomplished electronically
- Instead of white board resorted to annotate function of zoom
- Prepare video demonstrations in advance
- Provide Supplementary videos
- Accessible websites
- Innovative ways to assess same skills online
- Challenging to assess the skills
- Consider more factors in online assessment
- Workload of student
- Bandwidth requirement
- Platform
- Students had to adjust with sudden change
- Provide accommodations
- Communicate with students Using institutional email
- Used the learning management system
- Provide feedback
- Synchronous video online calls discussion
- Use short messaging applications
- LMS for posting lecture materials
- Use Video conferencing

- Using PowerPoint presentations
- Not confident about video editing
- Cannot use adobe photoshop to prepare more complex materials for teaching
- CITC of Institution providing regular webinars for teaching online
- Comfortable facilitating activities used in f2f: Raising questions, waiting students to respond thru chat or opening cameras
- Using the whiteboard, annotate function zoom to exemplify further the concept
- Use LMS for quality academic assessment and for accreditation
- Easier to deliver course online since we already using LMS: Using Online exam, Using Google forms to facilitate peer evaluation
- We still want to achieve the course and program outcomes regardless of the mode of delivery
- Ensuring quality of education
- Ensure that Program outcomes and year level outcomes are being achieved
- Effectiveness of online education is similar to face to face.
- Passing and Attrition rate did not drastically change
- Satisfied with their (the student's) performance
- Faculty evaluation of the students provide more positive comments on quality of feedback in online education
- Similarities
- I'm still confident that we were able to achieve the program outcomes of our students even if it was conducted online.

- Prefer DE because we can still achieve outcomes without being infected with covid19
- DE is delivering course curriculum remotely
- Facilitating teaching and learning strategies
- Achieving set course year level and program outcomes
- Only Difference is that we don't interact directly or f2f with students
- Cannot see them f2f and facilitate the activity f2f and everything for me stays the same
- Actual interaction to facilitate learning outcome still the same
- There still similar but few adjustments for DE
- Making the Practical exam thru synchronous video call
- Having them (the students) upload videos
- Accommodation/changes needed since we can't do it face to face
- Learn to navigate and be proficient in using Learning apps, LMS and Videoconferencing

Initial Codes of P2

- Acquired Language and Cognitive Conditions (ALCC)
- Dysphagia
- Introduction to Audiology
- Diags Introduction to Diagnostics
- Anatomy and Physiology for SLP
- Neuroanatomy for SLP
- Intervention & Clinical Reasoning
- Aural Habilitation

- CRP1 (Clinical Reasoning)
- Counseling
- Aural habilitation
- We are already utilizing zoom and had Moodle(LMS)
- We had Moodle to share lectures and get submission of the students that helped in the transition
- Introduce teletherapy, get them(the students) comfortable with the idea
- Wait for the guidelines coming from PASP (Philippine Association of Speech Pathologists)
- Structuring the program
- Capacity of the students to cope with the sudden change
- Introductory courses helped them (the students) it was a way to guide them
- Concern about the student's internet connection
- Concern about students who did not have stable internet connection and not ready for online service delivery at home
- Make alternative plans to meet the outcomes.
- Limited interaction with actual patients
- Bandwidth
- Internet is a concern for some students.
- Recorded sessions
- Sacrificed Dysphagia - activities that require palpation
- Did not lose the outcomes that were set
- Basic course did not have much issues
- Had materials on hand

- Putting materials on the screen and then utilizing it in terms of how they would use it in classrooms
- Adjust the method of evaluation of the students
- Integrity of how the students would be able to respond to the quizzes and the exams.
- Answers are readily available on the internet,
- we did multiple cameras, so one camera for viewing the exams and another to view the student as they were actually completing the exams
- Utilize (google) meet and zoom
- Translating everything and delivering online.
- Teaching and learning were able to convert it online completely
- Done almost asynchronously
- Structured meetings
- Make sure that even if we're all online we want to feel connected
- Showcase some outputs of students and view it like an expo
- View materials students did and learn from each other
- We had to do a technical meeting
- Enough time to plan ahead and given enough time to be given feedback and then revised some of the plans
- plan ahead of time
- i had a backup plan
- adjustments
- provide feedback as soon as possible
- Distance education is not ok if you put it if there's not enough time
- Time is such a huge component.

- email, via written communication takes a lot of turnaround time
- added a lot to the workload
- Program director was really instrumental towards having the right mindset towards distance education
- a shift in the method of delivery
- never going to be a change in the content
- outcomes needs to be met.
- Free seminars, webinars
- modify activities
- utilize and maximize Moodle,
- maximize your LMS helps a lot
- rooted on your philosophies, your theories
- modifying your teaching and learning activities f
- maximizing the materials that are readily available
- program director also encouraged us
- Support system that il felt was really lacking
- we weren't physically together,
- group chats really helped having the group chat with the faculty
- schedule meetings like for example after class and then we just talk about what happened in class and it helps you process the things that happened
- Generally happy with how we did it.
- Still Want f2f , there's a human component that needs to translate physically
- recording session, recording lecture
- Everyone was comfortable with the camera already

- Benefits of having the lecture recorded, students can go back and clarify
- Students making most of the material that is given to them
- I do not see a lot of difference whether it is done f2f or online
- A lot of components honed when done online-ex. Planning of students
- Student's communicating better, better written communication
- DE cannot provide -posture, expressions, small physical reactions can be pick up better if f2f
- Not fair to say DE better than f2f
- You try to engage your students as much as you can
- You don't know what's happening to them at home kasi we don't require them to open their cameras
- breakout rooms.
- You have to confirm and validate what's happening to them and if it was a face-to-face class than its gonna be easier because you see the groups already working together.
- We do the live zoom lectures
- you also see how different kinds of learners respond to stimuli
- We use zoom, since zoom had a direct message option there are some students who would send questions to me via direct message
- phone in question
- We make sure that everyone could be included
- we prepare for things that could and may happen.
- more inclusive :we were able to reach students who are not within the area ... from different areas

- It provided us with a wider net for expansion and consideration of the needs of others
- It does work for some students like some students who might be too quiet or might be too shy when they are in the classroom might do work really well while they're on DE
- connect more personally with the faculty members at a more personal level because
- communicate regularly with them either through email, direct message on chat

Initial Codes of P3

- Aural Hab and Senior sem 1
- May resistance
- May dread
- Sobrang daming kailangan
- Change sa platform
- Nagbago din yung LMS
- Anxiety over sa mga posibleng madaming gawin
- Kailangan palitan or mag isip ng accommodation
- identify yung kailangan naming gawin for synchronous
- Kailangan namin identify pano namin mababago yung outputs na usually required for face to face
- Maghanap ng platform na magagawa ng intern kahit papano pa rin yung nagagawa nila sa face to face
- research yung sa zoom kung paano gamitin yun

- kailangan namin itrain sarili namin and yung intern din paano gamitin yung zoom, materials for internship
- Modifying yung mga lectures
- Recorded na lectures
- mga exams, written exams to online
- Wala siyang masyadong difference
- Course outcomes nahihit naman
- Nakakapagturo pa rin kami
- skill based naasses pa rin
- Course outcomes and learning outcomes wala siyang masyadong difference
- Teaching style- mas maraming preparation and planning for online
- Prerecorded lecture
- Gumagamit din ako ng mga ibang modalities (halimbawa h5p)
- Titingnan mo muna kung akma kung alin dun ang pinaka okay na material bago mo siya incorporate sa lectures mo.
- Moodle
- Nakapagmigrate din ako that time ng mga materials
- Lectures for blackboard
- Mostly experiential yung parang nagrererearch ka rin kaw rin mismo magfafamiliarize sa sarili mo dun sa platform so yon
- Majority is adjustment phase
- For internship parang 1 week kayong puro classroom muna synchronous
- internship -andami niyang planning
- Sinasala namin para lang magfit muna siya dun sa kakayanan namin

- Bandwidth considerations
- Pareho lang ang demand
- I dont think there's alot of difference kase the topics were maintained ganon
- nahihit parin yung outcomes.
- The only difference is how we assess ; pag skills paano mo siya itatranslate into online
- things get lost in translation: (like in a classroom setting i would honestly know kung di naintindihan)
- Hindi lahat nakakapagsabi kung naiintindihan nila yung material right there and then during the lecture itself
- Communication: mostly email,
- madaming email
- madaming discussion forum
- Face to face i feel yung communication line parang mas mabilis nasasabi natatanong agad kung meron di naiintindihan
- Asynchronous or synchronous yung line of communication- email and forums
- Recorded evaluation
- Missing yung actual na interaction with the patient
- Naretain namin yung other outputs
- yung actual interaction with the patientplanning magfa facilitate ng actual na eval and intervention yon mejo nawala
- Additional preparation before the exam

- Check the environment (halimbawa yung kapag written exam na revalida pag panel presentation we had to check yung environment kung meron bang kodigo)
- Moodle
- Trainings for Blackboard
- I dont think everything that was thought before was really made me very prepared
- Hard (It was hard even yung first sem na full blast ng online kase ano all of those are subjects that were previously thought face to face)
- Planning, the preparation of the materials whether I had to convert something para maging synchronous Asynchronous man siya na activity yon.
- overworked
- More work (I was doing more than the work that I would've done had it been face to face so tung transition na yan was really stressful)
- questioning whether the activities i have prepared or my assessments were they really hitting the course outcomes
- Have feedback based on the results of the eval,
- Makikita mo naman kung nahit mo naman yung course outcomes
- Time and training
- Training for blackboard -if we were given enough time to really get to know, familiarize dun sa LMS
- Prepare yung material
- didn't had enough time to prepare yung mga materials
- First transition there was resistance

- Reklamo na not enough time given for the outputs kase yung mga outputs before na kailangan niyo gawin or demonstrate in class now it has to be recorded
- additional work also for them (the students)
- Gauge how much what is necessary, (ano yung necessary na outputs tapos gaano katagal ibibigay namin for a certain output.)
- It will take time before you get used to that kind of modality
- They (students) were never given a time to process
- no orientation regarding the LMS
- Things are recorded so they can playback
- Not much difference in terms of skills
- Lahat naman ng ginagawa on a face-to-face nagagawa pa rin naman siya when we are doing ano online intervention
- Hitting the course outcomes
- Feedback from students
- Outcome measure
- It is effective
- Training
- Orientation-setting expectations
- Easing them with the transition
- Concerns in motivation; Self Directed Learning
- We're not there to really monitor whether they're listening or not
- students who expressed concerns sa motivation.
- Self-directed learning

Initial Codes of P4

- Articulation
- Voice Disorders
- Dysphagia
- Internship
- adjustments to accommodate the changes from face to face to online
- Ask the students to access materials that were recorded
- Recorded Lectures
- difficult internet connection
- problems with my internet connection
- We had to adjust
- Instruct our patients to access the online meeting
- Provide webinars or seminars for some of the activities
- The exams were transformed into an online modality
- specific techniques or assessment procedures that the students were expected to do ..had to change into online modality or
- Assessment (We had to ask them to record themselves and perform the techniques or the assessment procedures on their family members .instead to the teachers or the instructors of the course)
- view the videos that they submitted
- had difficulties communicating with students who had poor internet connection
- some of the activities were not applicable to other students with different type of learning styles
- Difficult to adjust

- Some of the students had difficulties learning through the online method
- Provided very detailed guidelines written in verbal guidelines for these students
- Had several meetings
- underwent training
- faculty members shared experiences with online modalities
- faculty members researched
- did some readings on different studies regarding online education,
- Online training
- We had training on test construction
- We also discuss the different best practices for each of the courses done during the semester or the year and it helped us adjust.
- Providing formative activities
- providing feedback for students
- providing a more specific rubric for each of the activity provided and then discussing it to the students helped in facilitating those activities
- Concerns at home also affected the way we had to adjust to this life
- poor internet connection in specific areas so that contributed greatly to the difficulties
- accommodate
- We had to describe in very detailed manner on how to how would the students gain their experience on how to touch patients or how to provide hands on experience given that we're in a virtual modality
- Outcomes didn't really change that much during from face to face to online learning

- able to achieve those learning outcomes
- Lectures were or the topics given were the same
- provide the similar experience for practical examinations or writing paper, writing evaluation reports, writing activity plans or writing therapy plans so we tried to provide a similar experience with the face-to-face methods
- Online room(For the practical examination so we had just like in face-to-face sessions we had an online room where it was just the instructor and the student, and then the student will perform)
- Rubric for online practical exams
- observe different videos of patients and create evaluation reports
- provide comments and also grade them
- difference would be mostly be being in front of the students and also giving them 1 on 1 feedback
- some students were hesitant in asking questions during online classes
- feedback given to students are individualized
- students would email questions
- extra effort to share what their classmate asked and then how we answered.
- The discussion needs to be facilitated in the way that we have to ask each and everyone of the students
- difficult to adjust from one method to another completely
- Several meetings
- several trainings
- time consuming
- We were able to adjust

- Manage the extra time that we had to provide in making the materials
- for the online practice you had to record yourself right after you finish your PowerPoint and upload that presentation.
- difficult to delineate when are you working for your work and also time for your family and also responsibilities at home
- additional time to adjust to online modalities
- overlaps with responsibilities at home
- Appropriate for some subjects that do not require physical manipulation
- Some therapy techniques also provide a an instruction where we use physical moves so i think some of the courses like that are better with face to face sessions
- we have to teach students to physically manipulate our patients or how to manage them hands on I think would need additional parameters on training siguro for our students for us to ensure that they will be ready
- adjust on providing education for our students
- Provide quality education for our students
- adjustments that we can't do because of physical social distancing or the pandemic.
- Providing lectures
- adjustments in assessing the students
- adjustment in handling sessions or intern sessions that are conducted online
- DE provides opportunities for the students to perform the SLP skills needed given that they are learning online
- More training

- More formal training and formal education
- We're able to adjust to it
- target our learning outcomes and program outcomes
- Good experience

Initial Codes of P5

- Fluency
- Audiology
- Diagnostics
- Identifying that we have would need to be translated into online
- All the students would be informed of how things will be running
- Migrate those lectures into the online format either synchronously or asynchronously
- Meet the students on time
- run the lecture live
- we would make recordings for them to access at a given time
- We already have a system (LMS) in place that we just had to utilize
- Support of the faculties is very important
- different levels of our ease of use of technology
- share each other's best practice and implement it in the different courses
- maximize the materials online that our department has and use it
- Concerned on capacities of our students
- Concerned courses: laboratory sessions

- Laboratory sessions using simulations, using actual materials, sometimes, even actual patients
- A population of our student body that would need more time for them to adjust to the new way of learning
- Ensure that learning isn't shortchange or sacrifice
- ensure the security of our exams
- ensure that there are no avenues for certain people to not be completely honest or diligent; honest with completing their requirements
- maximize the online resources available
- experience the same hands-on learning that we are providing in the lab sessions
- using zoom or google meet or any other platforms for video conferencing
- Implementing more secure measures in the conduct of the exams
- Created a mandatory setup that would enable the facilitators of the exam to see the environment of the student while taking the exam, to see what the students able to access during the conduct of the exam,
- do dual camera setups when they use their laptops and another device just for us to be able to see them while they take the exam
- translate some of the requirements, some of the written exam requirement into other outputs, projects, papers all the other outputs that would still be reflective of their learning without sacrificing the measurement
- technological knowledge
- a lot of hours spent on learning how to do things

- learning how create online materials.
- familiarizing with what the other options there are online that we can use
- appreciate the assistance of all my co-faculty members (because they were the ones that facilitated how we could learn faster, how we could learn together , and it ended up well, the anxiety)
- Ensure that the outcomes we have set for all of the courses that we are running are being met.
- assistance from people that I know are knowledgeable with things that we are going to be using, I'm going to be using for the first time.
- seek help from external people that are
- do my own research
- look it into references or resources online that would help me understand better how could use these different modes online
- Technological assistance (They're a phone call-away, email-away for concerns that I might have for all the platforms that we are using)
- Monitoring how we are all using the systems
- Assistance
- It could have been very helpful if there is an exposure to more online means of teaching
- more training in the use of all these modalities, all these platforms
- workshops
- LMS [Learning Management System].
- Without the learning platform, i think it's going to be a very disorganized

- Extended services of the learning platform
- LMS: You can make your exams there, you can post your lectures, provide forums, everything essential into ensuring that the discussion is still dynamic even if it's not face-to-face.
- synchronous sessions, we still encourage discussions, recitation, group work even if it's online
- Breakout rooms
- Discussion forums for asynchronous sessions, students can actually go back to the discussion at any point in time
- Ensuring that all the program outcomes are being met
- all the course outcomes are being met
- look at, requirements, the flow of the discussion, all of the aspects that we have put up and constantly comparing them to the outcomes that we have set for the course.
- able to achieve all those outcomes that we have set, even if the mode of delivery was very different,
- learning experience also for us to broaden our perspective
- Expectations and the outcomes that we have for the face-to-face , courses, we were able to replicate it in the online mode of teaching
- Distance education for me is you know being conducting education activities in a nonphysical manner, in an online manner
- it is not as different

- It's a new way of being able to teach these concepts and teach these skills without the need for physical interaction, while ensuring that, your objectives are all being met.

Initial Codes of P6

- Language development
- Fluency
- Language conditions
- Convince the entire team that you know, we are equipped for the transition
- Convincing the students and their family that it would actually work
- Team effort
- The content won't really change,
- preparing the outputs
- Workload increased
- ensuring that each and individual student is learning
- Preparing the materials eats up a lot of time
- students really understood the main ideas of the subject
- individual work
- several formative activities
- formative activities, and it's scaffolded
- more consultation periods during the class
- synchronous discussion

- online forum where people can post questions and thoughts anonymously
- Google form wherein people will write in their questions in that form
- Reaching out to 42 students was very hard,
- group didactic
- Summative assessment was very different
- Weekly quizzes.
- More case analysis and application questions during the output
- Apply the topics
- Give feedback individually
- Group activities were scaled down into individual output
- More formative activities
- CHED, the government regulation body
- go back to the program outcomes and the year level outcomes
- program evaluation
- a lot of support from the department
- support system
- I have to lead a department
- make them believe that this is achievable
- do SWOT [*strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats*] analysis
- provide feedback on what should be done
- planned as a department
- final outcomes were made

- rely on the program outcome
- paradigm shift on your teaching process
- Delivering the same content, but thinking out of the box
- More student-directed
- student-oriented
- The framework was already how do you learn and how are you going to learn this material and with all the constraints that are happening and without changing the outcomes and how the program was designed.
- Technology
- surprised that a lot of universities (in the Philippines)do not have LMS
- LMS [Learning Management System)
- Technical support from the ICT (Information and Communications Technology

APPENDIX D

Transcripts of the Interviews

1 P1'S Transcript

2
3 P1:um same curriculum I was able to facilitate Voice disorder both f2f and online, motor
4 speech condition, as well as research 1 & 2.

5 P1: This was back when the pandemic started march 2020 my initial reaction was I was
6 a bit although I already I expected it because of the pandemic emerging infectious
7 disease covid 19, I still found it initially surprising the amount of work I have to do
8 especially.at beginning when we were more focus on recording or preparing
9 prerecorded lectures instead of facilitating the sessions synchronously just like what we
10 do, in terms of amount of work i was quite surprise at the beginning also felt some
11 extent more comfortable or relaxed in the setting in the work from home setting since it
12 reduce or minimizes the risk of contracting the infection

13 P1: ok first with the surprising what was surprising for me was i thought that workload,
14 perhaps in terms of expectation i initially expected fewer tasks if it was converted online
15 but in the beginning there really more tasks, on top of preparing the presentation the
16 lecture handout and the activities. I also had to prerecord the lecture in advance that's
17 an extra work, on top of that we were asked to submit numerous documents at the
18 beginning just to prove we are really providing DE to our students. I remember before
19 we were asked to submit weekly reports, detailed reports on our u activities and
20 student assessment so that was really surprising part perhaps in terms of the
21 expectations there was a mismatched with the expectations I became more comfortable
22 as the semester went by and I was also able to adjust with the WFH setting I like the
23 comfort of working from home , not commuting from work, not waking up early just to
24 commute to work and spending more time with my family and more time for me was
25 well to relax and relax and enjoy the free time after I complete my task for the day.

26 P1: In terms of the process well for the lecture presentation were more or less the
27 same i just had to adjust the class activities, the activities we do during the session that
28 can be done using online video conference platform like Google meet or zoom um so
29 for the lecture part no major changes for the activities slight adjustments and then for
30 the student assessments, for example the examination, written examinations, practical
31 examinations, group projects and individual outputs so that's were where I really made
32 um adjustments or changes response to DE specifically for example for practical
33 examinations we were used to having move types practical examination in clinical
34 courses for example for voice disorders but we had to adjust the task to make it more
35 feasible in the online setting we tried various thing such as asking the student to
36 prepare video record themselves or facilitate the practical examination synchronously
37 using online video conference platform, so um the transformation was really more on
38 the mode of administration but in terms of the outcome expected the course learning
39 outcomes as well as the program outcomes still stayed the same.

40 P1: Yes, there were differences, for example during F2F classes i relied more aside
41 from using PPT, I relied more on the white board to draw diagram flowcharts to provide
42 examples, provide actual demonstration to students that involve physical contact and
43 during F2F we tend to use worksheet to prepare worksheet for students to accomplish
44 so we had to print the worksheet in advance and asked them to accomplish the
45 worksheet so with the online or DE all of that transformed into electronics for example
46 the worksheet had to be accomplished electronically instead of using the whiteboard

47 actual whiteboard um we had to resort to the annotate function in zoom for example
48 and um to compensate for the lack of direct demonstration we had to prepare video
49 demonstrations in advance facilitate by faculty members as well as provide
50 supplementary videos for students um either from freely accessible from YouTube or
51 other websites that the student can access.

52 P1: What was challenging was finding creative or innovative ways to assess the same
53 skills online we know that esp. clinical skills are needed to be demonstrated by
54 students. It was kinda challenging to find ways on how to actually assess the skills even
55 if we were just conducting it online. It was also challenging to consider. I think we had
56 to consider more factors in online assessment such as the workload of the student, the
57 bandwidth requirement for the test for example, the platform where the student for
58 example will upload the output esp. if there are video output as well as the deadline esp.
59 In the beginning of the pandemic the students also had to adjust with the sudden
60 change of the mode of delivery of education, also had to provide accommodations to
61 them for example by extending the due date of output. So those were the challenging
62 things I encountered for student assessment.

63 P1: So, we primarily communicated with our students using our institutional email
64 address. Primarily used that also used the learning management system specifically
65 Blackboard to provide quantitative feedback specifying the scores as well as feedback
66 comments, qualitative in nature. Um for some student especially those who need or
67 require remediation we try to set appointments thru synchronous video online video
68 calls discussion so that's another mode of communication, rarely in specific instances
69 we also use short messaging application such as viber in specific occasions for
70 example where interns are providing or facilitating webinars to patient we need to
71 provide immediate feedback to them for example during the webinar we had to use
72 viber as well to communicate.

73 P1: I can say that I was fairly confident with my background and skills in using these
74 applications because even before the pandemic we were already using or trying to
75 maximize the for example the LMS for posting lecture materials and everything and i
76 was also able to i can use video conferencing various video conferencing applications
77 without any problems. And I'm also used to using ppt presentations to prepare my
78 lecture. Um one thing I'm not confident about video editing. I don't really have the skill to
79 prepare or to perform complex video task. As well as for example using photo shop for
80 example i can only use ppt. Or canvas for preparing simple posters but i cannot use
81 adobe photoshop to prepare more complex materials for teaching.

82 P1: um for the one i specifically mentioned i was not able to receive any training on that
83 I did not also had the initiative to study it more since I did not feel the need to actually
84 specialize on it but i think at the start of the pandemic also and even before the
85 pandemic the center for innovative communication and technology(CITC) of our
86 institution were providing regular webinars for teaching online teaching for example
87 mentimeter kahoot to make the sessions more interactive but personally i wasn't really
88 able to use them or maximize them. I don't know i still felt more comfortable facilitating
89 the activities that i used to do in face to face online for example asking raising

90 questions during lecture, waiting students to respond either thru chat or by opening their
91 cameras and then using what i mentioned earlier using the white board, annotate
92 function zoom to exemplify further the concept and um what else and that's it.

93 P1: Well, I think the since institution is eyeing for accreditation locally and regionally as
94 well as internationally i think that's a requirement for accreditation to use learning
95 management system so even before the pandemic the institution was already requiring
96 us to use these LMS i think primarily for quality academic assessment as well and for
97 accreditation purposes.

98 P1-Majority of the classes were delivered traditionally face to face discussion, pen and
99 paper examination but in some instance we were already using online exam for
100 example um in some instances as well as using Google forms for example to facilitate
101 peer evaluation to the students. So majority were delivered traditionally but in some
102 instances we were already using um online mode and it was easier as well to deliver
103 some aspects of the course online since were already using LMS as mentioned earlier.

104 P1: So in terms of outcome we still want to achieve the course and program outcomes
105 that we set for our student regardless of the mode of delivery for online I think the the
106 thing primarily consider is ensuring that the student receive the quality education that
107 they deserve despite um having uh despite doing this uh facilitating everything online
108 aside from that we still have to ensure that the program outcomes year level outcomes
109 are being achieved um for uh just in case for example that we get uh audited either by
110 the institution, or by CHED or by the accrediting bodies like PASP.

111 P1: um of course this will come from a biased perspective since i am the faculty
112 member facilitating these courses also looking at the students' performance as well as
113 the student feedback provided during the faculty evaluation at the end of the semester I
114 can say that um in terms of effectiveness of online education is similar to the ones that
115 we were achieving face to face.

116 P1: Alright um so for example in terms of the rate of the students who successfully pass
117 the course and the attrition rate of the students for example. The rate did not drastically
118 change I cannot say for sure but I think the attrition rate were even lower when we
119 transformed to distance education. Um I can't say the actual grades of the students but
120 in terms of their performance um as their teacher um I am still satisfied with their
121 performance even if we conducted everything online and um aside from that as I
122 mentioned earlier in terms of the faculty evaluation of the students the feedback they
123 provide the comment were mostly positive and did not center too much in the mode of
124 education. They actually provided more um positive comment in terms of the quality of
125 feedback being provided the accommodation being provided to them during online
126 education. And um things ayan those are the similarities that i observed.

127 P1: personally, I'm still confident that we were able to achieve the program outcomes of
128 our students even if it was conducted online.um And personally I do not think the
129 benefits facilitating face to face classes actually outweighs the risk for contracting covid

130 19 infection during this pandemic i still prefer as of now online DE because we can still
131 achieve the same outcomes without worrying the risk if being infected with covid 19.
132 P1: well for me distance education is delivering um the course curriculum and
133 facilitating teaching and learning strategies online or remotely while still achieving the
134 set course year level and program outcomes
135 P1: in terms of the difference the only difference that I'm seeing we don't get to interact
136 directly or face to face with the students but in terms of actual interaction needed to
137 facilitate the learning outcome still the same. I think that's the only difference you cannot
138 see them face to face and facilitate the activity face to face and everything for me stays
139 the same
140 P1 well um to some extent there still similar but a few adjustments for online for DE
141 P1: these are the one i discussed earlier for example making the practical exam instead
142 of move type practical exam we had to facilitate them either thru synchronous video call
143 or having them upload videos so more of the accommodation or changes needed since
144 we can't do it face to face
145 P1: Yes. I had to learn how to navigate and be proficient in using the LMS, other
146 learning apps (e.g., Google forms, Kahoot), and videoconferencing apps (e.g., Zoom
147 breakout rooms) to ensure effective teaching and learning among students.

1 P2'S Transcript

2 P2: So for...okay.....Because so far this is like the third..... so the first semester that
3 we had to do distance education was when at the onset of the pandemic so that was
4 2nd semester of 2019-2020 at the time we had to shift the intervention and clinical
5 reasoning practice this is part of the old curriculum. We also had to shift dysphagia
6 and..... I think those are the only courses that....and I think I was also part of ALCC
7 that team, at the time..... so yeah those are the courses that I handled and then in the
8 first semester of 2020-2021 I handled anatomy, neuro anatomy and then counseling
9 uhmmm teaching and learning.... and I think that's it. And then in the second semester
10 again we had to run ALCC again..... yeah ALCC as part of the laboratory team
11 uhmmm..... Aural hab.....ay hindi, yung intro to audio.....and then intro to audio,
12 Diags introduction to diagnostics and CRP1 these are already part of the new
13 curriculum and then..... ano pato.....

14
15 P2: Andami nga eh. ano paba yung subject na hawak ko last year, I forgot na.... yeah
16 and then I had to do mid-year term kase again so I had to do Intervention and CRP1 too
17 during the mid-year term. And then I am also preparing for all the prepared the materials
18 for the uhmmm..... first semester which is starting next week supposedly uhmmm....
19 that's gonna be again uhmmm... Diags, CRP1 (Clinical Reasoning) of the new
20 curriculum and I am also handling counseling again and now I am also handling
21 homeroom for the first time so that's part of the new curriculum and also I almost forgot I
22 had pala ano AHR Aural Hab also Lab In the first semester so from 2020-2021 all of the
23 subjects that I mentioned are all part of the new curriculum that we are handling

24 P2: Okay my first I think Im not too concern, I wasn't too concern about the courses
25 that were running as lectures because prior to the start of the shift to full online we were
26 already utilizing zoom and some of the.....we already had moodle at that time that was
27 the one that we were uhmmmm..... constantly utilizing to share the lectures and also to
28 get the submissions of the students which I felt at that time really helped a lot when it
29 came to the transition because It wasn't something that was sent uhmmm.... that was
30 totally foreign for all of us but my main concern was when we had to shift Diags and
31 CRP1 to online because the course itself requires the student to handle patients directly
32 so the questions there was that if we are going to have to ask the patients to come in
33 before psychically in the school what's gonna happen now so we knew that we had to
34 shift to teleteraphy and the students were not trained in teleteraphy at the time so
35 uhmm.... we fortunately the..... when the courses structured in such a way that the
36 students are supposed to do multiple sessions with the same patients so usually they
37 do 4 therapy sessions and then so 2 sessions first and then they do a case
38 management and then 2 other sessions and then the final case management. So
39 because there were several sessions that were spread out uhmm.... what happened
40 was that if I had to make do or remove first some of the sessions the initial sessions,

41 just so I can introduce teletherapy get them comfortable with the idea that they are
42 going to be providing the services online, I was able to do so had to schedule uhmm.... I
43 had to wait also for the guidelines coming from PASP and you know as part the
44 uhmm..... what do you call this? I think the technical panel like LaSalle was also part of
45 the technical panel that contributed to the particular document. It really helped that
46 some of the faculty members knowledgeable about teletherapy, so that helped me a lot
47 with regards to structuring the program and getting them prepared for teletherapy
48 provision because at the time when we had to break the news to schools that these is
49 whats gonna happen. Of course, there....my main concern was really the capacity of
50 students to cope with the sudden change because it wasn't something that we were all
51 ready to do, so uhmm.... but..... upon evaluation at the end of the scores they said that
52 the introductory courses really helped and it was a way to guide them slowly into what
53 they are supposed to do so when the time came, I think they did uhmmm.... one
54 technical session with the patient and then two actual teletherapy sessions with the
55 patients. They were able to do so uhmmm.... confidently and they were able to execute
56 with the tasks well uhmmm.... yon, so that was the problem for the students who had
57 good internet connection, my other concern was that, what about the students who did
58 not have stable internet connection because we had some students before who were
59 not ready for online service delivery at home so because they used to be staying at the
60 dorm, and the dorms had stable internet connection once they got home they have to
61 rely on data and that was a main problem so we had to make alternative plans for them,
62 how do we ensure that we still get to meet the outcomes that we have set for the
63 course with uhmm... limited interaction with actual patients their bandwidth could not
64 sustain the minimum requirement for teletherapy. so....there.

65 P2: I think for the other courses even if uhmmm.... of course, uhmmmm..... Internet is
66 still going to be a concern for some but because some of the students say that if we
67 record the session as long as they can have the time or have the funds to have the load
68 to download them quickly for, example in the middle of the night, they can still go
69 through the courses in the morning so its not that big of an issue. My other concern
70 would be for the other course like for Dysphagia since a lot of uhmm.... the evaluation
71 that we do there involves palpation like touching a patient's body and then try to feel try
72 to determine if the swallow is good or for example if we have to provide intervention that
73 involves touching the face, how much pressure is needed to provide the sensation that
74 the patient needs so that's the other concern that I have, so.... I think those are some of
75 the things that I sacrificed when we had to shift to online, fortunately when Dysphagia
76 ran for the first, because uhmm.... in the old curriculum Dysphagia had a laboratory
77 component. And that happened 2019-2020 so since it was until the halfway point when
78 Dysphagia started to be shifted online for that particular curriculum, we were able to do
79 all the palpation all the physical therapy techniques at the beginning of the course and
80 then it was a sacrificed that much. In the second curriculum in the new curriculum

81 dysphagia doesn't have a lab component anymore so ultimately even if we don't get to
82 do it physically for uhmm... with the students or with a specific patient since theres no
83 laboratory component it's not..... it does not..... ano ba parang..... it doesn't loss any
84 of the outcomes that were set and its not required by ched anymore, it's just an
85 alternative course that was introduce or maintained by LaSalle because we knew that it
86 was...that they should have knowledge about this particular field of practice but they
87 can continue to develop this skill once they go into internship or once they go into
88 practice at least we covered the basics during these particular course.

89 P2: Sige. I think for.... sige let's start with the lectures first. For the lecture courses, if it's
90 a lecture per sake, it wasn't to much of an issue.....ay nde wait.....wait sige....let's do
91 with the ano na lang uhmmm....2nd year to...parang from introductory courses clinical
92 until internship sige yun nalang. So introductory, anatomy, neuro anatomy like all the
93 basic courses we didn't have too much of an issue fortunately because we had
94 materials on hand already like pictures and the models so its just a matter of putting the
95 materials on the screen and then utilizing it in terms of how they would actually do it in
96 the classroom. So It wasn't that much of a stretch. I think the main problem for us there
97 was that we had to adjust the method of evaluation of the students because since the
98 introductory courses their very basic, the material and the information is something
99 readily available online the main concern is the integrity of how the students would be
100 able to respond to the quizzes and the exams. Because the answers are readily
101 available on the internet, so the main adjustment there was that we did multiple
102 cameras, so one camera for viewing the exams and another to view the student as they
103 were actually completing the exams. So we utilize to meet in zoom for that so that's the
104 major adjustment I think but at everything else, its just translating everything and
105 delivering online. Once we started going into the clinical courses does are ALCC, the
106 main concern that I uhmm.... we did especially in the last year was that whenever we
107 have to teach something uhmm..... in terms of lecture we also have to provide another
108 topic whichh covers "how do you adjust if you are going to do it online?" Because
109 evaluation processes or terepuding processes were all previously uhmm....thought like
110 if you are doing it face to face so.... since sometimes there are components like for
111 example extra materials that the patient has to prepare at home or certain instructions
112 that the family members need to have before we actually do the therapy, those are
113 some of the components that we needed to include to ensure that the students would
114 be successful in translating the knowledge that they get from the scores not just for face
115 to face but also for online service delivery. And then..... yeah I think that's it, one of the
116 things that we had a hard time last year was that I think it we were still in the process of
117 transition so ideally for some of those courses they should've started doing actual
118 evaluation on certain patients, but we weren't able to do that as of yet last year. So
119 hopefully that's something that we can continue to do now that were back. Well, were
120 back with online and we had more time to... you know to evaluate and to see what was

121 lacking last year....ok.....and then for the other courses involving the other roles for
122 example like counseling and also for uhmmm.....ano pa ba... counseling and
123 teaching and learning. Teaching and learning were able to convert it online completely
124 uhmm....it can actually....we did it almost asynchronously the whole thing was done
125 almost asynchronously the same with counseling because a lot of the topic reports of
126 the students were done asynchronously, however the only change that we did for
127 counseling last year was that instead of the students actually doing counseling services
128 for their patients before that was the ultimate uhmmmm.....parang performance task of
129 the students uhmmmm.... the patient that they saw during diags, what we did was that
130 they did peer to peer counseling so they would meet with a specific classmate 3 times
131 throughout the whole semester to do counseling sessions with them. One you will be
132 the counselor another one you will be the counseling. I felt that at the time it was
133 something that we needed to do, because we were already feeling the burnout of the
134 pandemic, of online learning, not being able to connect with others. So by having those
135 structured meetings the feedback of the students was that they really felt or they really
136 appreciated the fact that they were able to exercise what they learned but at the same
137 time also decompressed some of the feelings that they had towards someone who was
138 familiar with them all throughout the session. So it's something that I retained in the
139 course until now, even if they can still do the feedback or the counseling sessions for
140 their patient we still maintained the three sessions together with their classmates or with
141 their counseling circle group members so that they have someone to connect to
142 because I think that's something that we needed to maintain during online because for
143 me I felt like we were all disconnected to because I keep comparing it to how we are
144 doing it during face to face so I think that's something we want to do now, we want to
145 make sure that even if were all online we want to feel connected and also for these
146 coming semester we want to.....uhmm even if the materials are done asynchronously or
147 presented asynchronously we want to do like a showcase or a premiere of some of the
148 outputs of the students so that they can view it like an expo or something like that so
149 they can view the materials that the students did and we can learn..... they can all learn
150 from each other like what this person did what other person did and see their
151 perspectives of their other peers and other classmates and then lastly for the pre
152 internship courses like diags and intervention. For diags and intervention the main
153 challenge was that we had to incorporate teletherapy and the.... as a topic so we
154 always had to teach things two times for example this is how you are going to prepare
155 for an evaluation if it was face to face and this is how you can prepare for an evaluation
156 if you're going to do it online, because even if we knew that the students are first going
157 to go online in the first few months of the internship, we knew that there was a
158 possibility that they would do face to face at the end of the internship or once they
159 practiced, and based..... the feedback coming from the previous set of graduates was
160 that they always had this apprehension that since they were all trained online

161 throughout their whole internship plot, that they wouldn't do well once they had to do
162 face to face therapy, so we had to give them the face to face background and the online
163 background so that they will be knowledgeable at the very least and find confidence in
164 doing it because they knew there were something that they could go back to just in case
165 they decide to do online practice or they decide to do face to face practice, they always
166 have the material and the information coming from the courses to back them up. So
167 those are the main challenges that we did. Fortunately in the second run of the courses
168 we also were able to find patients who were more stable in terms of internet and also in
169 terms of how to utilize the technology that they have on hand we didn't have that many
170 problems already. I think it was because compared to 2020 when we did it 2021 we had
171 the whole year like the whole world had time to adjust to doing things online so since
172 they started learning it from other people once we had to introduce it it wasn't to much
173 of a stretch anymore, and like we did it talaga the first time talagang we had to teach.....
174 we had to do a technical meeting like we had to do each group had to meet one patient
175 for one hour just to teach the parent how to open zoom, this is the mic, this is the
176 camera, this is the...., this is how you do it. So they had to guide them all throughout,
177 but this year we didn't have to do it anymore because you know...once we tell the
178 parent "oh ma'am this is the zoom link to the class then were just going to meet you
179 there." as long as you meet them there, you send them the link they already know how
180 to get there, so its just a short introduction to them unlike before that it really takes a lot
181 of time. I think there were only one a couple of students who needed that much
182 assistance but other than that I think for the most part everyone is on board with online
183 even the patients so it's not just the students

184 P2: I think uhhh... because I think the...at the time when we had to shift... the initial
185 shift ... we had to do the initial shift... for me as a person I always been on the side that
186 ok if there's something that needs to be done ok let's do it. and we knew that it was
187 something that was bound to happen, I think as early as February, I think March yeah
188 that was... the idea was already being Introduce to me uhhh.... starting February
189 until...yeah we had to execute it like March 16 so at that time I think.... since I was
190 given enough time to wrap my head around the Idea of what needs to be done, I was
191 given enough time to plan ahead and given enough time to be given feedback and then
192 revised some of the plans, I think, I felt like I dealt with it pretty well at the time because
193 I think there was just an ulterior goal there was at the end of the day I think my goal
194 was only to ensure that we finish the semester, we have to finish the semester,
195 everyone has to finish the semester so since I had that goal I think I was just working
196 and working through that and I wasn't to frustrated because I think we had..... what
197 helped was that I had plan A,B,C,D ahead of time so I knew If something's not gonna
198 work I had a backup plan, so if something didn't work it didn't get me down too much, it
199 didn't add to my anxieties because I knew there was something else that I could do. So
200 that really helped coping with all of the challenges that happened during that particular

201 semester but I did not realize how tired I was until we ended haha until the semester
202 ended its like the goal was just to finish... the goal was to finish the semester, and when
203 the semester finished like oh my God I could not believe that we did it and that looking
204 back I could not understand like how we are able to do it but we did, so I think it was like
205 blind faith that ok we just need to work together and with...let's ride together, let's shirt
206 together, let's finish this we can do this guys ganon parang ganon lang siya tapos nung
207 tapos na parang naiisip mo ahh pagod na pala ako parang ganon... ganon siya so nag
208 decompress talaga ako during that particular period. And then we have to it all over
209 again for one whole year and then there were some adjustments again but I think we
210 were more ready because of the things that we learn when we ran it the first time. The
211 next time that I was super stress again was when we did intervention during the mid-
212 year term , I think for distance learning....ano ba....it's hard enough to do a summer
213 class because there's less time to process things but I think when you're doing it online
214 and we're doing it from a distance perspective it's much harder because there's...ano
215 ba...I think some of the things that you wanted to clarify you needed answers right away
216 okay , so the problem was that I needed to....the faculty needed to response to the
217 concerns of the students as quickly as possible because we are going to meet them the
218 next day, and then the next day, and then the next day....so in short if they had
219 concerns with their paper, with their patients, with their reports,with their therapy
220 material we had to provide feedback as soon as possible, and I think that really put a lot
221 of pressure to the faculty members but we again as goal oriented people we knew we
222 are gonna be done by a certain date so at the beginning of the course, before we
223 started I already.... part of the orientation with the students was that let's just put our all,
224 let's just work together towards completing everything for the whole like 18 days that we
225 had to work together, and as soon as the 18 days are up, you know, take the time to
226 relax and you know decompress it, don't.... don't talk to each other awhile, don't talk
227 shap anymore because you need life's outside those 18 days, so I think that was tough,
228 that was really tough I wouldn't recommend that it be done ever again. Not because of
229 how it was ran I think if it was ran not in 18 consecutive days it would've work but since
230 it was.... we had to meet the deadline of the start of internship eh, that was the ultimate
231 objective we has no choice but in terms If learning in terms of focusing on what you
232 needed to learn it really helped. Not just the students but even me because since it was
233 everything that was what we were just doing day in and and day out we were able to
234 focus so much on the patients, what we needed to do for the patients, what the students
235 needed to learn to be able to meet the needs of the patients, that really helped a lot but
236 if you need...I think... yeah that for if uhmm....distance education is not ok if you put it
237 if there's not enough time, If there's not enough time to do everything you're supposed
238 to do, so a big component I did not realize that for distance education time is such a
239 huge component. I think if it was face to face, like again looking back if that course we
240 have to do it 18 days ng tuloy tuloy and then it was face to face. I think it wouldn't be

241 that hard versus if it was distance education because If you were face to face you're all
242 together In one whole room and the feedback can be given right there, right then and
243 there but for online it's always gonna be via email, via written communication and that
244 takes a lot of turnaround time so that added a lot to the workload and the how tired
245 everyone was by the end of.... I wouldn't say frustrating because we knew what we are
246 going to get into but yeah it added a lot to the workload....how..how ...so..yeah it was
247 just the workload it was just a lot of work versus if was that face to face

248 P2: what helped us get ready..... I think what helped us get ready really uhmm... Kxx
249 was really instrumental like our program director was really instrumental towards having
250 the right mindset towards distance education, for us it was.....because from the very
251 beginning... it was very clear to us that it was just going to be a shift in the method of
252 delivery but there was never going to be a change in the content of the... and the
253 outcomes needs to be met. So, because that was very clear to us from the very
254 beginning we knew and we have confidence that what we were going to do worked or is
255 gonna work. Other things that helped at the time at the beginning of the pandemic there
256 were a lot of free seminars, webinars and I took a lot of those for teletherapy I think I did
257 that 8 hour crash course on teleteraphy. From teleteraphy practitioners from the US so
258 that gave us confidence since these are people who've been doing...are doing it as part
259 of their work for the past how many years already and it works for them, it gave us
260 confidence that this is also going to work for us. Another thing is that it helped that I took
261 also some courses on online service delivery like how to modify like some of the
262 activities or like the....having some of the background just to utilize moodle like how to
263 maximize moodle, how to maximize your LMS helps a lot....ano pa ba.....Oh and I think
264 for me....the.....my background also from my masters...from....even if its help
265 profession education it's not distance education but I think at the end of the day even
266 if...since its still education at the core like a lot of the principles its really...you know that
267 as long as what you're doing is routed on you know your philosophies, your theories
268 these are ideals you know that your only modifying your teaching and learning activities
269 for example then and maximizing the materials that are readily available with you, you
270 know that you're in the right path or you're in the right course. Another thing that really
271 helped....because I think with our program director also encourage us to think about
272 what are the problems that might happen and since we were going at it with that
273 perspective that "okay what could go wrong?" It helped us to plan....make different
274 plans okay for example what if the student doesn't have internet or what if the student
275 doesn't have a patient, what if this student doesn't have a partner or what if they loss
276 this partner what are you going to do? So having those hypothetical scenarios in our
277 head helped us get ready for.... or to full proof the plan to ensure it will still push
278 through. For exhaustion what really helped at the time...I think every course that I did
279 when we did online...one of the things that I really miss or like part of the support
280 system that I felt was really lacking when we did online was that we didn't have....we

281 weren't physically together and we didn't have that chit chat during lunch time
282 during...while we're waiting for the next classes in the office and when...at the... during
283 classes the group chats really helped having the group chat with the faculty...other
284 faculty members because it's the time where you can talk about some of the things
285 relative to the course. Another thing that we did sometimes we just schedule meetings
286 like for example after class and then we just talk about what happened in class and it
287 helps you process the things that happened, and another thing...well aside from work...
288 you...discovering new and other hobbies that you might want to do once you're done
289 with work, you're offline already...uhmm really helped like watching Korean dramas
290 really helped me a lot since the start of the pandemic, I think I started watching...holy
291 week eh...oo.....that's the only time that I started cause I didn't wanna start because I
292 knew that it was gonna take up a lot of time before when I was doing face to face, but
293 since I had a lot of time now then that's when I started with this hobby of mine so yeah I
294 think that really helped tide me over the last year talaga really because it helped
295 transport me with other worlds aside from what we were doing like day in and day out
296 and....yeah making the most of your time also with your family because you get to
297 spend more time with them because before like looking back it's always going to be...I
298 think yeah now that we're in this pandemic and we see you know memories from
299 facebook and you think about how you were able to squeeze in everything and you
300 knew that you had... there was something that had to give and usually its time with
301 family so it's also making the most out of time with family whose really available there
302 with you at home...there

303 P2: I think in generally....okay how like how we run it parang ganon overall? I think im
304 generally happy with a how we did like what we've been doing. I would of course if
305 given a choice...I would still want to do face to face I think there's a lot... there's a
306 human component that needs to translate physically with other people, but then again
307 that's part of me as part of my extrovert personality I think. I think I need that, I always
308 need that. But I see also the benefits of DE....like for some of the components that...
309 like just recording your session. Like recording the lecture, simply recording the lecture.
310 Before during face to face it was something that we've been already...well starting to do
311 already but I think it wasn't readily accepted or I think...ano ba...common before there
312 was a lot of paranoia like why would you record your lecture like why would you record
313 the classroom parang ganon yung feedback before eh, pero now we've been recording
314 it for like the whole year already like now were so...everyone was so comfortable with
315 the camera already like before when we started we were all so cautious about the
316 camera. But we also see the benefits of having the lecture recorded because the
317 students who didn't understand, they can go back to certain parts lang and then clarify
318 kasi I really get questions like that and It's good to see that the students are making the
319 most out of the material that is given to them and not just you know parang...kasi
320 parang before andaling...andaling gawing excuse"ay hindi ko kasi naintindihan" parang

321 ganon kasi hindi siya recorded but now they don't have that excuse anymore. But I think
322 in general...yeah I'm happy with how we ran it because I think whenever we like for me
323 especially since I handled the pre internship courses like diags and intervention.
324 Whenever I see them working together with the patients I really do not see a lot of
325 difference whether it was done face to face or whether it was done online. Actually, a lot
326 of the components are more honed since we had to do it online. The planning , how the
327 students plan for the sessions is so much better now, compared when they were doing
328 it face to face because they now that since everything is recorded and everything is
329 gonna be you know...has to be prepared ahead of time for online because you couldn't
330 just you know get something from the cabinet of toys uhhh... they had to prepare and
331 they had think about what they needed to do. So that's really something thay I wouldn't
332 have.....I think I wouldn't have developed that skill so much if we were still doing face
333 to face, but I think...and also there capacity to communicate with the parent kasi they
334 have to coach the parent. So their communicating better, more like translating
335 information better to the parent... yeah those are the things that i've seen improve
336 during this period. And also I think communication was a written communication is
337 better but I think there are still a lot of components that distance education could not
338 provide for example...uhmmm yun nga.... while those...ano ba...aspects of
339 communication is improve, other like the software skills like watching out for your
340 posture, watching out for your...like small physical reactions for example facial
341 expressions those are somethings that I think we need to....that you can pick up better
342 if you were doing things face to face because the context that the environment
343 provides...the physical environment provides could not be replaced by the virtual
344 environment that you see because whenever we work together with the student, the
345 parent and the patient at home...uhmm....even if you do a wide like shut of the camera
346 andami paring nangyayari sa bahay that you don't know eh na parang ahh this is the
347 reason pala why this kid is acting up this way so it was a physical environment if we
348 were physically present there of course we would know and we could be able to
349 address them so unless the parent is very vocal about or we ask the right questions
350 about the concerns or the problems that are happening then we wouldn't really know, so
351 there are.....because there are some parents like who do teletherapy, they only see the
352 kid here and then the parent standing here. We never.... we had one session where we
353 never saw the moms face, we never saw the moms face, so we didn't know if she was
354 happy, she was upset or what because she wasn't comfortable about being on camera,
355 but she was responsive. So, we couldn't defer them just for that particular reason. So
356 yeah those are some of the things that.... I think prevents or like...but overall, I think
357 that again those are isolated cases but in general I'm happy because a lot of the things
358 that I expect them to do back in 2019 are the same things that we are doing now at
359 2021 so there's not much of a difference in our case.

360 P2: I think it's not fair to say DE would be better than face to face or something....I think
361 there are some positives for each side of the coin. What's good about the experience is
362 that since we did DE... we knew that ok DE gives this that face to face could not provide
363 or well hindi naman na provide but because or face to face.... di natin sobrang
364 naconjour yung face to face like yung nga yung planning...yung planning for the
365 sessions hindi siya astidius as when we were doing it face to face. Could we have
366 thought it that way during face to face? Possible! Pero I don't think yung gravity nung
367 situation would be as impactful. Kasi unfair den kasi to say to the student na "nde
368 kailangan prepared ka ahead of time kasi haharap ka sa patient, dapat kung ano yung
369 toys mo na prepared mo na ready mo na" hindi fair yun kasi alam nila na pwede naman
370 silang kumuha ng ibang toy if it doesn't work out eh, unlike sa tele na talagan " hindi
371 kailangan talagang anong prinepare mo yun na" kase wala kanang mapapagkuhanan.
372 So yun kasi yung reality nung DE eh nung tele. So I don't think matuturo siya as
373 effectively on face to face, like yun yung advantage ng DE. pero sa face-to-face
374 naman... I think yun nga ang kaya naman iprovide ng face to face is that yun nga mas
375 maging perceptive ka dun sa nangyayari sa environment mo kase
376 parang....your....yung confide kasi yun environment nang DE dun lang sa screen eh,
377 hindi katulad sa face to face na lahat ng nangyayari sa paligid mo like kahit yung air
378 con, kahit yung... alam mo yung temperature, yung light, ganoong mga bagay natatake
379 note mo siya so... hindi katulad sa distance education na hindi siya ganon ka...its not a
380 factor that you would consider becausee your not knowledgeable about it based dun sa
381 environment nung patient. So ang gagawin mo to know about it you have to ask, ok
382 lang ba yung ganyan, ok lang ba yung ganun pwede naman pero hindi realistic na
383 everytime tatanungin mo sila about it. So yon, yun yung mga components but I
384 think....ano ba....and also at the end of the day I think yung isang component ng DE,
385 like even if we do the live zoom lectures ganon iba parin yung makukuha mo yung
386 reaction ng student like paglive na lecture kasi you can modify your instruction better
387 since youknow if their still listening attending if they are responsive to the activities
388 versus if you're doing DE, kasi for DE as much as....well there's the chat box diba but
389 most of the time...alam mo yon....you try to engage the students as much as you can
390 but hindi siya...you don't know what's happening to them at home kasi we don't require
391 them to open their cameras. So those are some....even if we do breakout rooms na nga
392 eh diba, we do breakout rooms ganyan, and then there's some groups that are really
393 talkative like they talk a lot during the call or in the breakout room but there are some
394 who would just you know work quietly in their own google docs and you have to confirm
395 and validate what's happening to them and if it was a face to face class then it's gonna
396 be easier because you see the groups already working together. So those are the
397 things that I think uhmmm....you can try to simulate but it still at the end of the day it's
398 still going to be very different. So there are some component, and I think what's good
399 about seeing both ends like the DE and the face to face, you also see how different

400 kinds of learners respond to stimuli because surprisingly...before I forget pala...parang
401 there are some students na before nung face to face....they wouldn't talk... they
402 wouldn't share anything in the class like you don't see them raising their hands on
403 anything, but when we shifted to DE and as long as we use zoom...if we use google
404 meet its not gonna work but if we use zoom, since zoom had a direct message option
405 there are some students who would send questions to me via direct message. So, it
406 turns out these students who probably if we were In face to face hindi sila
407 magrerrespond naman...baliktad naman...sila yung di magrerrespond sa face to face
408 pero sa DE doon sila nagrerespond kasi alam nila hindi sila majudge ng classmates
409 nila for asking questions that they feel might be stupid ganon kasi direct message lang
410 siya saken. Tapos they can be anonymous like I tell the students "sige if you send me a
411 direct message I won't tell your names" so they na I really keep their confidence...na
412 meron kaming phone in question ganyan so sasagutin ko lang ganon so at least
413 nasagot yung tanong niya tas at the same time hindi siya napahiya ganon. So may ano
414 siya....parang I appreciate both end of the....parang walang ifafavor na isa
415 lang...parang ganon.

416
417 P2: for me distance education in the BSSLP courses is....its uhmm....ano ba....It's
418 something that we've been...I think something that will stay I mean even beyond the
419 current situation that were in because its...we see the benefits of the things that were
420 done in the past two years since march 20...wala pa pala tayong 2 years, mga a year
421 and a half na pala tayo....yon kasi I see that there are some...kasi it has its benefits, it
422 has its strengths in terms of how we structure the sessions, how we structure the
423 courses, how we make sure that everyone could be included and also how we prepare
424 for things that could and may happen. So I think those are things DE provided us with
425 the opportunity to look into those things and to be more inclusive also because one's
426 factor that DE has provided us is that we were able to reach students who are not within
427 the area of [REDACTED] like they're from different areas but also the same time provide
428 service to patients who are not within the area of the school because before all the
429 patients that we cater are just within from Dasmaringas Cavite area diba. inclusivity yun.
430 So yeah it provided us with a wider net for expansion and consideration of the needs of
431 others and I think yun nga as I mentioned... it does work for some students like some
432 students who might be too quiet or might be too shy when they are in the classroom
433 might do work really well while they're on DE and to a certain extent allows them also to
434 connect more personally with the faculty members at a more personal level because we
435 communicate regularly with them either through email or yun nga through direct
436 message on chat. So those are things that I think needs to be part of the curriculum all
437 throughout because it allows us to be more inclusive not just for the patients but also for
438 the students yon.

1 P3's Transcript

2
3 P3 Okey Aural Hab and then Senior sem 1 I think yun Lang yung both face-to-face
4 syaka online na parehong curriculum

5 P3 Syempre if i'll be honest yung initial reaction ko ano sya may resistance may dread
6 tapos naanticipate kona din na sobrang daming kailangan gawin kase prang yun nga
7 um yung change sa platform is one is we used to have moodle diba per nung nag
8 transition din naman ng purely online nagbago din yung LMS
9 so yon one ano yon one factor nagcontribute yun other than that anxiety over sa mga
10 posibleng madaming gawin (chuckle)

11 P3: I had to change Kailangan kong um palitan or mag isip ng accommodation kase
12 una ay sorry nakalimutan ko internship din pala kasama ba yun or hinde na.

13 P3 OK sorry so yun ano dun internships so una s classroom naman lahat ng parang we
14 just had to identify yung kailangan naming gawin for synchronous kase nung umpisa
15 nun transition wala naman kaming asynchronous that time kase biglaan siya nung
16 march. I think isang accommodation lang dun talaga is yung kailanvan namin identify
17 pano namin mababago yung outputs na usually required for face to face halimbawa
18 yung panel yung mga colloquiums ganun um practical exams yon and then yung sa
19 internship mejo different din siya in the sense na from scratch namin siya ginawa as in
20 maghanap ng platform na magagawa ng intern kahit papano pa rin yung nagagawa nila
21 sa face to face halimbawa lang we had to research yung sa zoom kung paano gamitin
22 yun then kailangan namin itrain sarili namin and yung intern din paano gamitin yung
23 zoom, materials for internship lastly yung identifying ng patient yung mga ganung bagay
24 tapos yun lang mostly modification ng outputs tapos training sa bagong gagamiting
25 platform yon and then yung succeeding for classroom mostly modifying yung mga the
26 lectures dun andun na yung mga recorded na lectures pag may grade ng outputs
27 halimbawa yung mga exams yon written exams to online na

28 P3: Was there a difference hrap na tanong yan (chuckle) wait give me a moment. I
29 think now wala siyang masyadong difference for me ha kase yung course outcomes
30 naman na kumbaga nahihit naman siya in the sense na nakakapagturo pa rin kami
31 kahit yung mga skill base tapos naasses pa rin namin yon yon so prang in terms kung
32 titingnan ko siya in terms if course outcomes and learning outcomes wala siyang
33 masyadong difference. Yung teaching style- oo! (Chuckles) Kase ani eh mas maraming
34 preparation and planning for online

35 P3: so halimbawa like right now kung um yung mga prerecorded lectures yon ano yon
36 even yung um preparation ng kase gumagamit din ako ng mga ibang modalities
37 halimbawa h5p yung mga ganyan so lahat yon titingan mo muna kung akma kung alin
38 dun ang pinaka okay na material bago mo siya incorporate sa lectures mo.

39 P3: what made me ready wala charot. (Chuckles) I think helpful yung nagMoodle

40 P3:Oo kase kahit papano mejo may idea ka how to go about tapos kahit papano
41 nakapagmigrate din ako that time ng mga materials eh ng kunyari halimbawa
42 worksheets for this certain subjects si that sort of di ko sinasabi napadali niya yung
43 buhay ko pero nabigyan niya ako ng idea kung paano ko siya kahit papano irurun yon.

44 P3:(chuckle) I did not feel that there was enough support on my end what trickled
45 down was kung ano na yung eto yung gagamitin eto ang kailangan gamitin may mga
46 lectures prior to that i think yung kay sir joshiko yung mga ganun lectures for blackboard

47 kase before naman kahit papano we're utilizing pero na eh di lang talaga siya 100% so
48 that was helpful but pero yung full blast na online i felt pa rin hindi siya enough. It was
49 mostly experiential yung parang nagresearch ka rin kaw rin mismo magfamiliarize
50 sa sarili mo dun sa platform so yon
51 P3: Actually majority of it is ano eh adjustment phase plus yung immediate na may
52 nirerequire sayo ng output i think we were parang at that time when the whole pandemic
53 started parang 1 week lang yun eh lalo na for internship parang 1 week kayong puro
54 classroom muna synchronous pero the next week kailangan magpasyente na so that
55 was ano yun yung major yung ina-ask or the demand to have a certain output while you
56 are still adjusting sa bagong ano yon
57 P3: During the initial phase ang pinakamahirap for me was internship kase yun nga
58 prang it was andami niyang planning in the sense.pati yung patient namin that time .
59 Halimbawa ito lang kaya naming platform kailangan namin talagang synchronous prang
60 ganon um tapos yung mga ganon bandwidth considerations yung mga ganon factor
61 pero sa ngayon parang pareho na siya pareho lang yung planning pareho lang yun ano
62 P3: Oo.parang pareho lang ang demand for me ha
63 P3:Hmmm Personally I dont think there's alot of difference kase the topics were
64 maintained ganon tapos kahit papaano nahihit parin yung outcomes. The only
65 difference is how we assess usually yung ano yung.. uh yung outputs mostly kase we
66 had to modify yun nga like for instance pag skills paano mo siya itatranslate into online
67 so yon um ...ano pa ba..... i think yon tapos yung preparation itself... kase before like
68 especially in classroom uh paggawa ko ng powerpoint pagpasok ko sa klase ok na yun
69 chuckles pero ngayon kase prang i also feel sometimes things get lost in translation
70 like in a classroom setting i would honestly know kung di naintindihan pero ngayon
71 kase with how things are kahit synchronous siya um not everyone gets to uh i don't
72 know why pero hindi hindi lahat nakakapagsabi kung naiintindihan nila yung material
73 right there and then during the lecture itself parang ganun. So i think yun yung mga
74 major differences niya. And then yung communication kase ngayon ano mostly email,
75 madaming email (chuckles),madaming discussion forum ganyan so yon mejo different
76 siya kase um uh when in face to face i feel mas ano ba yung communication line parang
77 mas mabilis parang na yon nasasabi natatanong agad kung meron di naiintindihan but
78 now yun nga kung kahit asynchronous or synchronous man siya usually yun yung line
79 of communication- email and forums yon.
80 P3: mmm okay before like for instance in one of the subjects in aural hab they would
81 have actual patients kase and that would be their practical tapos eval paper tapos
82 nagecase- pre sila for that now we have to make do of a recorded evaluation tapos
83 from there nila ibebase yung eval so what's missing ba eh yung actual na interaction
84 with the patient yon , one of those sa modifications although naretain namin yung other
85 outputs like evaluation report and case management pero yun nga yung actual
86 interaction with the patient and sa mismo mag din planning magfa facilitate ng actual na
87 eval and intervention yon mejo nawala yon um for other courses before kase we would
88 require them to present in a panel na face to face not much difference naging online
89 lang siya but the panel is still there nagkaron lang ng mga additional na ano parang
90 preparation before the exam halimbawa yung kapag written exam na revalida pag panel
91 presentation we had to check yung environment kung meron bang kodigo yung mga
92 ganung bagay

93 P3 I think the readiness, it was helpful i think that we had Moodle before kase that
94 natuto ka na mag ano eh mag parang may idea kna kahit papano idedesign and
95 transition yung mga bagay bagay. There were ano naman prior the pandemic there
96 trainings for Blackboard yon tapos if i remember correctly we attended a seminar na
97 pinresent yung Blackboard, tung different LMS, kahit papano may idea with ano but
98 having said thay yung actual na tlga na nagfull blast na i dont think everything that was
99 ano thought before was really made me very prepared yon
100 P3: Sige i'll come from the perspective of when it all started.(chuckles) It was hard
101 even yung first sem na full blast ng online kase ano all of those are subjects that were
102 previously thought face to face, so the planning, the preparation of the materials wether
103 I had to convert something para maging synchronous Asynchronous man siya na
104 activity yon it was, it was hard. I felt overworked more of that parang ganun parang I
105 was doing more than the work that I would've done had it been face to face so tung
106 transition na yan was really a stressful parang ganun, di parang ganun, ganun talaga
107 stressful siya! Oo yon um Was there anxiety Yes kase everything especially during the
108 first we were delivering it i was also questioning whether ano the activities i have
109 prepared or my assessments were they really hitting the course outcomes yon um over
110 time now kse 2nd run na siya ng mga courses. Mas ano ka na confident ka na. But that
111 was the sentiments that i had when i was initially starting the ano.
112 P3: One because I'm teaching the same subjects (chuckles) malaking.tulong yun that
113 the materials don't have to be tweaked as much and then you've also see have
114 feedback based on the results of the eval ay results nung course mo kung makikita mo
115 naman kung nahit mo naman yung course outcomes mo or hinde. So yon its ano1 and
116 then whatever difficulties mejo na- anticipate mo na siya so mas nakakapagplan ka
117 better now now that you are running it again. I think that's malaking tulong yon.
118 P3 i think time is really ano, time and training. Like one had it been na yung training for
119 Blackboard was ano ba prang if we were given enough time to really um parang get to
120 know, familiarize dun sa LMS yon and then second time itself to prepare yung materials
121 mo for your ano. Because you're not just looking at ano diba segments prang one day
122 at a tine what you are preparing the whole semester na parang for me I think one of the
123 difficulties then was really I felt I didn't had enough time to ano prepare yung ano mga
124 materials yon
125 P3 oh the first na transition there was resistance of course! andun yung reklamo na not
126 enough time given for the outputs kase yung mga outputs before na oh kailangan niyo
127 gawin or demonstrate in class now it has to be recorded so there is really ano ba
128 additional ano naman from them, additional work also for them noh, so yun yung mga
129 ganun klaseng reklamo, tapos i think when we initially transition yung face to face
130 classes to online. One of... Yun yung di naanticipate tlga is time for the students to
131 prepare so yon sangkatutak na reklamo sa , yung sobra sobrang outputs walang not
132 enough time to do the output. Overtime though because yun nga from yung the, when
133 you are running it again, ayon mejo na-anticipate mo na that twill be a problem so i was
134 able ano ba parang i was able, even mga ka team ko din were able to gauge how much
135 what is necessary, ano yung necessary na outputs tapos gaano katagal ibibigay namin
136 for a certain output.
137 P3 mmm yes yung other i think one of the things na initial na reklamo nila was it wasn't
138 really working for them because they are also transitioning from face to face to online so

139 it will take time before you get used to that kind of modality diba ng learning so some of
140 them that they are not motivated ganyan, um overtime though nagkaka-- i think now
141 they are so used to it kaya ano mejo nawawala na rin naman yung ganung klaseng
142 reklamo but those were the initial complaints.

143 Parang wala naman from the evaluations that I received in my courses noh, parang
144 wala naman reklamo in terms of yung, wala, wala actually wla eh.

145 P3: That's a good question, you know if they were also trained actually how to go
146 about it no na parang it's also not thrust on them kase I also felt that was what
147 happened eh na prang oh online na eto pak eto na mga kailangan nyong gawin
148 magkabalase pa rin tayo ganyan so um yon prang it was all prang they were never
149 given a time to process or go thru yung mga ano parang there was no orientation
150 regarding the LMS I remember ha parang it would have ease kung meron yon yon.

151 P3 Overall outcome, actually even, Ano ba i would say the outputs are a lot better now
152 i don't know if it's because most of the things are recorded so they can playback
153 sometimes kase in synchronous sessions or face to face sessions parang ano siya
154 when it's done, it's done diba tapos you're on your own to review so I think the
155 advantage of doing online classes, is yun nga everything is recorded they get to play it
156 back when they don't understand something yon um but i also see that ano um there's
157 not much difference in terms of skills also so kase I've been handling internship and
158 kumbaga lahat naman ng ginagawa on a face to face nagagawa pa rin naman siya
159 when we are doing ano online intervention parang ganon.

160 P3: I think it's the same whether i'm hitting the course outcomes at the end of the day
161 yun lang naman yung main ano ko eh um and then uh I think additionally also is yung
162 feedback then from the um hinde wait sige, next is yung output yung yung output ng
163 mga students, for me that is a good gauge also whether or not effective yung online
164 classes. Tapos yung lastly yung feedback from the students kase if it was not ano
165 naman if it was not effective for them wala din yung ano. It think yun mga main na
166 outcome measure.

167 P3: For me it is effective kase a the end of the day yung napoproduce mong students
168 who will be transitioning to internship and these students who are graduating and who
169 will become therapists anon I felt that whatever skill is needed para maging ano sila
170 maayos na therapist, entry level na therapist, effective siya but hard. Effective.

171 P3: um i think if you're going to introduce new modalities training is really needed for
172 ano for faculty members and for students as well. Those who are coming in na first
173 years maybe distance education maybe new to them some may have an idea from their
174 highschool but still the platform will be different diba so training is.... ako ha itrain
175 mona sila para ma- familiarize so that they also nagkaron ng added um anxiety syaka
176 added feeling ko cognitive load na without the training they are just ano ba sila na yung
177 hinahayaan sila, oh enrolled ka na bahala ka na tingnan mo yung subject ganyan it
178 doesn't parang nalelessen niya yung ano efficiency so kung merong training for those
179 who are starting with yung ano distance ed that will be helpful yun lang.

180 P3: Oh magandang tanong yan, nung naguumpisa I was hoping that they, for me,
181 students and the parents noh yung ano setting expectations yan tapos yung easing
182 them kase I think what was highly ano ba parang questionable then, is it as effective as
183 face to face nog, will my child still learn, nagsasayang ba ako ng pera, so yung mga
184 ganung klaseng, if they could have ano ba um topics on that para noh ma ease lang

185 tapos setting expectations din kase I feel also my god so sorry nakalimutan kong
186 sabihin na distance education is highly ano siya nagrerely sa motivation ng child eh ng
187 estudyante malaking factor yon tas ano so parang yung yon i feel yon baka kailangan
188 din yun i ano expectations from the student as well kase kung baka parang ako kung
189 parent din naman ako tapos magsstart na mag DE yung anak ko parang ano ba yan
190 parang anon naman yung anak ko nalang ang gumagawa parang panay ganito
191 ganyan parang ang dami daming ganyan so yung mga ganung bagay baka kailangan
192 ng ano dun additional lecture part na siya ng orientation baka pwede nilang gawin yun,
193 yung psychological aspect ng mga bagay bagay yon.
194 P3 I think when we were starting kase there were really ano students who expressed
195 verbally thru email that they are having a difficult time because yun nga it's not
196 motivating, they just have to turn on the video , they go thru the lectures but since we're
197 not there to really there to monitor whether they're listening or not parang its um for
198 them nalelessen yung motivation nila. Isa pa yung sa synchronous and then when
199 there's recorded lecture or sometimes ano parang feeling nila yun nga kase it's self
200 ano na siya eh yung sa oras nato gagawin ko siya or papanoorin ko siya gagawin ko
201 yung outputs sa oras nato walang nagmomonitor sakina oy kailangan mo siyang
202 gawin or natapos mo na ba yung ganun so i think yun yung mga bagay na ano, but yes
203 there were students who expressed concerns sa motivation. ----Yes I think that a better
204 term yung self-directed learning.

1 **P4's Transcript**

2

3 P4: Those courses were **articulation** and phonology and also I had the chance to
4 teach **voice lab** and then I did that with distance education also **dysphagia** classes
5 tapos face to face and online teaching and also **internship**, so I was part of the
6 **internship** team who handled interns for both face to face and distance education or
7 online internship sessions

8 P4: At first, all made big adjustments to accommodate the changes from face to face to
9 online modalities but some of the lectures during face to face sessions may also
10 somehow use online methods like we ask the students to access materials that were
11 recorded and then they will just submit their responses for that, but we had to....we
12 were going to meet at the next meeting so it's not really a full online part but when it was
13 the transition from face to face to full online modality it was quite difficult because all of
14 our lectures had been recorded or some of the concern for students were difficult
15 internet connection, their poor internet connection, same goes for me so I had problems
16 with my internet connection so sometimes it wouldn't connect during my synchronous
17 sessions and also yun it was a problem to me. It was a difficult time to adjust to it during
18 that time last year.

19 P4: some of the activities were for face to face sessions like um practical exams also
20 the....practical exams....and some of the sessions where interns were supposed to be
21 expected to be yon expected to be done in face to face sessions but then we had to
22 adjust and had to instruct our patients to access the online meeting and then conduct
23 there to there and also provide webinars or seminars for some of the activities that we
24 had to adjust to during that time.

25 P4: some of the things that we did also ma'am were practical exams for the students so
26 we wanted them to do a return demonstration during classes and we had to...uh .the
27 exams were transformed into an online modality, and some of the patient care so they
28 were ask to interview patients and then write their papers but most of the things that
29 were affected during the transition was the practical exams for articulation, for voice and
30 also the hands on experience by the students on how to conduct their assessment and
31 management for patients.

32

33 P4: Since the practical exams we had to... there were specific techniques or
34 assessment procedures that the students were expected to do so we had to change into
35 in..... into an online modality or sometimes we had to ask them to record themselves
36 and perform the techniques or the assessment procedures on their family members
37 instead of on their.....instead to the teachers or the instructors in...of the course. So we
38 had to just view the videos that they submitted

39 P4: It was difficult to actually transition from face to face activities into the online ones
40 because sometimes we had difficulties communicating with students who had poor

41 internet connection and sometimes some of the um the activities were not applicable to
42 other students with different type of learning styles. So it was difficult to adjust to it.

43 P4: Some of the students had difficulties learning through the online method but they
44 were able to adjust naman still, so it was difficult during the start pa.

45 P4: I think it was because of the how we communicated with them and also how we
46 provided very detailed guidelines written in verbal guidelines for these students, and
47 they were able to adjust as well during or with the circumstances

48 P4: I think most of what we did during the transition we had several meetings and also
49 we underwent training and also we had um faculty members who were trained to
50 provide um shared experiences with online modalities and some of them were uh some
51 the faculty members also researched also um did some readings on different studies
52 regarding online education so they also shared what they learned to other faculty
53 members so we learned alot from that.

54 P4: uh I think yes it was very effective for the dept and for me also because um the
55 only experience I had with online modality was ub for example I wasn't able to attend
56 my masters class so we had to do a conference call so I think that somehow an
57 experience for online learning but um not a full one but the training that we got actually
58 helped me become more confident in providing activities or lecture or educational
59 activities for our students with the online training and also with the meetings and also
60 the sharing of other faculty members.

61 P4: We had training on test construction so we um analyze the different test materials
62 made by other faculty members and then some of them provided feedback on by testing
63 materials. So...and then the we....the faculty members also provided suggestions on
64 how to improve it even that were doing an online modality and how um... we also
65 discuss the different best practices for each of the courses done during the semester or
66 the year and it helped us adjust to... or actually apply more certain best practices for
67 online methods just like providing formative activities and then providing feedback for
68 students and also providing a more specific rubric for each of the activity provided and
69 then discussing it to the students helped in facilitating those activities

70 P4: I think mostly trying to somehow....parang....teka.....I think what's difficult for me
71 and my students in the transition to online learning is how we conducted or how were
72 trying to live a normal life even that we are in a pandemic but we had to adjust and also
73 had to perform our responsibilities given that we are worried about this situation outside
74 our houses, and some of the concerns at home also affected the way we had to adjust
75 to this life I guess. So I think that's basically it and then also the poor internet connection
76 in specific areas so that contributed greatly to the difficulties because some of my
77 students whenever we had synchronous practical exam some students had...would
78 message me that their...they don't have electricity for that time, their internet is not
79 working and sometimes yon we had to accommodate and then provide another session
80 for them to be able to attend to their activities

81 P4: I think the difference would be we were able to provide direct feedback for our
82 students and then it involves somehow the hands on experience like for example when
83 were doing assessment on the oral motor structures of the patient, or sometimes when
84 we were required to our patients in their neck or in their facial structure so you that
85 affected the lessons greatly so we had to describe in very detailed manner on how to
86 how would the students gain their experience on how to touch patients or how to
87 provide hands on experience given that we're in a virtual modality

88 P4: I think most of the outcomes that were.....some of the outcomes didn't really change
89 that much during from face to face to online learning so I think they were still achieved
90 during both face to face and online activities since we already produced 2 batches of
91 graduates that were done in online internship I think it's okay we're still able to achieve
92 those learning outcomes even if they were provided online.

93 P4: I think so ma'am since um the lectures were or the topics given were the same and
94 also we tried to at least provide the um similar experience for practical examinations or
95 writing paper, writing evaluation reports, writing activity plans or writing therapy plans
96 so we tried to provide a similar experience with the face-to-face methods so i think it
97 was okay.

98 P4: For the practical examination so we had just like in face to face sessions we had a
99 an online room where it was just the instructor and the student, and then the student
100 will perform, he will provide instructions, perform the techniques on the professor, the
101 professor will pretend to be the patient and then try to ask questions and provide
102 feedback after the session so I think given that there is a rubric the students were able
103 to perform skills needed for the online practical exam. And also we had the students
104 observe different videos of patients and they had to create evaluation reports and then
105 we would provide them a rubric and then write their evaluation reports, provide
106 comments and also grade them using that method. So I hope that's um a way we had
107 to adjust to simulate the face to face type of activities with the students.

108 P4: mm i think the difference would be mostly be being in front of the students and also
109 giving them 1 on 1 feedback because sometimes some students were hesitant in
110 asking questions during online classes since everyone is um everyone is listening i
111 think so i think they had worries about that. The difference would be providing
112 sometimes the feedback given to students are individualized so instead of them
113 hearing the comments or the questions from their other classmates we had to , some
114 students would email questions and then sometimes those questions will be or are not
115 heard by the other students so we had to provide them extra effort to share what their
116 classmate asked and then how we answered so sometimes you the discussion needs to
117 be facilitated in the way that we have to ask each and everyone of the students rather
118 than being in a classroom because in a classroom you can see their facial expressions
119 , you can see their gestures or sometimes their confused faces so we can ask them

120 directly what are they thinking about and then how they feel about um discussing inside
121 the classroom.

122 P4: It was frustrating at first because it was very difficult to adjust from one method to
123 another completely so there were several meetings, several trainings that we had to
124 undergo in a short span of time it was frustrating and also it was yon and of course it
125 was time consuming And also it was very difficult for everyone but yes somehow we
126 were able to adjust to it and then manage the extra time that we had to provide in
127 making the materials because the difference between face to face and online is that
128 when you after you finish your lecture, after you prepare your PowerPoint presentation
129 you'll just discuss it with your students but for online, but for the online practice you had
130 to record yourself right after you finish your PowerPoint so um it would sometimes
131 make you work until late at night in order to finish that and also upload that um
132 presentation. Unlike when your in face to face yon you're just directly giving it to the
133 students... so it takes another time and then we're at home so it was difficult to
134 delineate when are you working for your work and also time for your family and also
135 responsibilities at home and the like.

136 P4: I think the most frustrating one is the additional time that we had to that we had to
137 had in order to adjust to online modalities since yon it would since the workload is
138 almost somehow the same with face to face in a way but you just had to do it here at
139 home but the additional time that are required to do it uh sometimes it overlaps with
140 responsibilities at home so i think that's the problem.

141 P4: For some subjects yes I think it would be appropriate. Like subjects that do not
142 require um physical manipulation of the patients. Like some courses like dysphagia,
143 motor speech, voice when we do our oral peripheral mechanism assessment it needs
144 direct contact to the patient and also some therapy techniques also provide a an
145 instruction where we use physical moves so i think some of the courses like that are
146 better with face to face sessions but some courses can still be provided purely online. I
147 think our course in Fluency, um adult language conditions, language for both pediatric
148 and adult patients i think they can provided purely online given that it's mostly
149 knowledge on how to handle or how to communicate with their patients, how to provide/
150 conduct assessment procedures that can be provided online. But the other courses I
151 mentioned previously um motor speech conditions, voice disorders and dysphagia
152 need face to face instruction.

153 P4: I think um there will be some courses that will be applicable for the BSSLP program
154 but a few instances wherein we have to teach students to physically manipulate our
155 patients or how to manage them hands on I think would need additional parameters on
156 training siguro for our students for us to ensure that they will be ready for yon dysphagia
157 practice, for OPM assessment and the like for our students so hopefully we're targeting
158 that yon on our online distance education training.

159 P4: I think distance education is a way we had to adjust on providing education for our
160 students given the times that we are in right now so all the adjustments had to be made
161 so I think distance education actually help um us to still provide quality education for our
162 students given that we're at home and also there were big adjustments that we can't
163 do because of physical social distancing or the pandemic.

164 P4: In providing lectures, adjustments in assessing the students adjustment in handling
165 sessions or intern sessions that are conducted online so I think those were the
166 adjustments like distance education provides opportunities for the students to perform
167 the SLP skills needed given that they are learning online so i think practice as well.

168 P4: I think more training would be the best practice for conducting online or distance
169 learning for our students . But I think the training provided by the co-faculty and by the
170 department is sufficient to provide quality education still. So If given the chance yes I
171 will attend more training, formal training, formal education but yon given that we're
172 able.to adjust to it and still target our learning outcomes and program outcomes I think
173 it's still a good experience all in all.

1 **P5's Transcript**

2

3 P5: Oh, okay. Um, several actually um, fluency should I be able to give you the course
4 codes, ma'am?

5 P5: Okay, so first of all is fluency, another would be uh, introduction to audiology, and
6 then I've also handled um, diagnostics uh, and then um... Ano pa ba courses ko? Uh, I
7 think- I think those three mainly uh, if we're talking about courses that I was able to run
8 in both um, settings both distance learning and face-to-face. Yes.

9 P5: I think um, speaking for our institution, I think we are of an advantage because um,
10 a portion already of our curriculum would utilize um, online means of uh, teaching. So
11 when we had to transition fully for distance learning, it was just about- you know, um,
12 identifying which uh, within the at- that we have would need to be translated into online.
13 So in terms of adjustment, of course, there is also some level of worry or some level of
14 uncertainty, but um, it was very helpful that um, the department has already been
15 equipped of um, ways for to be able to use online learning. So that was that um, the
16 adjustment period I think um, a couple of weeks just so everything gets settled and-
17 you know, all the students would be informed of how things will be running, but
18 generally, um, in my opinion, we were able to um, quickly adjust to the system and run it
19 as smoothly as we could have.

20 P5: Right. Um on top of my head, one perfect example would be and the- and the
21 easiest to translate would be the didactics or- or the lectures. So from uh, in person
22 definitely we were able to easily migrate um, those lectures into the online format either
23 synchronously or asynchronously. So we would either um, meet the students uh, on
24 time and run the lecture um, live or we would make recordings for them to access at a
25 given time no'. Um, sorry ma'am, can you say the second question again?

26 P5: Yes. Yes. Oo. Um, I think I- I describe it that way, I feel that it was quick kasi-
27 because um, to- yun nga. As I've said earlier, we already have a system in place that
28 we just had to utilize um, wider or um, use in more of our activities as educators and it's
29 also uh, I- I defined as quick because looking at our um, counterparts in the other
30 universities, I think um, we were able to um, move or transition into pure online uh,
31 considerably earlier than the other institutions. Uh, in fact, I remember correctly um, we
32 are the only institution that did not need to um, pause for a very long time before we
33 resumed in the online setting.

34 P5: Um, well, number 1, the support of the- the faculties is very important um, not- not
35 all of us are technically adept, so we have different levels of um, our ease of use of
36 technology. So um, it was-it- the way that the department has been able to share each
37 other's best practice and implement it um, in the different courses was very helpful.

38 Another thing would be um, the assistance that comes from our um, at- uh, technical
39 um, team in the institution, so there have been several instances during the transition
40 that we really needed them to prioritize certain request or certain um, uh, things that we
41 have to um, employ for our online learning. And lastly, um, the materials that the
42 department already has um, I think we were able to maximize um, the- the materials
43 that our um, online that our department has and use it as we tackle everything through
44 the online teaching mode.

45 P5: Right. Um, initially, I was very concerned if courses that needed to do laboratory
46 sessions, so um, we are very attuned to um, conducting our laboratory sessions using
47 simulations, using um, actual materials, sometimes, even actual patients and uh, it- it
48 was something that uh, we were uh, worried about because again it wasn't really
49 something uh- doing it online is um, very new in that particular manner. Um, another
50 thing that I was concerned about is um, the different um, learning um, capacities of our
51 students um, I feel like some students um, would be very comfortable learning through
52 online means, while um, I feel like there's also uh, a population of our student body that
53 would need more time for them to adjust to the new way of learning, so um, with that
54 there was also-as an educator, there was always this part in um, our minds that um,
55 would we have um, more ways to ensure that- you know, learning isn't um,
56 shortchange or sacrifice. I think one last thing would be when we do um, summative
57 activities, examinations. Um, I think, again because we have been used to doing our
58 exams um, face-to-face uh, there was a question of- you know, how- how do we
59 ensure the security of our exams, how do we uh, ensure that- you know, there are no
60 um, avenues for certain people to not be completely honest or uh, not be um, diligent
61 and um... Ayun, um, honest with completing their requirements. I think those things are
62 um, the top most concerns that I had during the transition period.

63 P5: Okay. Um... let's um- I think I gave three so I'll- I'll try my best to go through each
64 one. First, the concern about um, laboratory sessions um, so one of the things that we
65 were able to do is to maximize, again the online resources available for them to be able
66 to experience the same um, hands-on learning that we are providing in the lab sessions.
67 So um, it became a translation of uh, seeing patients in person into seeing per- patients
68 using Zoom or Google Meet or any other um- ano tawag dito? Platforms for video
69 conferencing um, another thing is again that no' yung- yung exposure to- actual
70 patients. Same thing we were able to um, facilitate- although at the start, it was uh, a bit
71 slow no' a lot of the patient, again they are also adjusting from being able to go to our
72 sites, our institution, to do face-to-face evaluations into turning on their devices and
73 doing it online. So eventually, um, I think for- for both ends, for the patients and- and
74 for our end, in the institution, we were able to find the middle ground and- you know,
75 conduct it successfully. As for the exams and the outputs, um, I think to things
76 happened in order to address concerns about that. Um, number one, is um,

77 implementing more secure measures in the conduct of the exams, so a lot of the
78 courses including the courses that I have handled have already um, created uh, a
79 suggest- a mandatory setup that would enable the facilitators of the exam to see the
80 environment of the student while taking the exam, to see what the students able to
81 access during the conduct of the exam, so uh, that was very helpful um, everyone was
82 very com- all the students very compliant um, specifically, when we ask them to do dual
83 camera setups when they use their laptops and another device just for us to be able to
84 see them while they take the exam. Another thing is that we went back into um, our uh,
85 objectives for uh, our outputs and for the course and we were able to translate uh, some
86 of the requirements, some of the written exam requirement, into other um, outputs,
87 projects, um, papers um, all the other um... all the other outputs that would still be
88 reflective of their learning without sacrificing um, yung- yung the measurement that we
89 need to see for what they have learned and how we are going to move forward.

90 P5: Okay. Um, first thing that came to mind was anxiety definitely. Um, again, I
91 mentioned earlier about not everyone has the same technological knowledge- you
92 know, not everyone has the same um... manner to which technology is being used and
93 one those people that are really not very good at it. So there was a lot of anxiety at the
94 start, there were a lot of um, hours spent on- you know, learning how to do things,
95 learning how create online um, materials. Um, a lot of the time- a lot of time was also
96 used familiarizing with what the other options there are online that we can use um, but
97 the thing about it is um, that anxiety didn't really last very long because again um, while
98 all of us were um, in- in that particular moment of adjustment, the support that comes
99 from my co-faculty members are also very um, very much uh- tawag dito? Um... sorry.
100 Um, I would definitely appreciate the assistance of all my co-faculty members because
101 they were the ones that facilitated- you know, how we could learn faster, how we could
102 learn together um, and it ended up well um, the anxiety uh, when it was all running
103 smoothly and we are getting positive feedback not just from our fellow um, faculty
104 members but also from our students. I feel like that was the marker that whatever it is
105 that we are implementing, we are implementing it correctly and we are being able to um,
106 ensure that the outcomes we have set for all of the courses that we are running are
107 being met.

108 P5: Mm-mm, um, a lot of it- if- if were talking external or outside of the institution um, of
109 course I had to also ask for assistance from um, people that I know are knowledgeable
110 with um, these things that we are going to be using for the first *a while* (??)- at least for
111 me, I'm going to be using for the first time. So I had to seek help from external people
112 that are um, more familiar with it, I had to do my own research no', I had to look it into
113 references or resources online that would help me um, understand better how uh, could
114 use these different modes online that was it. Institutionally speaking, I'll just going back
115 to it- institutionally, I think um, what the technological um, assistance that was given uh,

116 that- it was very uh- an'tawag-it was very sufficient. Um, they were very um, hands-on
117 and very um, particular about monitoring- uh, at least, in my opinion, monitoring how
118 we are all using the systems uh, and I think that was very helpful. Um, they're a phone
119 call-away, they're an email-away for-for concerns that we- I've- I might have for all the
120 platforms that we are using.

121 P5: Um, I think, looking back it could have been very helpful if um, there is an exposure
122 to more online means of um, teaching. Um, it would have been uh, a much easier
123 transition if the- the ratio of online and face-to-face prior to the pandemic was a little bit
124 more um, equal um, because um- at least in my experience, I remember uh, if I would
125 quantify it around ten- 15 to 20 percent of the previous um, school years have
126 encouraged online and 80 percent would be really face-to-face. Now, um, if there was
127 a... much stronger um... push for- for the education sector ay- for- for the teaching
128 faculty to maybe started transitioning certain aspects of um, the courses into online
129 means. I think that would be really helpful when it comes to um, being able to transition
130 much better for a full year of online learning. Another thing, I guess would be um- in
131 connection to that um, more training in the use of all these modalities, all these um,
132 platforms. Um... partly, I think uh, we are partly to blame because I-I think if I remember
133 correctly there have been instances when the institution would uh, provide um,
134 seminars or workshops regarding all of these platforms and back then, uh, since they
135 were optional uh, and- you know, as I am not very much into exploring that aspect of
136 teaching at that time I would- I didn't give much importance to those um, workshops, so
137 I- if- those workshops were more frequent uh, from the institution or if those workshops
138 were something that could be accessible at your own time, I think a lot of um- a lot of
139 teachers- a lot of the faculty members would definitely able to learn more in such a
140 shorter amount of time and be helpful with the transition.

141 P5: Uh, very important um, because uh, without the learning platform, I think it's going
142 to be a very disorganized um... run of any subject or any topic. Um... the advantage of
143 course of having a learning platform that is paid and has all these um, extended um,
144 services no', as comparing it to- you know Google Classroom for example which has a
145 lot of limitations because it's for free. The- the learning system that we are using-
146 basically if you understand it and you know how to um, maneuver it and use it to your
147 advantage as a teacher, you wouldn't have problems. You can make your exams there,
148 you can post um, post your lectures, provide forums, everything essential into ensuring
149 that the discussion is still dynamic even if it's not face-to-face. Ayon, I think those are
150 the very important points about the LMS [Learning Management System].

151 P5: Right. Um, well two- two things uh, would- would often happen for- for the
152 interaction part of it no'. Number one, uh, definitely is when we do synchronous
153 sessions, we still encourage- you know, discussions, recitation, group work um, even if

154 it's online. We can definite- now we know, we can use- you know, um, breakout rooms
155 for example that would be uh, the venue for- for certain, um, students to- you know,
156 come together and discuss and as teachers, we can just jump from one forum to
157 another. Um, for asynchronous sessions, what I have been doing is um, providing a
158 forum for discussion, so even if the interaction isn't um, live or- you know, directly
159 online or on time, at least using the- the forums um, the opinions and questions be still
160 be expressed and um, response from the- the teachers would still be provided and the-
161 the advantage there is since it's in uh, it's uh, written or it's typed um, the students can
162 actually um, go back to the discussion at any point in time if especially, if they have-
163 you know, things they wanted to um, review or to be clarified about there. Y-yon siya.
164 Excuse me.

165 P5: Actually, um, we were very- we were very particular about um, ensuring always- I
166 remember this time, last year, ensuring that all the program outcomes are being met, all
167 the course outcomes are being met. So, uh, I remember having to look at um,
168 requirements, the flow of the discussion, um, all of the aspects that we have put up and
169 um, constantly comparing them to the outcomes that we have set for the course. Um,
170 what I uh- what I would be very particular about is um, the fact we were able to um,
171 achieve all those outcomes that we have set, even if the mode of delivery was very very
172 different, so it was a learning experience also for us to broaden our perspective in a way
173 uh- broadening meaning, "Ow, we can still uh... successfully reach these goals even if
174 we do not do it in person."

175 P5: Um... if- if you're say- if you are asking if um, they're basically the same, um, I
176 would say, "Yes." I would say um, the expectations and the outcomes that we have for
177 the face-to-face um, courses, we were able to replicate it in the um, online um, mode of
178 teaching. Therefore, I would say they are um, both effective and um, both able to um,
179 answer for all the um, the- the requirements that we are setting no' for- for our
180 students.

181 P5: Um, distance education for me is- you know, um, being-conducting education
182 activities uh, in a nonphysical manner, in an online manner, that for me is what uh,
183 stands out when I hear or when I think about distance education. So, um- and um, the
184 perception before might be different, but now I have a better understanding that um, it is
185 not as different as a lot of people might think from- from person or physical um, ed-
186 um... traditional modes of teaching rather it's a new way of being able to teach these
187 concepts and teach these skills without the need for um, physical interaction, while
188 ensuring that- you know, your- your objectives are all being met.

189

1 **P6 Transcript**

2 **P6:** Okay. So, I handled language development from infancy to uh, school age. I also
3 handled uh, fluency disorder class. Mm I also, last year, I also handled uh...
4 interprofessional education– wait. I forgot, I'm so sorry. I am supposed to say the two
5 consecutive years of handling a subject or any subject basta with uh, as long as in the
6 four-year course curriculum?

7 **P6:** Uh, okay. Uh, yeah. So, not uh, IPE is not included 'cause that was uh, that was not
8 part of the old curriculum. So, it's just **fluency**, uh, school uh, **language development**
9 **from infancy to school age, language conditions**, and yeah, I think that's it.

10 **P6:** Um... we, we already– because I'm, I'm also an administrator, so um, even before, I
11 was actually one of those people who decided if, you know, we uh, the department will
12 be going um, online or face-to-face, so during the latter part of uh, 20– school year
13 2019-2020, we are already foreseeing that the classes will continue to be online, that it
14 is no longer just uh, temporary uh, situation. So, I was a bit um... hesitant initially
15 because um, the faculty at that time were so apprehensive with the transition so my
16 apprehension is not, does not really root from us not knowing what to do, but it's more
17 of the team believing that we can actually do it uh, because a lot of uh, the people are
18 not well aware of the uh, of how online classes happen. Um, I was fortunate because
19 during my graduate school, I've had like several courses which are purely online, so I
20 can have more or less an idea on how a course will run, on how the um, the outputs or
21 the exams happen, so I was a bit comfortable with going online, but uh, the issue that I
22 encountered is actually more of me being an administrator and, and um, trying to
23 convince the entire team that you know, we are equipped for the transition and again,
24 and convincing the students and their family that it would actually work. That was the
25 concern I had at that time.

26 **P6:** Well, we, we are very lucky 'cause we have uh, you and the team, and we also
27 have our educational specialist and it was more of like a team effort, of being able to
28 provide an example and provide the document and sharing what, you know, what you
29 could do um, and aside from that, it's just, I guess, later on, the people saw that this is
30 something that will continue to um, like the pandemic will persist over time for longer
31 period of time, I think they were able to understand that and that they were able to see
32 that, you know, the content will won't really change, it's just a matter of like preparing
33 the outputs, but again, during the first semester of 2020, I saw how it took a toll on the
34 faculty members because of, you know, how their workload increase like three-four-five
35 times no' um, like with me, I used to work approximately like 10-12 hours, but when the
36 pandemic started I work every day for like 16-17 hours just to catch up with all my
37 classroom duties and, and um, admin work, so I saw that it's the same for a typical
38 faculty member, so that was one of the things that um, I had to bargain with the higher

39 administration to shelter all the faculty members for the ad-on task that should be rolled
40 over to them, so which I think, they appreciated that's why, they were able to do it even
41 if it's really hard for them.

42 **P6:** Um... because I think, like we were more focused now on ensuring that each and
43 individual student is learning because we are teaching it in a different way, unlike before
44 um, when we see them or when we give exams, that's it, so um, what we did— the
45 change that we did—for, during the pandemic period, when we do the emergency
46 remote teaching, we had a lot of formative activities, so these are like more individual
47 activities or group activities with a lot of paperwork, so that, the amount of time
48 dedicated to checking those and doing synchronous and then having a lot of video
49 didactics. Uh so I think that eats up a lot of time as well, and preparing the materials
50 eats up a lot of time as well, especially for 2020-2021, that was the first time like a lot of
51 the faculty will be delivering the courses online, so a lot of people do not have pre-
52 recorded lectures and the likes.

53 **P6:** Right, so one of the difficulty I had while running language development from
54 infancy to school age last year, was that I am by myself, I don't have any partner, and I
55 have like 42 students. So... um, it's a foundational course for SLP, so one of the things
56 that they really need to learn is to understand how it 'cause— it is considered as a
57 backbone subject, so it is the foundational subject wherein all the higher uh, language
58 classes are um, anchored them, so one of the things that I had to visualize when I'm
59 transforming the curricula was that I have to ensure that these students really
60 understood the main ideas of the subject. So, previously, what we did in the class is to
61 provide um, a lot of group activities, but I, we saw during the first run uh, of the, of the
62 class when I was with the partner is that later on, when they were doing the disorder
63 component they didn't really understand the basic concepts of that subject. So, what I
64 did uh, during online, I gave a lot of um, individual work and then I give, I gave several
65 formative activities for them to complete, unlike the previous years, when we were
66 delivering it face-to-face, we didn't really have formative activities; we have like one or
67 two uh, activities that they could do as a group but none as an individual, so that's
68 something different, I gave like two or three formative activities and it's scaffolded so it's
69 like one activity uh, is-is anchored to the next activity, so they could also see the
70 progression of the case they initially picked and how the child evolve as-as the child
71 theoretically grew older and then with the output, I had two different outputs per term, so
72 I had like an individual output and group output uh, so that it took so much time (*laughs*)
73 so they, I then I had a lot more consultation periods during the class itself and during
74 the um, consultation period. So before, we would do lectures for four hours and then, or
75 sometimes uh, lectures for 3 hours and then group activity for an hour, so the way I
76 setup the face- uh, the online is that I gave a lecture for two hours and then independent

77 work for one hour and then uh, group discussion again after one hour, so it's-it's a
78 totally different um, delivery and that goes the same with um, fluency as well.

79 **P6:** Um... it's not siguro though- I think the only difference I can see is that we have
80 synchronous discussion and we also have online forum where people can post
81 questions and thoughts anonymously. Was it ano- ano, I don't think it's anonymous, I
82 think nakal- I think their names were written there, but um, there's also a- a form that
83 we developed, a google form wherein people will write in um, their questions in that
84 form. During that class, I think what's different was that we were able to make a contract
85 with the class because I was by myself, so you know, reaching out to 42 uh, students
86 was very very hard, so what we did is we grouped them and then, they have small
87 group uh, review, so uh, I forgot what's it called. Um, it's a group didactic wherein like
88 they teach one another and then, when someone does not understand something, that's
89 the time they consult with me, so they also learn from each other, I think that's one of
90 the very different um, things I did for last school year.

91 **P6:** Um, it was very very different, the summative asse- the summative assessment
92 was very very different because um, the lower order um, thinking questions were
93 delivered uh, during um, weekly quizzes, so the um, the summative assessments-
94 previously the summative assessments for language development was facilitated
95 through uh, multiple choice-exam, so it's more of like recall uh, task. This was during uh,
96 face-to-face, but we- when we migrated online, we had a lot more case analysis and
97 uh, application questions during the output, that's why it wasn't really an exam, it is an
98 individual output, so what will happen is that during the major exam, like a prelim,
99 midterm, uh, finals, oh not finals, prelim and midterm, they were given a case, they were
100 able uh- they were asked to apply the topics during that period uh, so for example,
101 previously, for the learning theories, you know, we uh, like when we did face-to-face, we
102 would ask like uh, confrontational (*laughs*) naming like whose, what this, like this, theory
103 says that blah blah blah], so for the- during the pandemic we asked them to provide
104 uh, like a therapy; an example of a therapy session that utilizes this theory etc. etc. So
105 those were like I think one of the differences that we highlighted during the ano- during
106 the uh, migration and we also took time to give them feedback individually, unlike
107 before, we just gave- return the paper and then, the- the case analysis sessions were-
108 were done in groups, so the- the student wasn't given individual feedback on his or her
109 understanding of the course. So during the migration, the group activities were scaled
110 down into individual output, so um, what I- what I did was I itemized all the problems in
111 the output, so that took like three weeks of checking (*laughs*), yun yung main difference.

112 **P6:** They were all saying that it was harder, somehow they feel like it's harder um,
113 towards- towards the end of 2019-2020 because the pandemic hit uh, around march,
114 so language disorder- the language disorder course previously was uh, was delivered

115 from January to March uh, using the face-to-face uh, setup and then, from march-
116 onwards, online setup, so because we weren't really prepared with the immediate
117 migration. The communication of the outputs weren't really given ahead of time, so it
118 was different this time is that we- I personally gave them like the major output were
119 already posted at the start of the semester and I think that is something that
120 the-surprisingly, it gave the student a lot of anxiety, seeing (*laughs*) the major output
121 posted ahead of time. I would think that they would be more prepared that they would,
122 you know, more or less have um, mental representation of what would be required, but
123 a lot of the students say that it gave them a lot of anxiety, so even if they were more
124 formative output um, majority of the students say that- that they were just so stressed
125 by it, that they were able not um, able to do it well, even with several examples. Um,
126 however, when I saw the output, so it was basically the same output for face-to-face
127 and the-during the prelim period, it was the same output for uh, the face-to-face and the
128 uh, online class. In the face-to-face, it was a group activity and- and the online, it was
129 an individual output. Surprisingly, the individual- the one for face-to-face had better-
130 way better uh, performance than that of- uh, the one in online had better performance
131 than that of uh, face-to-face, so I contribute it to more formative uh, activities. 'Cause-
132 um, for the face-to-face, they were only given like one session to apply their knowledge,
133 but for the online, they were given I think two-three sessions to really practice doing it,
134 so the student said that it was harder might- well, it's a general comment on my end,
135 that all my classes are hard, so (*laughs*) I don't think it's-there's a difference between
136 the face-to-face and the online pero- but the students um, towards to end the feedback
137 that I got was that they appreciated when they were doing disorder, the next semester,
138 uh, one of the laboratory assistants that I had, one of the instructor that assisted me in
139 the lab, told me the difference- 'cause she's the one who run the disorders with me in
140 the previous year, she said that there's some sort of depth in understanding and more-
141 the students were somehow more at ease with the cases we provided them when they
142 reached the disorder class, so- and the students also said that they more comfortable
143 uh, with uh, with- do you hear me? Do you? Can you hear me? Oh, okay. So the
144 students were also said that they were more comfortable with the cases because they
145 were already trained previously with uh, the- the case studies and case scenarios.

146
147 **P6:** Uh, I- you know, even now, I really question if we are doing it right, you know. Um,
148 it is- I- we were- I was asked to discuss in a symposium last November 'cause I- um,
149 CHED, the- the government regulation body thought that we had the best practice
150 amongst all four university And I was- as I was making my PowerPoint, I felt like an
151 impostor because I do not- honestly, I do not really know if this works. Um, I would think
152 that- 'cause the things that linger in my mind is that um, as I scour through the um,
153 internet about these practices and the application of you know, how making the

154 curriculum or individualize the— you know, when you reached through the online and—
155 and emergency remote uh, journals because I do not have an education background. I
156 always wonder if I am doing it the way it should be done, so I actually want to see the
157 third year now reach internship because they are actually the group who has majority of
158 their professional subjects delivered online um, so I want to see how they perform
159 'cause I think that would really be a measure of— if we did deliver it, though ano—
160 efficiently.

161

162

163 **P6:** Um, well, I always go back to the program outcomes and the year level outcomes.
164 So if they're hitting those outcomes— so when I sit down and eval— 'cause I also uh,
165 evaluate performance of the faculty and their teaching uh, skills and effectivity, I always
166 just go back to uh, you know, um, the program outcomes if they are *hitting* it and some
167 of the uh, techniques that was taught to me by a colleague um, so I always go back to if
168 they're able to facilitate critical thinking, if— if the students exhibit critical thinking, if they
169 exhibit self-directed learning, if they are able to appraise information um, if they are able
170 to— I don't know how to explain it in a— an educational uh, terms no', but if they were— if
171 they are able to look at how to implement the theory in a three-dimensional manner like
172 if they are able to translate it and connect theories with clinical practice, if they are able
173 to apply it in case scenarios, so those are some of the things that I consider important
174 whenever I look at the delivery of the course. So, when—when— when I was— we did a
175 program evaluation just recently and I was comparing it to the program evaluation
176 manual given to me by *Seaton Hall* and everything we need was in there, you know,
177 but for me, at the back of my head, I always worry if— kasi it seems too good to be true
178 that how are we able to really visualize it and do it with ease when all the rest are like
179 struggling (*laughs*), so it's just me being— I think being pessimistic. If, you know, if we
180 actually got it or we thought we got, but we didn't. You got what I'm saying?

181 **P6:** Yeah, um, actually, I was— I forgot who I was talking to. I was saying that— because
182 during the time that we were delivering the new curriculum face-to-face, the— the faculty
183 were stressed because it's a new curriculum and then, there's a directive of
184 implementing outcomes-based education, so it's a— it's a too— too prong issue, so a lot
185 of the faculty— I— I don't think a lot of faculty really grasped what *OBE [outcomes-based
186 education]* really is. So I think the difference with online is that you don't have any
187 choice, but to do *OBE [outcomes-based education]*. So I think I was telling someone
188 that—when I was going back to the notes regarding *OBE [outcomes-based education]*,
189 I— it actually hit me that we are more outcomes-based like we geared towards more
190 *OBE [outcomes-based education]* when we migrated to online versus when we were
191 doing it face-to-face. Yun.

192 **P6:** I– I had a lot of support from the department. I was– I always tell everyone even my
193 bosses that one of the blessings that the uh, department has is because we are uh– we
194 have the specialist needed to execute that, so within the department there’s a support
195 system like we have you, like someone who’s doing online, we have dean whose
196 doing– you know, who has a background on education, we have techy-people, we
197 have– you know uh, innovative people, and I think that really really help. Um, I think on
198 my end, I am always an out of the box thinker, so– you know, if there’s a situation that
199 needs to be proven right, it is easier for me to prove it right. So um, on my end, it was
200 more of– because at one point, I had to put a side all my doubts because I have to lead
201 a department and make them believe that this is achievable (*laughs*) so that was really
202 one of the struggle I had at the start ‘cause I was really doubting. So I had to um, just
203 really think of like do a SWOT [*Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats*]
204 analysis (*laughs*) on what could go wrong and then, and– yun nga, going back, the
205 blessings that we have, specialist in the team whom I– I consulted and– and were able
206 to– they were able to provide feedback on what should be done. So I think that made
207 the–the system easier. The problem with the other departments uh, that I know of is that
208 even if they have those specialists, they didn’t really include those specialists in the
209 program planning for the transition. They didn’t really plan as a department, they
210 planned as an individual. So I think that is why there were a lot of problems during the
211 delivery versus our department planned as a department, so that’s why um, there were
212 very little hiccup when we were uh, delivering the program.

213 **P6:** I was actually pretty– I was pretty satisfied with the way the students’ outcome–
214 final outcome were made and how the– I saw their evolution in looking at a situation
215 related to language and–language development and disorders from the time they
216 started with me in language development until the language conditions. So I was–I was
217 pretty– pretty proud, but again I’m not sure because this– the cohort that I handled from
218 language development to language disorder is basically a very good cohort. Um, I mean,
219 they’re very different batch compared to their predecessors, so I’m not sure if it’s an
220 intrinsic quality (*laughs*) in their end or if it’s uh, really the result of the teaching.
221 However, um, when I was discussing with one of the laboratory instructor, when I was–
222 we were trying to process the– the two cohorts. Um, she pointed out that the skill that
223 the third year– that the second year had after taking language development and
224 language condition significantly way higher than that of their predecessors who
225 underwent the same curriculum. Um, they weren’t really comfortable with um– the
226 previous ones weren’t really comfortable with cases and their thought process were
227 segmented um, unlike the cohort who underwent uh, peer online. They were very um,
228 concrete in their thought process, they are able to explain– you know, the evolution of
229 language development and apply it with the conditions, so very holistic thinker. So–
230 yeah– yeah, when I was delivering it my– by myself and I was doubting, I just go back

231 to rely on the program outcome and I go back to the videos that were made during the
232 previous summer about the online evaluation, about the uh... 'test construction cause
233 we had several videos made during the summer, going into uh, school year 2020-2021
234 and those were the videos that I uh, went back and checked it and rewatch it when I
235 have doubts just like check if I was adhering to what our um, specialist recommended.

236 **P6:** I think um, that's a- that's a very difficult question. How did- I think it's a- it's a
237 paradigm shift on- on- on your teaching process. It's just really- to say it simply, it's-
238 it's a really- delivering the same content, but thinking out of- well for me, thinking out of
239 the box, so the things, the techniques that I have been used to using for the past 17
240 years. I had to like really flip that way of thinking and- and become more student-
241 directed. I was- that's one of the thing I shared in the um, in the convention. Um,
242 distance learning actually forced me to be student-oriented, it forced me to be more
243 creative in- in eliciting- you know, the skills that are needed and- and to just- It's
244 sounds cliché no' but to just think creatively and- and used that framework because
245 before framework was I am here to teach you and you listen and you learn, but during
246 the pandemic it- it became um- it was flipped around and the framework was already
247 um, how do you learn and how are you going to learn this material and with the- with all
248 the constraints that are happening and without changing the outcomes and how the
249 program was designed. If I defined it well (*laughs*). Yun. That's- that's distance learning
250 for me.

251 **P6:** Oh my goodness, I don't- I don't think with could have survived if we didn't have the
252 technology that we do like LM- I'm surprised that a lot of universities do not have LMS
253 [*Learning Management System*], if we do not have the technical support from the um,
254 ICT [*Information and Communications Technology*]- from- I forgot what they stand for-
255 the- that information technology thingy. If we didn't- if we- if we did not study how to do
256 the video accurately, how to uh, do the quiz- the what was that? The Kahoot! and all
257 that technology. We couldn't have engaged this new generation of learners, to engage
258 and sustain engagement.

